

'DOING' DIGITAL INCLUSION: A PARTICIPATORY ACTION RESEARCH STUDY OF
DIGITAL INEQUALITY

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Abstract

The impact of digital inequality on marginalised populations, such as those experiencing homelessness or people who use drugs, is a complex and multifaceted issue. This thesis examines the ways in which digital inequality intensifies other forms of social inequality in these populations and how digital tools and technologies can play a role in addressing these compounded inequalities. To achieve this goal, I adopt an immersive, participatory action research (PAR) approach involving active participation from those affected. The research draws on the concept of digital capital, which refers to the resources individuals possess to navigate and effectively utilise digital technologies.

The study findings indicate that digital inequality can have far-reaching and significant impacts on marginalised populations, exacerbating existing social inequalities and contributing to further marginalisation. Access to digital tools and technologies can be essential in addressing compounded social inequalities, such as lack of access to education, employment, and healthcare, particularly for people currently using drugs. However, the study findings highlight the importance of trusted intermediaries or digital champions in addressing inequality and how compassionate care and kindness are integral to that work. Such intermediaries advocate for those experiencing digital inequality, providing support and assistance to help navigate the complexities of digital tools and technologies. The findings suggest that when support is part of holistic care, the impact of digital inequality can be mitigated, and positive outcomes can be achieved.

This thesis contributes to the ongoing research in this field of study. It demonstrates the importance of addressing digital inequality as a critical component of social justice efforts. It highlights the need for policies and programmes prioritising holistic support and meeting individuals' access needs. It also recognises the importance of trusted intermediaries in bridging the digital divide and addressing compounded social inequalities. Focussing on the lived expertise of those impacted by digital inequality and those seeking to mitigate that impact, this research contributes to the broader field of studies.

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Table of Contents

Abstract	2
Acknowledgements	3
Table of Figures	10
List of Tables	10
Chapter One: Introduction	12
1.1 Foreword: the personal, the political and the practice	12
1.2 Study background and rationale	13
1.3 Research questions	17
1.4 Structure of Thesis	18
Chapter Two: Literature Review	20
2.1 The development of digital exclusion – first level digital divide – barriers to accessing infrastructure	22
2.2 The development of digital exclusion - second level digital divide: digital skills and usage	25
2.3 The development of digital exclusion - third level digital divide – digital understanding	27
2.3.1 Identifying those most affected by digital exclusion - poverty	29
2.3.2 Identifying those most affected by digital exclusion – disability	31
2.3.3 Identifying those most affected by digital exclusion - age	32
2.3.4 Approaches to involving those affected by such inequality.	33
2.4 The development of digital exclusion - third level digital divide – digital understanding	33
2.5 Defining ‘digital skills.’	34
2.6 Digital Skills vs Digital Understanding	37

2.7 The complexity of barriers to digital inclusion	40
2.8 What works in addressing digital inequality and in addressing the absence of digital capital?	42
2.9 Homelessness: intersecting inequalities	46
2.10 Conclusion	47
Chapter 3: Methodology.....	49
‘Doing’ Digital Inclusion and Participatory Action Research	49
3.1 Introduction	49
3.2 PAR as a positive, disruptive agent for change.....	51
3.2.1 Strengths and critiques of PAR.....	54
3.3 An outline of a PAR approach	56
3.4 PAR and digital inclusion in Scotland	58
3.5. Personal positionality, expertise, and access in PAR research	59
3.6 Engaging partners for a PAR approach.....	63
3.7 Exploring PAR.....	64
3.8 Doing PAR’: working from the inside.	68
3.9 Participatory Action Research Cycles: Simon Community Scotland	71
3.9.1 First Cycle: Familiarisation and Problem Identification.....	74
3.9.2 Second Cycle: Get Connected 36	75
3.9.3 Third Cycle: Get Connected 100.....	76
3.9.4 Fourth Cycle: exploring a digital approach to harm reduction	77
3.9.5 Fourth Action Cycle: A digital approach to harm reduction	77
3.10 Summary.....	78
Chapter 4: Findings - PAR Cycles	79
4.1 Action Research Cycle 1 – Get Digital Scotland	80

4.1.1 Exploring the essential digital skills framework	80
4.1.2 The expertise of people with lived experience	80
4.1.3 The Framework and Toolkit: feedback from staff and senior leadership teams	84
4.1.4 Beyond the Framework	87
4.1.5 Action phase (first cycle).....	88
4.1.6 Digital Champion Training.....	92
4.2 Action research cycle: Get Connected or Get Connected 36	93
4.2.1 A pandemic response	93
4.2.2 Evaluating Get Connected	94
4.2.3 Staff Feedback on Get Connected.....	96
4.3 Action research cycle 3: Get Connected 100.....	96
4.3.1 Insights from Interviews	96
4.4 Action research cycle 4: ADATHR.....	98
4.4.1 Digital inclusion work in a harm reduction context	98
4.4.2 Insights from project participant data.....	99
4.4.3 Co-production as a Tool to improve outcomes	101
4.5 Findings from the Framework	104
4.5.1 Communication and Connections	105
4.5.2 Money matters.....	109
4.5.3 Leisure and Education	112
4.5.4 Finding Information.....	115
4.5.5 Health	116
4.5.6 Online Safety and Risk	119
4.5.7 Digital Literacy.....	121

Chapter 5: Findings and Analysis.....	123
5.1 Empowerment	123
5.1.1 Education	123
5.1.2 Data Privacy and Security	125
5.1.3 Agency, autonomy, dignity	125
5.2 The relational aspect of digital inclusion and digital champions.....	128
5.3 Digital Capital.....	133
5.3.1 Digital Capital and Digital Inequality	133
5.3.2 Digital Capital and Education	135
5.3.3 Digital Capital/Inequality and the Erosion of Social Networks	135
5.4 Harm Reduction	137
5.4.1 The Intersection of harm reduction and digital inclusion.....	138
5.4.2 Digital Inclusion and MAT Standards.....	140
5.4.3 Who is a service really serving?	143
5.4.4 Keeping people alive	146
5.5 The ‘Pressure of Use.’.....	146
5.6 Learning in partnership: the democratisation of the digital domain?	147
5.7 Reducing stigma.....	149
5.8 The Intersection of digital inequality, health inequality and harm reduction.....	150
5.9 Conclusion	151
Chapter 6: Conclusion.....	152
6.1 The research questions addressed	152
6.1.1 What is the impact of digital inequality on people who are already socially excluded and on those currently experiencing homelessness?	152

6.1.2 What role do digital tools and technologies play in addressing compounded social inequalities?.....	153
6.1.3 What is the most effective approach to involving those affected by such inequality in designing and developing digital initiatives designed to address social (and digital) exclusion? In what way does the trusted intermediary (or ‘digital champion’) contribute to or minimise existing power structures and hierarchies?	153
6.2 Contributions to Knowledge	154
6.3 Limitations of research.....	155
6.4 Recommendations for funders, policymakers and practitioners	157
6.4.1 Recommendation for policy: Devices and data still matter. The first level digital divide should be reflected in policy	157
6.4.2 Recommendation for Funders: Invest in participatory action research projects that disrupt existing hierarchies of power and social class led by those with lived experience.....	157
6.4.3 Recommendation across Private, Public and Third Sector: Digital inequality should be a shared responsibility.	158
6.4.4 Recommendation for policy: The intersection of digital rights, human rights and digital ethics should be reflected across policy.....	159
6.4.5 Recommendation for practitioners: Supporting the ‘trusted intermediary’: aligning digital inclusion work with the ‘day job.’	159
6.4.6 Kindness, love and empathy matter in both policy and practice.....	160
6.4.7 Recommendation for future research.....	161
6.4.7 Final remarks.....	161
Epilogue	162
Bibliography	163
Appendices.....	178
Appendix A: Essential Digital Skills Toolkit (SCVO): tested during the first research cycle.....	178
Appendix B: Co-designed Get Digital Assessment Tool used during first research cycle	178

Table of Figures

Figure 1- A Model for replications of inequalities in a digital society	28
Figure 2- DQ Global Standards Report 2019	34
Figure 3- The essential digital skills framework	35
Figure 4 - Number and percentage of adult internet non-users, UK, 2011 to 2018	36
Figure 5 - Dutton and Reisdorf's Internet cultures.....	41
Figure 6 - Five different types of digital champion.....	43
Figure 7 - Illustration of Action Research Cycles	57
Figure 8- Intersection of Knowledge Sharing in Digital Inclusion.....	59
Figure 9- Navigating Positionality.....	63
Figure 10- Everyone is an Expert in Their Own Experience	69
Figure 11- Action is Part of Our Research	70
Figure 12- Bringing About Change.....	70
Figure 13- Your Time Is Your Own	71
Figure 14- Timeline: Cycles of Action.....	79
Figure 15- Impact of Devices on Participants' Lives	97
Figure 16- Illustration of the basic functions of the app designed by women for women.....	118
Figure 17- Positive support leads to positive outcomes.....	136
Figure 18- Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs with an Overlay of Essential Digital Skills	144

List of Tables

Table 1- The digital divide in the context of pertinent social determinants of health.....	16
Table 2- Adapted table on the continuum and implications of positionality	61
Table 3- Data on purposes for which the devices and data were used (Simon Community Scotland)	97
Table 4 - Alignment of principles of harm reduction and the overlap with digital inclusion, based on Hawk et al. 2017	138

Table 5- Alignment of MAT standards with digital inclusion activity 140

Chapter One: Introduction

1.1 Foreword: the personal, the political and the practice

The first iPhone was released onto the market in 2007, giving those individuals with the money to afford it immediate access to the online world and opportunities, information and services wherever they were and whenever they needed it. To a certain extent, the introduction of this particular mobile device accelerated the speed of digital participation in a way that no other device to date has done, and the smartphone became ubiquitous. However, the smartphone also immediately delineated between those who *have* and those who *have not*, with access to knowledge, education, employment, leisure, and even friendships, all marked by access to a digital device.

Before this point, I had worked in the nonprofit sector for all of my adult life, working in different spaces with various charities and organisations, working directly with other people impacted by a wide range of always-intersecting social inequalities. It was clear to me, even then, that this newly emerging technology could make things harder for people already impacted by systemic injustices. Not long after the introduction of the iPhone, I began to work specifically in the field of digital inclusion, working for a prominent UK charity supporting people who were offline. Initially, I worked across the Highlands and Islands in libraries, community halls, and cafes to help people use their laptops, sometimes to use public access computers, but rarely, at that point, to use handheld mobile devices. Then, it was generally considered to be older adults who were most impacted by digital inequality. Many funders and public service providers felt it was an issue that would pass with time.

However, as mobile technology became more commonplace, systems and platforms were rapidly developed and rolled out at scale, which, even though they may have been intended to support those most, indeed, would be built with inequality and exclusion, sometimes at heart: a 'systems' first approach. I could see from my work in communities the way digital systems were evolving and the way in which digital inequality was increasingly a social issue, and that, as always, those facing the most significant challenges, such as systemic poverty, and disability, those most marginalised by society, were most likely to be impacted negatively. So, over the years I

worked in the space, our work moved away from work specifically related to older adults and turned to those most affected by structural inequalities, and my practice evolved accordingly. At that point, I worked for a U.K national charity. Laterally, the agenda of the Scottish Parliament and the devolved issues in Scotland, such as health and social care, impacted the charity's ability to deliver digital inclusion work in Scotland. To meet this emerging need, I worked with colleagues to set up a new community interest company, Mhor Collective, to address the work required in the devolved nation and to underpin the work of The Scottish Council for Voluntary Organisations (SCVO,) which the Scottish Government has tasked to develop nationwide digital participation. SCVO is a membership organisation working across the third sector on a broad agenda of policy, advocacy, promotion and support of voluntary organisations. However, over the last decade, it has worked to ensure a collaborative national approach to address digital inequality, drawing on best practice in Scotland and beyond. UWS had also been part of this work, creating an Evidence Review offering insight into the most current research. This backdrop and these contexts offered me a particular privilege of access and the opportunity to combine personal, professional and academic spheres. This PhD is a studentship funded by SCVO and deeply rooted in immersive practice. I was aware that despite the significant amounts of emerging literature related to the field, with substantial levels of quantitative data and although it highlighted the link between social inequality and digital inequality, the voices of those most impacted were often absent. I was immediately drawn to the opportunity to explore this space as a social justice issue, to align research to my personal and political beliefs, and to work in an active way, led by those most impacted. Through this research, I hoped to be part of a group seeking to challenge existing power structures, understand both challenges and solutions and, most importantly, effect change and try to make things better. I believe we achieved this, although there remains much to do.

1.2 Study background and rationale

At inception, the internet was imagined to be an opportunity for equality on a global scale, a possible force for good that would unite people, regardless of class, ethnicity, gender, social grouping, or ability: a universal force for good. Vint Cerf, the developer of the internet protocol suite, and (Shimei and Lavie-Ajayi, 2021), one of the 'founding fathers' of the world wide web, asserted boldly that 'the internet is for everyone,' maintaining that access to the internet should be a fundamental human right (Cerf, 1999). The reality, however, does not match

this aspiration. Instead, an ever-growing body of academic research shows that digital technology is unequally distributed, connectivity and data unequally accessed, and that the application of that technology seems only to replicate further and exacerbate other social inequalities, compounding multi-layered exclusion and contributing to widening marginalisation. (JAM Van Deursen *et al.*, 2017)

On a global scale, the most readily available data highlights digital inequality focussed on connectivity and device ownership, showing a marked difference between the Global South and the Global North. Europe has long enjoyed significant infrastructure and connectivity investments, with some nation's Wi-Fi access and relative affluence resulting in comparatively higher levels of digital participation. Estonia, for instance, demonstrates significant advances in active digital citizenship, supported not least by a world-leading digital infrastructure. However, this superficial consideration of digital inequality as aligned to connectivity and device ownership masks a more profound challenge: the evidenced alignment of digital and broader social inequality.

Before March 2019, the impact of digital inequality was often underestimated in the public domain and, although an identified priority for the Scottish Government to enable 'everybody to share in the social, economic and democratic opportunities of digital' (Scottish Government, 2017), such policies nevertheless often seemed to have little impact on the ground in terms of the direct delivery of work supporting those facing digital inequality, with services focussed heavily on immediate face-to-face delivery and digital services focussing on those who could, rather than those who could not access them. In 2018, digital inequality impacted almost 20% of the UK population and older people, people affected by poverty, people with disabilities, and people not in employment, education, or training (*Lloyds Bank Consumer Digital Index 2019*, 2019). Digital inequality, in other words, crossed the lines of already established social inequalities, compounding the negative impact of digitisation and contributing to wider hardships such as intersectional discrimination. Yet, work across the public sector to address this issue was limited and led primarily by the third sector.

Covid-19, however, altered this landscape completely, necessitating urgent and immediate change, as all aspects of community were moved into the online space, which suddenly and ubiquitously provided a necessary lifeline for citizens to access health and well-being services, education, employment, financial support, connection with loved ones and much more. But for those offline, without digital skills, connectivity or access to devices, the impact of digital inequality suddenly became a matter of life or death. Covid-19 emerged first in Wuhan and then

quickly crossed continents and would progress to take millions of lives. As countries locked down, economies were frozen as the virus took hold. As the pandemic spread worldwide, the correlation between health, well-being and digital engagement became increasingly apparent. Governments, supra-national health organisations such as the World Health Organisation, and national agencies, including the NHS, moved to digital platforms as the primary source of dissemination of vital information. (Beaunoyer, Dupéré and Guitton, 2020). In the UK and across the world, schools, colleges, and universities closed their doors and education was moved heavily online. The internet became an urgent, vital space for citizens confined through necessity to their own homes, enabling basic needs to be met, including social connection whilst in isolation, shopping for food, access to health information and practical medical support (as GP surgeries and pharmacies in the UK moved online); education; accessing financial support including furlough schemes and benefits systems. Indeed, the internet became the only space for civic engagement and access. However, the pandemic also illustrated sharply the impact of digital inequality. Researchers immediately seized on the societal implications of Covid-19 and the absence of digital access, 'the COVID-19 pandemic represents the first large-scale event for which digital inequalities become a major factor of vulnerability, both to the health-related impacts of the exposition and the spreading of the coronavirus, and the socio-economical consequences of the pandemic.' (Beaunoyer, Dupéré and Guitton, 2020). Furthermore, researchers also highlighted the way in which the absence of access impacted on particular groups. On a global scale, connectivity was raised as an issue, with developed countries in a better situation to offer a digital response. In 2020, 55% of households across the world had an internet connection: in the developed world, this connectivity was enjoyed by 87% of the population, compared with only 47% in developing nations, and falling to only 19% in the least developed countries (ITU, 2019) demonstrating the global digital divide and correlation with national wealth. Again, this divide immediately impacted on those already facing wider social inequalities, and it is argued their covid-related health and wellbeing outcomes. In developed countries, the pandemic further exacerbated existing inequalities experienced by marginalised groups, including those differentiated by 'economic class, gender, sexuality, race and ethnicity, ageing, disability, healthcare, education, rural residency, networks, and global geographies' (Robinson *et al.*, 2020).

The pandemic also offered a clear demonstration of some of the theoretical discussions which form the basis of this thesis and, in particular, the way in which Bourdieu's theory of capital is reflected in conversations around

digital inequality both during the lockdown and before. Covid-19 brought the relationship between digital and health disparities to the fore: health research had already demonstrated the importance of economic, social, and cultural capital in understanding health inequalities, for example, Pinxten and Livens who reflect specifically on mental health (Pinxten and Lievens, 2014) and Song who summarises explicitly ways in which social capital can enhance health (Song, 2013). Gonzalez et al. find that ‘network support is a relevant predictor of self-rated health status cross-nationally, while social participation and interpersonal trust are robust to its addition. We also find that income inequality moderates the association of social capital and self-rated health, indicating that a disintegrated society negatively affects the health of individuals, more so in countries where income inequality is high.’ (Gonzalez, Fuentes, and Muñoz, 2020). The notions of ‘network support’ and ‘interpersonal trust’ are explored in this thesis as the focus is on the use of digital champions, embedding work to minimise the impact of digital inequality as part of holistic models of support to address broader social inequalities.

Returning to the context of digital inequality and the impact on health during COVID-19 specifically, Ramsetty and Adams highlight the digital divide in the context of pertinent social determinants of health (Table 1).

Table 1- The digital divide in the context of pertinent social determinants of health

	Built environment	Social & community context	Education	Economic stability	Health and healthcare access
Contributions to the digital divide in health care	Lack of broadband Internet availability region-wise; limited access to free public Internet in community buildings such as libraries; absence of structural support/housing insecurity	Shared or cultural expectations regarding use of digital devices, telehealth, and telemonitoring; mistrust of technology and the medical community	Literacy; varying degrees of digital literacy; inconsistent or unavailable education regarding changes in technology	Inability to purchase devices or upgrades; affordable devices may not have the capability to work with proposed programs; inconsistent access to devices due to economic instability	Choices of technology/programs heavily tied to reimbursement; healthcare systems likely to pursue advanced technology that may outpace patient capability; patient comorbidities may affect the ability to use technology effectively

Source: (Ramsten *et al.*, 2018)

This table encapsulates one of the key reasons why the pandemic brought digital inequality to the forefront of public discussion: the ‘digital divide’ not only impacts on social and economic well-being but immediately and clearly on health outcomes and on the individual’s ability to keep safe and well during a pandemic and, ultimately, beyond. For example, within the United Kingdom, the national lockdown meant an immediate loss of face-to-face healthcare, requiring us to engage digitally to access information and medical support.

1.3 Research questions

Pre-Covid, debates in both academic and policy communities around the issues of both digital inequality and digital inclusion stressed that possession of basic digital skills and the right technology is insufficient to ensure that the most vulnerable members of the population can participate effectively in an increasingly digitally mediated world (Helsper & Eynon, 2013; White, 2016). Covid-19 highlighted the urgent need to generate more robust evidence of the relationship between digital skills and digital understanding and application of both to ensure that people can access and use digital devices and associated platforms for positive economic, social, and cultural outcomes (Bach, Shaffer, and Wolfson, 2013).

To achieve this, there is a need for more focused research into the *types* of digital usage, the practices associated with that usage and the extent to which people ‘understand’ the implications of their use in terms of accessing information, exploring opportunities, security, privacy, and informed decision-making (Piercy, 2016). It is essential to analyse what access to and use of digital tools and technologies afford or enable and what they may prevent or deny. There is a need for citizens to develop ‘critical digital citizenship’ (McGillivray et al., 2015) or ‘digital understanding’ so that they can be ‘sceptical’ of what transformations the digital world will produce and access the opportunities that are relevant to them. There is also an urgent need to understand how agencies working to support people in marginalised and oppressed groups can either empower or inhibit digital participation.

Van Dijk’s ‘resources and appropriation theory’ (Van Dijk, 2017a) determines that:

- ‘Categorical inequalities in society produce an unequal distribution of resources.
- An unequal distribution of resources causes unequal access to digital technologies.
- Unequal access to digital technologies also depends on the characteristics of these technologies.
- Unequal access to digital technologies brings about unequal participation in society.
- Unequal participation in society reinforces absolute inequalities and unequal distributions of resources’.

(Van Dijk, 2017a)

Each of the participatory action research approaches in this thesis considers the various elements highlighted by Van Dijk, including ensuring access to resources and digital technology, and explores the varying discussions laid out by Helsper (2021), Van Deursen (2021) related to the social causes and consequences of digital inequality.

The research questions therefore addressed in this thesis are:

1. What is the impact of digital inequality on people who are already socially excluded and on those currently experiencing homelessness?
2. What role do digital tools and technologies play in addressing compounded social inequalities?
3. What is the most effective approach to involving those affected by such inequality in designing and developing digital initiatives designed to address social (and digital) exclusion?
4. In what way does the trusted intermediary (or 'digital champion') contribute to or minimise existing power structures and hierarchies?

1.4 Structure of Thesis

In Chapter 2, the thesis critically explores the literature relevant to the discussion, reflecting on the evolution of the academic debate on digital inequality, encompassing broader discussions around first, second and third-level digital divides. The review also explores *who* is offline, identifying those communities of people most likely to be affected by digital inequality and considers some of the frameworks used in practice to gather data around essential digital skills, making the case both for the research undertaken for the thesis itself and also for a more profound, more participatory way of conducting research which might facilitate greater understanding of Ragnedda's assertion that digital capital should be considered an emergent capital (Ragnedda, 2018).

In Chapter 3, I then explore the methodological approach, highlighting how a participatory action research approach allows us to better understand the challenges facing offline people and how such exclusion can be addressed through co-designed cycles of practical action and reflection. Using a participatory action research approach, this study explores, through close partnership with third-sector organisations and informed throughout by the expertise and knowledge of lived experience, both the way in which digital inequality impacts specific marginalised groups and how also positive models of intervention developed for and by individuals within those groups, can contribute to more effective digital participation. Furthermore, the discussion on this methodology opens a broader exploration of how a participatory action research approach seeks to disseminate traditional power hierarchies, with lived experience at the heart of any research. Finally, this chapter introduces the third sector organisation engaged in the research.

In the findings and analysis chapters, I explore the impact of this participatory action research, particularly the emerging themes that contribute to a wider discussion of digital capital and how the digital space amplifies existing inequalities. I also explore how people, when given appropriate support in a meaningful context, can develop digital understanding to apply to their everyday lives in ways that will benefit them materially, practically and socially. These chapters also explore the way in which the *type* of engagement this research affords, the PAR approach underpinned by a Frierean insight, specifically, leads to a relational engagement which empowers participants to effect change, which can then offer insight and direction at national and strategic levels.

Finally, it is important to stress that the overarching aim of the research is to inform practice and policy by putting lived expertise at the centre, demonstrating that active participation can impact understanding and wider knowledge in the field. The final chapter, therefore, offers recommendations not only for further research but also for policymakers and those working in the space to minimise the impact of digital inequality.

Chapter Two: Literature Review

There can be little argument with the evidence that digital access and opportunity affords social and material benefits, which is an essential backdrop for the research. The most recent Lloyds Consumer Index presents social and economic benefits in clear terms, emphasising that ‘compared to those with less digital capability, being Digital First creates both economic and social value:

- 75% save money online, including paying up to 6% less a year for utilities.
- 84% connect with family and friends online.
- They are 1.7 times more likely to have improved their job prospects.
- 57% have improved their employability through being online.
- They are nearly twice as likely to have disposable income, with an extra £800 to spend per year (those with lower incomes who are Digital First are also more likely to have more disposable income)
- 42% are managing their physical and mental health through being online’ (*Lloyds Bank Consumer Digital Index 2019, 2019*)

The economic and social benefits associated with meaningful digital participation are also highlighted in other reports. CEBR relates these benefits to eight key areas of positive impact on the individual (*CEBR 2018*):

- Earning capacity: earning capacity is increased by between 3%-10% for an individual possessing essential digital skills.
- Employability: there are clear employability benefits in a society where almost 90% of jobs require essential digital skills (*Lloyds Bank – UK Consumer Digital Index 2018, 2016*): CEBR notes that there are increased employment opportunities for those in possession of essential digital skills with further chances to seek and secure employment.
- Transactional benefits: there are transactional benefits for the individual as well, with online shopping providing an approximate saving of 13% compared to in-store shopping.
- Social inclusion: the internet also has the capacity to support greater social inclusion, allowing for increased communication opportunities: those with essential digital skills are 14% more likely to contact family and friends.

- Time-saving: Digital access and the ability to use digital skills impacts an individual's time- an estimated 30 minutes per transaction can be saved by accessing government services and banking online rather than in person.

Good Things Foundation summarises the critical disadvantages of digital exclusion: poorer health outcomes and a lower life expectancy, increased loneliness, social isolation, and less access to jobs and education (*The economic impact of Digital Inclusion in the UK A Report for Good Things Foundation*, 2018). The internet is also being used increasingly to interact with public services – although growth in this area has been variable – with 32% of UK citizens completing online forms for government services in 2014, dropping to 28% in 2016 and rising again to 42% by 2018 (Office for National Statistics, 2019).

For young people, the internet can offer a vital means of support – with more than a quarter of young people aged 12-15 reporting that they are more able to be themselves online rather than face to face. At a nation-state level, the stakes are also high. For example, it is estimated that digital exclusion at current rates will cost the United Kingdom a loss of around £22 billion (CEBR, 2018). But wider digital participation and developed digital services will allow for the supply of more efficient health services as patients are able to make the most of online NHS services such as NHS Near Me in Scotland, greater digitisation of government transactions, and addressing recruitment issues related to the shortfall in digital skills, leading to greater productivity and increased output (CEBR, 2018).

Additionally, Van Deursen and Mossberger highlight the potential positive societal and economic impact of the Internet of Things (IoT) over a wide range of domains, including energy, health, transport, and policing and public safety – but advise caution that these positive impacts will be hindered if individuals cannot engage with such systems. They also find that policymakers should be cognisant of this issue to avoid increased entrenchment of the digital divide as the IoT may further disadvantage those lacking the essential skills to use the technology ((van Deursen and Mossberger, 2018)).

Discussions around loneliness have also been a focal point for research. Wilson considers the potential positive impact of digital technology on the emotional well-being of older adults (Wilson, 2018), with research 'suggesting a fine balance between technology use to improve self-esteem through connections with social networks and an over-dependence on technology that can actually reduce feelings of belonging'. Wilson notes, ' There was

qualitative evidence, however, that technology encouraged older adults to communicate with friends and relatives, especially through emails. This communication and how easy a device was to decipher positively impacted older adults' perceptions of self-worth, which correlated positively with the frequency of use. Alternatively, if participants found technology difficult to use, this had a detrimental effect on self-esteem.' (Wilson, Grant and Carnegie United Kingdom Trust., 2017, p68) Again, this evidences the importance of a multi-faceted approach to digital engagement, with cognisance of an individual's circumstances.

Recent statistics also highlight the challenge of digital in the workplace, with sources drawing attention to the fact that not everyone in employment is in possession of all essential digital skills. Although there was a 15% increase in the number of people who use the internet regularly for work – the figure being 54% in 2019, an increase from 39% in 2018 - more than half of UK employees (53%) do not have the Essential Digital Skills needed for work (e.g. able to avoid suspicious links and pop-ups, share documents by attaching to an email, use online payments etc.) One-third of the workforce lacks cybersecurity skills. Furthermore, only one-third (34%) of employees say their workplace gives them digital skills support. (*Lloyds Bank Consumer Digital Index 2019*, 2019) There is clearly work to be done to engage a fully digital workforce.

Given this backdrop, evidencing the essential nature of the internet for health, wellbeing, education and employment, it is helpful now to explore the discussions on the 'digital divide'.

2.1 The development of digital exclusion – first level digital divide – barriers to accessing infrastructure

As highlighted by Robinson et al., 2020 marked the 25th anniversary of the phrase 'digital divide' being used in academic literature and beyond to highlight the impact of differentiated internet use on individuals (Robinson et al., 2020), further exaggerating existing social, cultural and economic divides. This literature review explores different aspects of the 'digital divide' and considers some frameworks used to measure the impact of digital skills interventions. The review will also explore the literature related to the 'trusted intermediary' or 'digital champion' model of support for digitally excluded individuals. Furthermore, as the research context is both practical and field-based, consideration will also be given to findings from grey literature that often inform this fast-moving space.

In the mid-1990s, discussions about 'the digital divide' emerged as technology raced swiftly forward to such an extent that the internet impacted all areas of work and life. This seismic change was further accelerated with the introduction of smartphones, giving the individual pocket access to infinite sources of information and opportunity. The evolution of the internet and the impact of ICT on the everyday lives of individuals is comparable to the effect of the industrial revolution, and the 'globalised information economy' (Stevenson and Domsy, 2016, p58) is now, for governments and individuals, a vital component of economic and social progression ((Selwyn, 2004)). Castells references the 'network society': a 'society where the key social structures and activities are organized around electronically processed information networks ... not just about networks or social networks, because social networks have been very old forms of social organization. It's about social networks which process and manage information and are using micro-electronic based technologies.' ((Castells and Cardoso, 2005, p187). Castells' networking logic substantially modifies societal operation and outcomes in production, experience, power, and culture processes. Individual autonomy, freedom, education, and suffrage are all affected by a structure permeated with digital networks.

The 'first level digital divide' refers to that divide related specifically to *material access* and often specifically to connectivity. In a global context, the internet has become an essential utility, comparable to electricity and water supply. It is a vital access point for health, education, employment and more and is now an integral element of social and economic progression (Selwyn, 2004). Historically, academic literature reflected on the relationship between social inequality (specifically poverty) and digital connectivity and saw material access as the primary objective, which, when available, would then 'remove' what was perceived as the key obstacle.

In the mid-1990s, discussion began to focus on the 'first level of the digital divide'. The effect on society was a clear demarcation between the 'haves' and the 'have nots'. The discussion focused on societal inequalities regarding access to technology and the infrastructure supporting that access. Movements such as 'Final Third First' sought to petition UK Government to embed equity of access with a clear focus on those disadvantaged by rurality, asserting that 'the 30%+ of the UK where market failure is predicted for next-generation access and superfast broadband – should be the first to receive public sector intervention and support.' (Final Third First, 2010). The discussions here tended to focus heavily on economic growth and potential and the impact of lack of access on business rather than on the exacerbation of societal inequality. Within a Scottish context, the Scottish Government's ambition concerning infrastructure was evident in 2011. It outlined in the infrastructure action plan

as part of the Scotland 2020 Vision, which states the Scottish Government's commitment to a 'world-class, future-proofed infrastructure that will deliver digital connectivity across the whole of Scotland by 2020'. (The Scottish Government, 2012, p1)

In a particularly passionate article, Stevenson (2008) highlights policymakers' use of the 'digital divide' in the US as a 'rhetorical trope in a neoliberal ideology', which placed 'responsibility for social and economic success in the emerging global information economy at the level of the individual and not the system, effectively foreclosing on any class-based analyses of the problems associated with the transition from a Keynesian welfare state and industrial economy to a neoliberal and globalized information economy.' (Stevenson, 2009), p232). Her article relates mainly to the discursive focus on public libraries, explaining the risk inherent when the discussion focuses on issues of infrastructures and access to devices: 'Unpacking the discursive significance of the "digital divide", with special focus on public libraries and projects of the Gates Foundation, illuminates how it foreclosed on the possibility of alternative problem definitions by making the problem a technical and administrative one rather than an issue of historic class struggle.' (p.235)

However, despite the evidence pointing to improvements in the aggregate figures relating to the extent of digital exclusion, a deeper dig into the data suggests that some systemic issues continued to prevent some groups from accessing the benefits of the digital world remain. For example, research by the Prince's Trust Wilson et al. established that the urban/rural divide in digital uptake appears to persist (Wilson, Grant and Carnegie United Kingdom Trust., 2017). Infrastructure remains a core element of this disparity, with 'deep rural' and 'remote and rural' areas facing the most significant challenges. In a further 2017 Carnegie UK Trust report, Bowyer highlights that 12% of rural premises cannot access a fixed basic broadband connection (Bowyer, 2017). However, research reflects that when broadband is made available in rural environments, uptake and use reflect participation in the urban environment (Philip, Cottrill and Farrington, 2015; Williams et al., 2016). Furthermore, on a positive note, community-led solutions increasingly meet the needs of such 'deep rural' areas, providing self-built infrastructure (such as the world-leading B4RN project) and creative satellite solutions (such as that being used by the Kyle of Sutherland Development Trust in partnership with a private provider). It should be noted, however, that satellite solutions, while providing access currently in locations where access was non-existent, are unable to match the speed and strength of fixed line, suggesting that such solutions are not 'future-proof' and that the urban/rural divide may remain a pressing issue in years to come (Philip *et al.*, 2017).

Notwithstanding that the discussion has moved on from the issues around access, the first-level digital divide remains a pertinent issue, though the conversation has evolved. The complex issue of establishing digital 'access' no longer means simply establishing the infrastructure to which users may have access, or that the availability of infrastructure is the main bone of contention. As well as inequality related to infrastructure, in discussions related to the first level digital divide, an emphasis is also placed on equitable access to the equipment that is necessary to access that infrastructure. For example, within the Scottish context, access to the internet for personal use has steadily increased. Since the baseline year of 2007, the percentage of adults using the internet for personal use has increased from 62.7% to 83.4% in 2016 (Scottish Government, 2016). In a global context, infrastructure disparity is clearly reflected when one compares internet access rates.

In the last months, emerging research also calls for a 'minimum digital living standard', reflecting the need for households to have enough connectivity to meet their requirements (rather than a bare minimum) and the appropriate devices to meet the demand of multiple people living within a household, requiring different devices for different purposes. (Blackwell *et al.*, 2023) This is significant as it reflects the need for a more comprehensive understanding of device and data equity.

2.2 The development of digital exclusion - second level digital divide: digital skills and usage

As more individuals gained access to that infrastructure and equipment in the UK, attention moved to the second level digital divide, digital skills inequalities. While the first level of the 'digital divide' refers to the differences in access to technology, the second level digital divide refers to the disparities in the skills and capabilities needed to use digital technologies effectively. Alongside the discussion around infrastructure, the Scottish Government also identified the importance of digital participation. It concluded that the individual needs support in developing the skills necessary to creatively engage with the digital world and benefit socially and economically from access. (Scottish Government, 2021a).

The discussion around the second digital divide is also evident in the academic literature, particularly around the impact of a lack of digital skills on accessing wider opportunities, including education (Radovanović, Hogan and Lalić, 2015). For example, Radovanic *et al.* note that students who lack digital skills and access to technology may struggle to keep up with their peers and miss out on educational opportunities, also reflecting that children from low-income families are less likely to have access to digital technologies and less likely to use them for

educational purposes, leading to lower academic achievement and limited opportunities for future success.

(Radovanović, Hogan and Lalić, 2015)

A digital skills deficit also impacts employment, with the most recent statistics reflecting that 36% of the UK workforce lacks digital skills for work in an economy whereby over 90% of jobs have a digital component. (UK Consumer Digital Index 2021 | Lloyds Bank, 2021.) Research also reflects the positive correlation between digital skills and income amongst employees and how those with digital skills might access exclusive fringe benefits, such as company cars, work phones, and stocks or shares in the company, showing again a link between skills and tangible outcomes and how a skills deficit might materially disadvantage an individual in the workplace. (Goss and Phillips, 2002; Lissitsa, Chachashvili-Bolotin and Bokek-Cohen, 2017; Weritz, 2022)

The second-level skills divide also clearly impacts health (Vida Estacio et al., 2021.). From the turn of the millennium, researchers drew a link between digital skills and the future impact of technology-enabled healthcare. (Gibson, Sloan and Moncur, 2013) In an article in *The Lancet*, Pirisi noted that people who lack digital skills and access to technology are less likely to use online health resources, limiting their ability to make informed health decisions and access health care services, leading to poorer health outcomes and increased health disparities (Pirisi, 2000). The pandemic, of course, highlighted the correlation between health outcomes and digital inequality on a global scale, which is heavily reflected in the literature which appeared during this period (Covid-19 Is Magnifying the Digital Divide - *The BMJ*, 2020.; Ramsetty & Adams., 2020; Seifert, 2020a, 2020b)

Ways of addressing the gap in essential digital skills are varied. Libraries have played an important role in supporting the development of digital skills. (Jaeger *et al.*, 2012; Real *et al.*, 2015; Alabi and Mutula, 2020) They can offer vital community space where individuals can access connectivity, devices and support from staff. They are often identified as an essential element in addressing digital inequality. In Scotland, WiFi is now available in every public library. A Scottish Government 2018 report highlights that 22% of people living in households with an income of less than £25,000 make use of their public library to get online, suggesting that these spaces (Scottish Government, 2018.). It is essential to note the challenges here, however. Libraries are heavily impacted by budget constraints imposed on them by local authorities, impacting their opening hours, staffing, and ability to provide support. Staff skills in offering digital inclusion support are often also an issue. (Jaeger *et al.*, 2012)

It is helpful to summarise this discussion on the second-level divide. Differences in digital skills and literacy compound disparities in access to digital technologies, and even when individuals have access to digital technologies, they may not be able to use them effectively due to a lack of this digital literacy. Digital literacy includes basic computer and internet skills, critical thinking, problem-solving, and online safety. In their systemic literature review, focussed explicitly on exploring this second-level divide, Van Laar et al. noted: 'that in contrast to digital skills, 21st-century skills are not necessarily underpinned by ICT. Furthermore, we identified seven core skills: technical, information management, communication, collaboration, creativity, critical thinking and problem-solving. Five contextual skills were also identified: ethical awareness, cultural awareness, flexibility, self-direction and lifelong learning.' (van Laar et al., 2017, p72). This insight is particularly interesting as it articulates the importance of context: that of a person's broader experience and the correlation between skills, outcomes and broader inequalities. This brings us helpfully to an exploration of the third-level digital divide.

2.3 The development of digital exclusion - third level digital divide – digital understanding

Alongside the narratives related to the first and second digital divides, a further discussion began to emerge, with writers such as van Deursen and van Dijk highlighting in 2015 that even though internet skill levels increase, gaps widen between the level of access available to different socio-economic groups. (van Deursen and van Dijk, 2015). This emphasises how disadvantaged groups cannot meaningfully exploit the potential of digital technology to improve and transform their own situation. Humphry highlights 'the need to recognise the ways that life situations and circumstances of hardship, such as homelessness, factor into the patterns of mobile and internet connectivity, creating unique issues of digital access and equity' (Humphry, 2019, p13). He argues for knowledge of these differences to inform the digital delivery of government services and approaches to telecommunications policies and assistance programmes.

The 2018 Ofcom report, *Access and Inclusion in 2018: Consumer's experiences in communications markets*, highlights issues of differentiation in internet access, uptake and use in the UK, complementing the findings of the 2018 Lloyds Bank Consumer Digital Index. (Access and Inclusion in 2018, 2018) These examples from grey literature highlight the growing trend in discussions away from digital inclusion as an issue purely related to

access, to discussions focussed on the relationship between digital exclusion and other types of exclusion, with a focus on differentiation.

Of particular interest are Van Deursen and Helsper's discussion on the third-level digital divide and how this relates 'to gaps in individuals' capacity to translate their internet access and use into favourable offline outcomes.' (van Deursen and Helsper, 2015). Van Deursen and Helsper note that 'digital inclusion has moved from investigations of skills and usage to tangible outcomes' – or the third-level digital divide. The internet remains more beneficial for those with higher social status, not in how extensively they use the technology but in what they achieve because of this use for several important domains. 'When information and services are offered online, the number of potential outcomes the internet has to offer increases. If individuals with higher social status take more significant offline advantage from digital engagement than their lower status counterparts, existing offline inequalities could be exacerbated (van Deursen and Helsper, 2015).

Van Deursen notes that 'even among users with autonomous and unlimited access to the ICT infrastructure, there will be important differences in their proficiency in enlisting digital resources for the achievement of specific objectives'. The Model for Replications of Inequalities in a Digital Society illustrates how the offline outcomes that result from pre-existing inequalities derived from socio-economic status are replicated in the digital world through inequalities in access (to infrastructure or equipment - the first digital divide), and skills (the second digital divide) as well as the use made of digital resources and motivation to use digital resources. These online activities have the same offline outcomes on disadvantaged groups, replicating pre-existing inequalities.

Fig. 1. A Model for Replications of Inequalities in a Digital Society.
Source: Adapted from Helsper (2012) and van Dijk (2005).

Figure 1- A Model for replications of inequalities in a digital society

Selwyn (2004) argues that essential digital skills are an integral component of a broader skill set that enables participation and engagement with wider society – that the consideration of individual digital understanding is vital in discussions related to societal inequality. Residorf and Jewkes (2016) argue that ‘ICT deprivation must be considered equivalent to other social deprivations such as low income, unemployment, low education, poor health, and social isolation’ (p. 780), noting that ‘...the compound effects of ICT deprivation, in combination with other social deprivations, arguably lead to loss of confidence and social capital’ (p.780). The discussion around a relationship between social capital and digital skills and understanding continues to develop in academic fields, with literature reflecting that the socioeconomic demographics of the digital divide reproduce earlier inequities based on class, race, and gender (Drori, 2006). As a result, we move into a conversation centred around information or digital capital or information capital. Access alone is insufficient because digital ability, understanding and attitude are also potential barriers. These are exacerbated by social inequalities.

2.3.1 Identifying those most affected by digital exclusion - poverty

Research from the Carnegie UK Trust evidences the link between inequality and a deepening digital divide. Poverty rates in the UK continue to climb: 30% of children, or 4.1 million, were living in relative poverty (after housing costs) in 2017-18 in the UK, and 70% of children living in poverty were in working families. The percentage of pensioners in relative poverty (before housing costs) rose from 17% to 18% between 2016/17 and 2017/18. In addition, around one in ten adults have had difficulty paying for communications services; this is highest among younger consumers and those with long-term mental illness (Bowyer, 2017). It is therefore vitally important to continue to consider the impact of *economic capital* on digital exclusion. Lloyds Consumer Index also draws attention to the fact that 61% of people earning *more* than £25,000 have essential digital workplace skills, significantly higher than those earning *less* than £11,499, where only one-quarter have these skills (*Lloyds Bank Consumer Digital Index 2019*, 2019) and that employees in manufacturing, construction, utilities, and retail sectors are the least digitally skilled. Furthermore, unemployed people are 64% more likely to lack Essential Digital Skills for life than the UK average (36% vs 22%). These statistics add further weight to the close relationship between financial and digital capital.

The available evidence suggests that disadvantaged young people – particularly those not in employment, education or training (NEET) - use information and communication technologies more to engage in employment-related activities, often through default services such as JobMatch. Yet, they were less likely than their peers to succeed, even partially, through this medium (46% compared to 65% of their employed peers (Princes Trust, 2016). One study in Australia evidenced that the socio-economic status of an area was related to computer use, IT activities, playing musical instruments, and participating in vigorous physical exercise. Participants from higher income neighbourhoods with greater socio-economic status (SES) were more exposed to school computers, reading, playing musical instruments, and physical activity. Participants from lower SES neighbourhoods were more exposed to TV, electronic games, mobile phones, and non-academic computer activities at home. The authors noted that these patterns might impact future economic, academic, and health outcomes (Harris, Straker and Pollock, 2017)

A study of physical and digital access to cultural spaces in the UK further evidence the disparity replicated in the digital space (Mihelj, Leguina and Downey, 2019). The results of this research confirmed that although digital environments could be used to engage new audiences, they continued to reproduce and enlarge existing inequalities, with even fewer individuals of lower socio-economic groupings using digital to engage with cultural spaces. While digital may undoubtedly allow for an extended marketing reach, it appears only to reach more people of similar social classes, consequently creating a more significant divide between the 'have and have-nots, not only reinforcing inequality but deepening it through the creation of alternative barriers.

Bauer (2018) also highlights that the ability to use the digital space influences income distribution both directly and indirectly, underlining that 'ICTs rarely are a single cause but interact with other technological, economic, and political forces to shape the extent of income inequality.' (Bauer, 2018) Van Deursen highlights (financial) resources as a cause of differentiation in access to the digital and that individuals from higher socio-economic groups are more likely to have access to higher quality digital devices and peripherals, with stable access to higher speeds of connectivity, with less limitation on data (Van Deursen *et al.*, 2017). This argument is complemented by Van Dijk's 'resources and appropriation theory' (Van Dijk, 2017), which determines that:

- 'Categorical inequalities in society produce an unequal distribution of resources.
- An unequal distribution of resources causes unequal access to digital technologies.

- Unequal access to digital technologies also depends on the characteristics of these technologies.
- Unequal access to digital technologies brings about unequal participation in society.
- Unequal participation in society reinforces categorical inequalities in society and unequal distributions of resources. (Van Dijk, 2017)

To summarize, available research suggests that, despite the egalitarian promises of digital as a leveller, the internet instead increases marginalization, deepening inequalities, with the disadvantaged economic groups particularly impacted by digital inequality. Moreover, the research clearly demonstrates not only the correlation between digital and financial exclusion but also the possibility that the continued societal application of digital technology may serve to deepen such inequality unless positive, nuanced interventions, both on the ground and at a policy level, are supported, primarily if the current policy of digital first/digital only is pursued.

2.3.2 Identifying those most affected by digital exclusion – disability

Disability is reflected as another critical indicator of digital exclusion, with Ofcom's research (*Ofcom: Access and Inclusion in 2018, 2018*) mirroring disparities in access to digital environments already addressed in both the 2018 and 2019 Lloyds Consumer Digital Index reports. (*Lloyds Bank – UK Consumer Digital Index 2018*)(*Lloyds Bank Consumer Digital Index 2019, 2019*). The Ofcom report highlights that smartphone ownership by disabled people is markedly different from non-disabled: 53% of disabled people have a smartphone in their household compared to 81% of non-disabled people. Furthermore, 67% of disabled people use the internet compared to 92% of non-disabled people. However, there are also differences in the type of impairment. People with learning disability display similarities in their use of communications services to non-disabled people. They are more likely than those with other disability types to have a smartphone in their household (70%) and access to the internet (86%). Those with a visual impairment are the most likely group to say their use of communication services or devices is limited by their disability.

Within a European context, research has shown that an individual with a declared disability is 62% less likely to have internet access at home than an individual without a declared disability. Additionally, an individual living with a disability is more likely to face additional barriers of financial constraints and a greater likelihood of unemployment, ageing, or living alone (Scholz, Yalcin and Priestley, 2017). It is also important to note that access to traditional cultural enablers for digital participation is, for disabled people, often 'strongly associated with

differential levels of exclusion from mainstream education and employment in European countries' (Scholz, Yalcin and Priestley, 2017, p.10) – libraries, colleges and other similar community spaces may benefit some individuals, but not all. In terms of social isolation, 40% of online respondents in the Lloyds Consumer Digital Index report (*Lloyds Bank – UK Consumer Digital Index 2018*)(*Lloyds Bank Consumer Digital Index 2019*, 2019) indicated that being online helps them feel less alone, a benefit that is felt even more strongly among disabled people online, who are more likely (67%) to express this view than non-disabled people.

For individuals with intellectual disabilities, research carried out by Chadwick et al. indicates that, with only a small number of exceptions, both the risks and benefits of being online are believed to be more significant for people with intellectual disabilities compared with those without intellectual disabilities (Chadwick, Quinn and Fullwood, 2017). The authors concluded that while there is clear evidence of the potential for significant benefits, the 'perception of increased risk may help to explain the reduced inclusion of people with intellectual disabilities in the online world' (Chadwick, Quinn and Fullwood, 2017, p22). Nine out of ten people with a learning disability reported being the target of online bullying. While it is understandable that those providing support to those with a learning disability are anxious about the increased risk, such concern negatively impacts individual participation in the digital space, further entrenching exclusion amongst individuals with disabilities.

Furthermore, there is evidence of a specific skills gap for those providing care and support for individuals with intellectual disabilities. For example, research shows that only 43% of carers expressed confidence in their ability to support digital access for an individual with an intellectual disability(Chiner, Gómez-Puerta and Cardona-Moltó, 2017), with Chiner et al. concluding that 'Training programmes for all the groups involved (i.e. people with intellectual disabilities, staff and family members) should be designed, implemented and assessed to promote the inclusion of people with intellectual disabilities in the digital arena.' (Chiner, Gómez-Puerta and Cardona-Moltó, 2017, p2).

2.3.3 Identifying those most affected by digital exclusion - age

The third edition of the Lloyds Consumer Digital Index reveals an ongoing intergenerational digital divide, also highlighted in the 2017 review. The proportion of people without digital skills is highest in older age groups, as 54% of the UK population aged 65 and over do not have the full suite of essential digital skills. In contrast, 96% of 15–24-year-olds are in possession of these essential skills (*Lloyds Bank – UK Consumer Digital Index 2018*, 2018).

An obvious explanation for this is that younger generations have grown up with digital technology. However, social exclusion issues may also impact the younger demographic. Vulnerable young people, especially those at recognised life transitions who are in care, excluded from mainstream education, homeless, unemployed, or seeking asylum, are most at risk of experiencing digital exclusion (White, 2016). Additionally, digital understanding – as well as digital skills - are impacted by age. Those aged 55+ are less likely to verify information sources online and are less likely to use online banking. The Carnegie UK report titled *Digital Savvy Citizens* evidences a significant risk awareness amongst this demographic – people from this age bracket are less likely to share photos, use social media, download media files, and use public Wi-Fi (White/Carnegie UK Trust, 2017). However, this continues with the downward trend in the number of older adults. However, research carried out by the Prince’s Trust (Wilson *et al.*, 2017) also established that 10% of young people do not feel they have the essential digital skills for work, with 18% of young people claiming benefits feeling the same way.

2.3.4 Approaches to involving those affected by such inequality.

The digital participation strategy, A National Framework for Local Action, was published on 24 April 2014. The strategy set out a national framework for action in local communities and workplaces across the country, which will use the power of the internet to break down societal inequalities and help people make the best use of the internet to become confident and creative users of digital technologies. At the highest level, digital participation is measured by access to and use of the internet. In Scotland, both internet access and use have continued to grow steadily since measures began, although the quality and purpose of that use continue to be of significant research interest and are indeed the context for this thesis. Scottish Government outlines the ‘ambition is to achieve world-class levels of digital participation framed in a global context with the aim of matching the rates achieved by countries that currently lead the world in terms of digital inclusion.’

2.4 The development of digital exclusion - third level digital divide – digital understanding

In March 2017, the Scottish Government refreshed its digital strategy for Scotland, outlined in Realising Scotland’s full potential in a digital world: a digital strategy for Scotland (Scottish Government, 2017) which sets aspirations for greater digital participation, with funding for third sector organisations working to address digital exclusion. The policy also states that the Scottish Government will work closely with schools, employers, and skills providers to tackle the persistent gender gap in digital skills and careers. For young people, the strategy also highlights a

commitment to ‘digital rights and responsibilities that empower people to access the digital world creatively, knowledgeably and fearlessly’ (Scottish Government,2017).

This Scottish policy context is essential for this thesis as many issues related to digital participation are impacted by devolution, particularly education, welfare, and health. Within the Scottish context, the Scottish Council for Voluntary Organisations (SCVO) led the digital inclusion movement through the digital participation charter. It was a partner in a significant UK-wide digital inclusion programme, One Digital, which sought to advance the organisational and individual capacity to benefit from the digital sphere. Furthermore, in terms of pandemic response, the Scottish Government led a collaborative national campaign to address digital inequality.

2.5 Defining ‘digital skills.’

In early 2019, the DQ Global Standards Report introduced a common framework for digital skills, literacy, and readiness (DQ Global Standards Report 2019 Digital Intelligence, 2019), noting that ‘Digital Intelligence (DQ) is a comprehensive set of technical, cognitive, meta-cognitive, and socio-emotional competencies that are grounded in universal moral values and that enable individuals to face the challenges and harness the opportunities of digital life.’ (DQ Global Standards Report 2019 Digital Intelligence, 2019, p8). This framework is a cross-sectoral, transnational piece which collates findings across various frameworks (DQ Global Standards Report 2019 Digital Intelligence, 2019). It seeks to synthesise these effectively, setting out standards that others can work to.

(DQ Global Standards Report 2019 Digital Intelligence, 2019)

Figure 2- DQ Global Standards Report 2019

Source: DQ Global Standards Report 2019 Digital Intelligence, 2019

From a UK perspective, this framework was influenced by the Tech Partnership’s work to define ‘essential digital skills’ (*Essential Digital Skills Framework, 2018*). This framework is used by practitioners in the field of digital inclusion within the UK, and over the course of this thesis, its application will be explored further. In Scotland, SCVO has created the Essential Digital Skills toolkit to assist practitioners in making practical use of the framework (*SCVO Essential Digital Skills Toolkit, 2018*).

The Essential Digital Skills Framework contains simple checklists for measuring Foundation Skills and Essential Skills and guidance on how to interpret the results. Essential digital skills are defined in four broad categories applicable both to life and work: communicating, transacting, problem-solving, and handling information and content. These are all set within a context of being safe, legal, and confident online. (*Essential digital skills framework - GOV.UK, 2018*).

Figure 3- The essential digital skills framework

Source: (*Essential digital skills framework - GOV.UK, 2018*)

Application of these frameworks allows for the development of research such as Helsper and Van Deursen’s findings on the positive field-based work in digital inclusion and, in particular, the ways in which an individual’s

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engagement with one domain of essential digital skills may then impact on other areas, which they refer to as 'collateral benefits' (Van Deursen and Helsper, 2018).

Though these skills frameworks provide important guidance for organisations and individuals, they tell us little about the current extent of digital exclusion in the UK. There is a growing body of grey literature which captures snapshots in the field, drawing on the application of the essential digital skills framework. One of the most well-respected sources of digital exclusion data is the Lloyds Consumer Index. The 2018 Index evidences an ongoing decline in the number of adults with no digital skills, with the proportion of UK adults unable to apply any of the above abilities falling from 10% in 2016 to 8% in 2018. A further 12% of adults were estimated to have limited essential digital skills (*Lloyds Bank – UK Consumer Digital Index 2018*). The Office for National Statistics (ONS) further highlights this improving trend, which was also evidenced in the 2017 review (Office for National Statistics, 2019).

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Figure 4 - Number and percentage of adult internet non-users, UK, 2011 to 2018

Source: (Office for National Statistics, 2019)

Within the Scottish context, the percentage of non-users of the internet also declined significantly since 2012, from 20.2% to 10.7%, with approximately 80% of the population in possession of the necessary essential digital

skills for life and work and only 7% lacking digital foundation skills. These statistics reflect a narrowing of the digital skills gap with other areas of the UK.

2.6 Digital Skills vs Digital Understanding

‘Roulette’, wrote Bourdieu, ‘which holds out the opportunity of winning a lot of money in a short space of time, and therefore of changing one’s social status quasi-instantaneously, and in which the winning of the previous spin of the wheel can be staked and lost at every new spin, gives a fairly accurate image of this imaginary universe of perfect competition or perfect equality of opportunity, a world without inertia, without accumulation, without heredity or acquired properties, in which every moment is perfectly independent of the previous one, every soldier has a marshal’s baton in his knapsack, and every prize can be attained, instantaneously, by everyone, so that at each moment anyone can become anything.’ (Bourdieu, 1986)

Similarly, the Internet, in its infancy, was perceived to hold the potential for challenging inequality- for being a leveller, where everyone- no matter their background or class might access equal opportunities and benefit from a new field offering social, educational, and financial possibilities. Principles of decentralisation, non-discrimination, bottom up-design, universality and consensus were revolutionary ideas with a scope far beyond the tech sector. (*History of the Web – World Wide Web Foundation*) – ‘the Internet is for everyone’ espoused Tim Berners Lee, the web’s creator. However, as Bourdieu reflects in research, such states of ‘equality of opportunity’ (Bourdieu, 1986) are illusory, and each of us is, instead, bound by our habitus- our ‘hereditary or acquired properties’ (Bourdieu, 1986)- our class, our family history – the networks we are part of and the influences we are able to draw on- impact profoundly on our economic, social, cultural and, this thesis will argue our digital capital.

Theoretically, then, this thesis draws on Pierre Bourdieu’s notion of habitus, capital, and field to explore the differential access to, use of, and understanding of digital environments, with particular attention to issues of dominant and non-dominant cultural and digital capital – considering what is of value, what is of currency in the local and informal fields in which the individual finds themselves. As Willig (2015) and colleagues stress, ‘Internet access may not, in and of itself, level the playing field when it comes to the potential payoffs of being online.

Instead, those from more privileged backgrounds may reap more of its benefits if they are more likely to use it in potentially beneficial ways. Danielssen (2011) has also highlighted the continuation of distinctive class habitus

that impacts access to leisure and education. What is important here is that the affordances and possibilities of

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digital practices are unequally experienced, distributed and interpreted and, therefore, it cannot be taken for granted that they are empowering, liberatory or can address existing systemic societal inequalities.

Bourdieu's academic enquiries into the fields of education and social inequality are equally applicable to the digital domain. Individual capital – the connection to others- or 'social capital' is replicated in 'digital capital' as the internet –with digital relationships, social networks, skills, and opportunities – being increasingly a key component of the individual's ability to participate economically, politically, and socially in wider society. Digital capital also allows for positive health and wellbeing outcomes, as well as wider cultural engagement. Without that digital capital, an individual is increasingly disenfranchised from such positive outcomes.

Furthermore, the individual's habitus 'acts in such a way as to embed certain cultural trajectories in individuals' (McGillivray & McIntosh 2006): increasing research evidence that access to and practice within the digital domain is closely related to an individual's background. Recent research shows that while connectivity may not provide a significant barrier, support is unequally accessed. Helsper and Van Deursen's recent research demonstrates that 'the quality of the support that people access is unequally distributed replicating existing patterns of disadvantage'. As those who experience the most difficulties in accessing the benefits of the internet are more likely to be from lower socio-economic groupings or have a disability (both related to 'class'), these individuals will also experience the most difficulty obtaining high-quality support even when it is available, creating an even larger 'gap' between those who do and do not need support. (Helsper/Van Deursen 2016).

Helsper identifies that 'Four key domains from which an individual can be excluded offline have corresponding domains of exclusion in the digital world: economic, cultural, social, and personal (Helsper, 2012). The first three domains are familiar to scholars who build on Bourdieu's (1986) theory of capitals, in which people's economic, cultural, and social assets are theorized (JAM Van Deursen *et al.*, 2017)

This research aims to take a considered participatory action research approach to understand better the exclusions, opportunities, and barriers within this theoretical framework, working primarily with people experiencing homelessness and also those who are currently using drugs.

This thesis reflects a Bourdieuean approach reflecting capital, field, and space discussions. Significant articles reflect this thesis- with Helsper's work being of particular interest. Working with Van Deursen on 'Collateral benefits of Internet use: Explaining the diverse outcomes of engaging with the Internet' (Van Deursen and

Helsper, 2018), she draws a theoretical framework focused on user choice and agency in the digital space, applying relative deprivation theory to digital inequality. In recent years, it has been noticeable that the academic and grey literature reflect a more nuanced approach to developing digital skills, emphasising the need for a greater appreciation of digital understanding rather than simply possessing practical skills. The 2018 Digital Attitudes Report (*People, Power, and Technology: The 2018 Digital Attitudes Report*, 2018) evidences this growing concern. The corresponding 2018 Digital Understanding Report, produced by doteveryone, defines *digital understanding* as separate from the development of basic digital skills. They argue that 'Digital understanding is about appreciating the impacts of technologies – how they shape people's lives and society as a whole.' (*People, Power, and Technology: The 2018 Digital Attitudes Report*, p8).

The evidence presented throughout Doteveryone's report highlights 'digital blind spots' for the individual as a worker and consumer, and member of society, which inhibit their ability to question the implications of technology on their lives. The report stratifies digital understanding into three categories: *aware, discovering and questioning*, with the latter being the most important. Doteveryone suggests that within a societal context, only 1% of individuals have sufficient digital understanding to consider how online debates can have a broader societal impact or how to exercise their own information rights so that they have reached the 'questioning' level of engagement. The same percentage is unaware of the impact of media manipulation methods and techniques such as 'bots' – software which runs automated responses - or understand why filter bubbles reflecting and reinforcing individual worldviews through algorithms are created and able to find ways to overcome them. This, in turn, continues to perpetuate a balance of power weighted heavily in favour of those creating technology and online platforms and those gathering data and influencing the individual.

White also evidences that individuals in lower socio-economic groups are the least likely to adopt digital behaviours which protect their privacy and security online. (White and Carnegie United Kingdom Trust, 2017) This Carnegie UK Trust report suggested that, within a Scottish context, people from lower socio-economic groups are less likely to turn off location services, use a passcode or use two factor authentication. This is of particular significance in the context of a shift towards universal credit, which means individuals requiring benefits are forced into a situation where it is necessary to share highly sensitive and personal data with online systems without the relevant skills to keep this information safe. Dodel and Mesch also note that, increasingly, cyber security, at the individual level, is a 'capital-preserving consequence of digital engagement'.(Dodel and Mesch,

2018). In other words, those within a higher socio-economic stratification and with the resultant digital skills are more able to protect both their physical and online assets.

Furthermore, in their most recent work, Van Deursen and Helsper note that 'A clear distinction needs to be made between the possession of Internet skills, undertaking different kinds of activities online, and the tangible outcomes in different spheres of everyday life that result from this engagement' (Van Deursen and Helsper, 2018, p3). Digital understanding is increasingly a focus of interest in both grey literature and academic literature, with ongoing research into how 'digital understanding' can be defined and quantified. Interestingly, White references a further challenge (White and Carnegie United Kingdom Trust, 2017), highlighting that while individuals may have some understanding of issues such as data privacy, they do not necessarily take the necessary steps to protect that privacy.

2.7 The complexity of barriers to digital inclusion

Good Things Foundation, in partnership with the University of Liverpool, provide an interesting insight into some of the motivations of non-users of the internet, highlighting that 52% of individuals who do not engage online see no need, 44% access the internet by proxy, 19% have safety concerns, 15% say it costs too much, and 17% don't have the right equipment (Good Things Foundation, 2018). This paper combined quantitative and qualitative methods, interviewing learners at various Online Centres to understand their motivations.

The #NotWithoutMe programme supported four projects across the UK in testing original engagement techniques and developing new practices to improve digital participation and increase essential digital skills for vulnerable young people. The project identified a number of key barriers, including 'pushed out learners' with social, emotional or behavioural needs, which have resulted in a lesser engagement with mainstream formal education and consequent lack of literacy, numeracy and essential digital skills; limited resources in educational and support settings; lack of confidence amongst parents, carers, support workers and educators; the risk of 'additional vulnerability' (cited as a barrier with a project based in a pupil referral unit where some young people demonstrated offending behaviour online, or who became at greater risk of sexual exploitation (Wilson *et al.*, 2017); and also advanced skills in one area may mask low skills in other essential digital competencies.

This risk of 'assumption of essential skills' is also a significant barrier for younger people. This is highlighted in both grey literature, such as #NotWithoutMe, and also in academic literature, such as Scheerder *et al.*'s

consideration of the way in which a family's educational background contributes to digital inequalities. (Scheerder, van Deursen and van Dijk, 2019). Furthermore, poverty impacts access to the tools necessary to develop digital skills – low-income households are less likely to have access to a home computer or broadband but rely instead on smartphone use. Robinson refers to the 'identity curation game' amongst younger people (Robinson, 2018, p661). Robinson sets out the rules for online engagement as '(1) constantly update or be sidelined, (2) engage in constant reciprocated identity-affirming interactions, and (3) maintain a strategy of vigilance to remove traces of failed identity performances.' (Robinson, 2018, p661) The findings of this research show how 'under-resourced youths experience connectivity gaps that disrupt their ability to play the identity curation game, as well as the resulting emotional consequences.' (Robinson, 2018, p661)

Research conducted by Dutton and Reisdorf also highlights the impact of 'internet cultures', defined by the researchers as 'five clusters of Internet users that vary in their attitudes toward the Internet as well as their socio-demographic backgrounds and their use of the Internet in general and social media specifically' (Dutton and Reisdorf, 2019).

Figure 5 - Dutton and Reisdorf's Internet cultures

Source: Dutton and Reisdorf, 2019

On the importance of differentiated use when approaching digital inclusion work, especially in the context of the potential positive outcomes of digital inclusion, Van Deursen and Helpser note that 'economic uses, often the focus of digital inclusion policies and interventions, are narrowly related to mainly economic outcomes', whereas

developing an individual's 'softer' digital communicative and creative skills development will have a wider impact in an increased number of fields (Van Deursen and Helsper, 2018).

The intergenerational divide in terms of digital practice, digital attitude, and digital understanding, as evidenced in Digital Savvy Citizens (White and Carnegie United Kingdom Trust, 2017), especially towards issues such as digital privacy and security, highlight the key issue that different age groups have very different needs in terms of developing skills and knowledge. However, Quan-Haase et al. demonstrate that, in the case of their research cohort in East York, older adults in Toronto did not let their skill level determine how they engaged with the internet, evidencing an apparently nonlinear association between older adults' skill levels and online engagement (Quan-Haase *et al.*, 2018b). Each of these studies indicates that access to the digital world provides an incomplete picture of the complexities of use by different demographic groups in different geographical settings. This is important because there can be no 'one size fits all' approach to ensure everyone benefits from accessing digital spaces to the same extent. Instead, recognition of complex and varied needs must be built into design and decision-making processes if well safe and questioning use of the digital is to be achieved.

2.8 What works in addressing digital inequality and in addressing the absence of digital capital?

Digital champions are defined by Helsper as 'either volunteers who help the disconnected online and increase their skills, or national figureheads who raise awareness among industry and third sector stakeholders'. (Helsper, p141) (Andreasson, 2019). In practice in the UK, the digital champion approach has become more nuanced- One Digital, for example, outlines five different types of digital champions.

Figure 6 - Five different types of digital champion

Source: One Digital

One Digital in the UK was a collaborative digital inclusion programme developed by Age UK, Citizens Online, Clarion Futures (part of Clarion Housing Group), Digital Unite and Scottish Council for Voluntary Organisations (SCVO) and was funded by the National Lottery Community Fund until 2020 to deliver digital skills training through a digital champion approach. The 2016 evaluation of One Digital highlighted some of the strengths of a digital champion approach, and the project continues to offer insight and learning and the benefits and opportunities of offering person centred support embedded in third sector organisations. Within the partnership, SCVO is undertaking a multi-faceted approach, with intervention at leadership, organisation, and individual levels to address digital inclusion. The main findings from an evaluation of One Digital suggest that training and supporting digital champions within third sector organisations positively impacts on their ability to share digital skills with their key client groups. (McGillivray, Jenkins, Mamattah, 2016, One Digital, 2019).

Van Deursen and Helsper note that a 'semiologic, rather than an economic approach is more likely to be effective in addressing digital inclusion' (Van Deursen and Helsper, 2018) with the trainer 'providing mediation for the learner's appropriation and use of digital concepts. This provides further evidence that the learner-centred

approach is most likely to entice non-users into digital participation. Additionally, Dutton and Reisdorf note that practitioners and supporting organisations who are supporting digitally excluded people might embed the following approaches to facilitate greater engagement:

- Demonstrate the relevance of the Internet to making one's life easier and more efficient.
- Convey a more realistic understanding of the sociality required of the Internet and social media, which is not overly invasive as feared by the doubters.
- Develop training that enables users to avoid some of the frustrations they experience in trying to get online and avoid unwanted information; and
- understand how personal information can be of value in meeting some needs, such as for shopping, but that it can be protected reasonably well through good information practices. (Dutton and Reisdorf, 2019)

This considers a more nuanced approach to data privacy and security, a key concern of both users and non-users. This approach is further supported by Quan-Haase *et al.*, who find that peer-led learning can be effective, especially with 'Savvy Users' who can act as digital role models and mentors. They also found that it is important to tailor training to support older adult needs, with these savvy users being in the ideal position to challenge the negative connotations surrounding digital media use, emphasising to reluctant older adults that online activity can be gratifying and manageable for all ages rather than just a hobby or a form of entertainment (Quan-Haase *et al.*, 2018a).

Interventions for a younger demographic were tested through the #NotWithoutMe programme, led by Carnegie Trust UK (Wilson *et al.*, 2017), which challenged the assumption that all young people have the essential digital skills that they need for life and work. This evidenced that vulnerable young people are particularly in need of additional support to develop their skills. Recommendations from this work indicated several positive strategies for engaging with young people to support the development of essential digital skills, including a flexible, co-design model with a creative approach to methodology for programme delivery, as with other digital inclusion projects. #NotWithoutMe also established that 'trusted intermediaries' – organisations which already have a relationship with young people - are best placed to drive recruitment and engagement and that embedding essential digital skills into existing programmes of skills development is also a positive approach. (Wilson *et al.*, 2017).

A further positive approach comes from the private sector, with BT supporting 810 placements for disadvantaged young people not in employment, education, or training to develop essential digital skills for the workplace. Over 57% of individuals secured opportunities post-placement through the Work Ready programme. Again, digital skills are incorporated as part of a wider programme of engagement and skills development.

From a campaigning and policy perspective, the 5 Rights project (*5Rights / The 5 Rights*, 2019), an output of the 5 Rights Foundation and led in Scotland by Young Scot, establishes five key rights for young people in the digital space and calls for these rights to inform approaches of policy makers, educators, and parent/carers:

1. The Right to Remove
2. The Right to Digital Literacy
3. The Right to Know
4. The Right to Safety and Support
5. The Right to Informed and Conscious Use

The Right to Digital Literacy calls for a commitment to digital literacy to be embedded across all areas of the curriculum by digitally skilled educators and should inform both the Scottish Government and Education Scotland. This positive intervention and support are also supported by the DQ Institute, which is addressing the same issue at a global scale through #DQEveryChild – a global digital citizenship movement for children which focuses on developing eight digital citizenship tools, namely:

1. Digital citizen identity
2. Privacy management
3. Critical thinking
4. Digital footprints
5. Cyberbullying management
6. Screentime management
7. Cyber security management
8. Digital empathy

Other interesting approaches in Scotland include the Get Digital Programme, a three-year funded multi agency programme lead by Simon Community Scotland, which seeks to support the development of essential digital skills

of people experiencing homelessness, as well as the skills of the staff who support them, working across organisations engaged in addressing the causes of homelessness and helping those affected. This digital champion project will be of particular interest as it places the Essential Digital Skills Framework at the core, allowing for a longitudinal study, and is part of a participatory action research approach which will allow for greater qualitative learning.

2.9 Homelessness: intersecting inequalities

In 2017-2018, 34972 applications were made by individuals declaring themselves as homeless- the first increase in nine years. Shelter Scotland evidence that 11% of homeless applications were a direct result of action by landlord or lender, and 27% for other reasons, including loss of accommodation tied to employment- supporting (Shelter, 2018).

Furthermore, 47% of applicants to local authorities during the period 2017-18 who were assessed as homeless or threatened with homelessness had at least one support need, defined as a mental health problem, drug or alcohol dependency, physical or learning disability, medical condition, or difficulties with skills of independent living (Scottish Public Health Authority, 2018). Jointly, these statistics, when set within the frame of the Lloyds report linking disability and financial hardship with digital exclusion, suggest that people currently experiencing homelessness are particularly likely to face digital inequality, and people currently experiencing problematic alcohol or drug use even more so.

It is also helpful, within this context, to reflect on research reflecting on the importance of social capital with regard to issues of homelessness (Rock Trust, 2013). Habner notes that 84% of local authorities and 80% of third sector organisations saw a link between promoting positive social networks and overcoming homelessness, that 68% of all organisations surveyed felt that supporting social networks offered the best value in the delivery of housing services and that 62% of all organisations could evidence increased likelihood of tenancy sustainment resulting from receiving social network-based services. This research indicates the correlation between social networks in Scotland and how they may be used to overcome specific challenges related to homelessness through creating safe, trusted spaces online and building relationships and community. Historically these safe, trusted spaces would be physical locations, but increasingly as a society, this physical space is replicated online, with Covid-19 precipitating this trajectory across the public and third sectors, as well as in the domestic sphere.

A Connected Scotland (Shelter, 2018) notes that there is an urgent need to provide more opportunities for social interaction for those affected by homelessness— seeing pathways through third sector organisations as one way of moving forward, developing social capital, and drawing on Habner’s ‘networked approach’. Humphry (2014) argues ‘for the need to recognise the ways that life situations and circumstances of hardship, such as homelessness, factor into the patterns of mobile and internet connectivity, creating unique issues of digital access and equity’ (Humphry, 2014, p.2), arguing for knowledge of these differences to inform digital delivery of government at a national level.

Other research studies reflect on the way digital technologies are applied by those experiencing homelessness. Bure, through her research working within a central Scotland context, established that ‘homeless individuals tend to use ICTs in ways which reinforce the patterns and practices of their subculture’ (Bure, 2005), highlighting that ‘Digital inclusion is often expressed as synonymous with social inclusion, with the deterministic assumption that one process can lead to the other’ (Bure, 2005, p5). However, this study reveals that people who are homeless can be relatively digitally included, especially with respect to mobile phones, while remaining socially excluded. (Bure, 2005) Partially in contrast, Roberson and Nardi outline the ways in which digital tools are used by those experiencing homelessness, noting that ‘digital technology use among the homeless is linked to collaborative practices ensuring survival and inclusion in social worlds beyond their immediate communities’ (Roberson and Nardi, 2010, p4). In other words, when appropriately supported, addressing digital inequality, and exploring the ways in which it correlates to wider social inequalities, is a meaningful contribution to the dissolution of barriers for people living the experience of homelessness.

2.10 Conclusion

The key learnings from this literature review are that a multi-faceted approach to digital engagement, in a way that is consistent with the overall needs and motivations of individuals, is needed. This review highlights the varying ways projects have provided positive and varied approaches to digital inclusion, with no one-size-fits-all approach dominating. Furthermore, the relationship between digital and social capital remains a consistent and important area of emerging study (Helsper and van Deursen, 2017; Van Deursen *et al.*, 2017; Van Dijk, 2017a; Ragnedda, 2018). Significant work is happening across Scotland where informal peer support models, more formal digital champion models and person-centred approaches are beginning to evidence change and where

spatial changes in usage are factored into project design: in other words, the physical spaces where individuals are more likely to access and use the internet should be given consideration. It is essential that, as these projects grow, there is an adequate reflection on their success or otherwise.

The literature reflects that long-term understanding of the impact of digital inclusion work remains a challenge, and greater longitudinal research is required. While the context of building a coherent evidence base with the continued prevalence of small, short-term research and evaluation projects is a clear limitation, there is nevertheless a lack of immersive, qualitative research exploring digital inequality. The review of literature highlights an absence of any writing reflecting action research approaches within the space of digital inequality which means that current research fails to engage with not only *how* digital inequality impacts on individuals facing wider social inequality, but also what might actively *done* to support those individuals to develop agency and autonomy in the digital space. This absence provides an opportunity for new research to centre lived expertise and the voices of those most impacted by the fast-paced, wholesale systems-first approach by undertaking embedded, participatory action research, a methodology again absent from the literature at time of writing. This, then, is what I set out to do.

Chapter 3: Methodology

‘Doing’ Digital Inclusion and Participatory Action Research

3.1 Introduction

This chapter explores the methodological approach taken and considers participatory action research as a useful tool for action-focussed work, highlighting both the dynamism and challenges of this approach. The chapter also outlines the value of shared knowledge production from praxis. As a practitioner working in the space of digital inclusion within a third sector organisation, a hands-on approach to research was always a key priority to ensure that research contributed immediately to the groundwork addressing digital inequality. Additionally, my practitioner role gave privileged access both to appropriate third sector organisations and to those individuals with lived experience. The duality of being a practitioner/researcher also allowed academic practice, including ethics, to inform and improve this work. Methodologically, this project followed an immersive, participatory action research approach involving collaboration with several key partners, including Scottish Council for Voluntary Organisations (SCVO) and Simon Community Scotland.

Much academic research in the field of digital inequality has, up until relatively recently, focused on a quantitative approach to data collection and evidencing impact. (Min, 2010; Jaeger *et al.*, 2012) This quantitative approach supports a very specific understanding of the impact of digital inclusion activity and, consequently, focusses on the first and second level digital divide (of connectivity and access to devices). While it may also touch on skills, such research is often limited in exploring the *application* of these skills and how developing digital understanding may impact an individual’s ability to use this understanding for personal empowerment. This approach has, for instance, informed thinking around the impact of rurality on connectivity and access (Philip, Cottrill and Farrington, 2015), which is of specific relevance to the Scottish context where the country has many hyper-rural communities where connectivity impacts on digital participation. In the United States, studies into the practice of ‘redlining’ also emphasise the way in which infrastructure excludes particular communities, contributing to further inequalities. Friedline *et al.*, for instance, find that poor rural communities of colour experience digital

redlining by having the lowest engagement with digital financial services because of limited access (Friedline and Chen, 2021).

Other studies reflect on the devices used to support digital inclusion work. Tsai et al. explore the use of tablets to encourage older adults online. (Tsai et al., 2015); Correa et al. explore digital inclusion activity on mobile phones (Correa, Pavez, and Contreras, 2018) and grey literature in the UK has often focussed on the impact of differentiated access. (Citizens Advice Bureau Scotland, 2018). However, data gathered in these circumstances offer only a short-term consideration of the impact of digital inclusion work, often through the lens of achieving short-term outcomes pre-agreed to meet funding stipulations.

Each of these examples contribute to the body of research exploring the impact of access, opportunity, systems and

Instead, through a participatory action research approach, this study seeks to enhance understanding of the impact of digital exclusion on marginalised groups, exploring the concept of digital capital with lived experience informing and directing both research design and research progression. The central research questions the thesis seeks to address are best explored through a methodology which, while taking consideration of quantitative data, enables a deeply qualitative approach throughout:

1. What is the impact of digital inequality on people who are already socially excluded, and in particular on those people currently experiencing homelessness?
2. What role do digital tools and technologies play in addressing compounded social inequalities?
3. What is the most effective approach to involving those affected by such inequality in the design and development of digital initiatives designed to address social (and digital) exclusion?
4. In what way does the trusted intermediary (or 'digital champion') contribute to or minimise existing power structures and hierarchies?

The Participatory Action Research (PAR) approach is disruptive and, in this study, looks to foreground lived experience to inform both research and action. As such, a PAR approach challenges the status quo and expects change to result. Drawing on a Bourdieusian lens, individuals, each emerging from a different habitus and with different understandings of cultural and social (and digital) capital, bring their experience and knowledge to the research work, informing praxis, ensuring it both understands and meets need in the context (or field) in which

individuals find themselves. The bringing together of praxis, individual experience, disruption of power dynamics, and the commitment to effecting change is a powerful agenda which sits well within third sector work in Scotland. It is intended that the output of this thesis will influence and contribute to meaningful change both in the field of non-profit sector work and in policy.

In addition, this study also reflects a collaborative approach with organisations to address this exclusion through the delivery of essential digital skills support using a digital champion approach, whereby support is part of a holistic engagement with people. The research has taken a mixed methods approach, with quantitative analysis of surveys and feedback questionnaires, as well as using a qualitative approach, embedded in practice, to assess not only the effectiveness of interventions with opportunities for reflective action and further research, which will be outlined later in this chapter.

3.2 PAR as a positive, disruptive agent for change

Adelman (1993) highlights Kurt Lewin as the founder of what we now refer to as participatory action research, focussing his work and research in community based environments to ‘demonstrate, respectively, the greater gains in productivity and law and order through democratic participation rather than autocratic coercion’ (Adelman, 1993, p7), using an approach which sought to empower research participants, encouraging and developing their ‘independence, equality and co-operation’ (Lewin, 1946). This approach was in stark contrast to the traditional ‘scientific’ approach of the time, which instead ‘othered’ research participants through observation. PAR, instead, was, and is, rooted in a commitment to egalitarianism. Lewin’s approach specifically addressed the ‘iterative process of interplay between researchers and participants which activities switch between action and reflection’ (Fisher and Ball, 2003), which then became a core element of the participatory action research approach. Kindon et al. (2007) highlight that ‘the key (to PAR) is an ontology that suggests that human beings are dynamic agents capable of reflexivity and self-change, and an epistemology that accommodates the reflexive capacities of human beings within the research process’. (Kindon, Pain and Kesby, 2007, p. 13). To develop thinking in this space, it is also helpful to consider Lewin’s approach alongside the writing of Paulo Freire, and specifically the influential *Pedagogy of the Oppressed* in which he identified the process of *conscientizacao* (conscientization) by which socially marginalised groups were empowered to better understand the forces affecting their lives and who might then use this conscientization to undertake political action. Freire

worked to unpick the challenges of existing hierarchies, to develop processes of open dialogue which would then lead to meaningful change led by those who are oppressed by the status quo, empowering them to undertake radical action. (Freire and Ramos, 2017). A revolutionary thinker, Freire focussed on *dialogue* as a key component of understanding and learning: fully reflective on the interplay of power, fully present. This is particularly relevant in the context of this study which focusses on those who are part of marginalised communities and, in particular, people experiencing homelessness and people who are currently using drugs and are often disempowered by systemic practices, both in and beyond the digital space. People in these situations are often excluded from meaningful dialogue and instead are heavily impacted by systems and individuals who hold control, among other things, over access to shelter, finance, medication and support.

The first wave of PAR 'represented a new epistemology of practice grounded in people's struggles and local knowledge, but one that reflected earlier movements in India with Mahatma Gandhi, whose method of non-co-operation and passive resistance enabled what he called the practice of 'soul power'" (Kendon/Sivanda 2007). During this period, there was a proliferation of PAR approaches. Most notable amongst these is perhaps Orlando Fals-Borda, whose highly influential work in this first wave ensures his position as a PAR pioneer. As an academic and a political activist, disillusioned with the treatment of the working class by the political elite of oligarchs in Columbia, Fals-Borda dedicated his life and work to challenging the prevalent positivist approach of research at the time, turning instead to reflective practice-based research. In particular, he considered the possibilities of radical dialectics and change in the field of social science research when the researcher becomes self-aware and cedes the autocratic power automatically imbued in the traditional roles of researcher and researched. In a speech given in 1995, he outlined the key principles of his life's work:

- 'Do not monopolise your knowledge nor impose arrogantly your techniques, but respect and combine your skills with the knowledge of the researched or grassroots communities, taking them as full partners and co-researchers.
- Do not trust elitist versions of history and science which respond to dominant interests but be receptive to counter-narratives and try to recapture them.
- Do not depend solely on your culture to interpret facts, but recover local values, traits, beliefs, and arts for action by and with the research organisations.

- Do not impose your own ponderous scientific style for communicating results, but diffuse and share what you have learned together with the people, in a manner that is wholly understandable and even literary and pleasant, for science should not be necessarily a mystery nor a monopoly of experts and intellectuals' (Fals-Borda, 1995)

The principles outlined by Fals-Borda are embedded in the current study, which intentionally seeks to challenge existing power structures by placing those with lived expertise at the heart of the work, ensuring their meaningful participation as 'full partners and co-researchers and also by working to ensure that the findings of the partnership are shared in a way that is accessible, meaningful and also requires concrete and immediate action in the field of practice.

Anthropologist Marja-Liisa Swantz also contributed substantially to the first wave of participatory action research. Her extensive research focussed primarily on communities in Tanzania, and in particular the societal role of women, and was highly intersectional, exploring spaces including social and cultural anthropology, ethnology, the role of religion, and gender politics. Swantz's approach to PAR was entirely immersive, to the extent that she was adopted by a member of the Zaramo community in her early years of research, an adoption granted to her by an older community member to ensure trust and cultural connection, to 'set' her within her community as an equal. This adoption influenced all her future work. (Nyemba and Mayer, 2017) . Of particular interest to those engaged in research which is also immersed in practice is, is Swantz's ground-breaking work linking theory and practice working in Jipemayo, Tanzania working directly with villagers to explore community-based solutions for the various challenges faced by that community in the wider context of a government agenda for change to health and social care and education. This direction for PAR influenced the second wave.

Community development was at the heart of the second wave of PAR. Through the 1980s, Chambers notes that Rapid and Participatory Rural Appraisals were used to address the challenges of evidencing the impact of development work and as a 'means to involve people as agents of their own development' (Kendon, Pain and Kesby, 2007). To bring things to the current day, as noted by Pain, Whitman and Milledge, 'Many names are now used to describe research processes that are in some way 'participatory' including Participatory Appraisal, Participatory Learning and Action, and Community-Based Participatory Research. However, PAR is distinct because: it is driven by participants (a group of people who have a stake in the environmental issue being

researched) rather than an outside sponsor, funder or academic (although they may be invited to help); it offers a democratic model of who can produce, own and use knowledge; it is collaborative at every stage, involving discussion, pooling skills and working together, it is intended to result in some action, change or improvement on the issue being researched.’ (Pain, Whitman and Milledge, 2017)

3.2.1 Strengths and critiques of PAR

As outlined in the preceding discussion, PAR offers a unique approach to doing research, focusing on not only the democratisation of knowledge but also the consideration of the socio-political contextualisation of knowledge creation and ownership. It seeks to address power imbalances through meaningful dialogue and reflection and to react through purposeful and intentional *work*. PAR also continues to signal a political commitment, a commitment to collaborative processes and participatory worldview (Reason and Bradbury 2006).

PAR is *movement*: it is far from the static model of observational research. PAR is *doing*. PAR is, however, not without its critics. Frideres is particularly damning, concluding that participatory action research is an illusion which misleads researchers and which fails to make any positive impact on communities. (Frideres, 1992) Frideres sets PAR in apposition to what he sees as appropriate scientific enquiry: a methodology which is clear, focused, observational, and detached. PAR, he argues, is instead, often led by ideological bias; that research goals are often confused; that data is poor and gathered by those with little or no research skills and that research participants can ‘control’ the findings of research with the ‘final authority to cancel, change or restrict data collection, analysis and problem identification’. (Frideres, 1992). Latapi supports much of this view, asserting that PAR elicits research of dubious quality and that it supports a general climate of scepticism towards rigorous academic enquiry. (LATAPI, 1988) Fascinatingly, (for the purpose of this particular thesis) Court and Latapi also suggest that such scepticism ‘may be associated with a failure to appreciate conclusions which originate in the application of new technology’, continuing ‘not only is research technology mystifying to many – it is often imported, heightening scepticism regarding its appropriateness.’ (Court and Latapi, 1979).

There is much to unpack in these criticisms. Firstly, it is difficult to contest the assertion that PAR is impacted by ‘ideological bias’. As detailed above, PAR is political, highly contextualised and rooted in the democratisation of knowledge, which presupposes an existing power dichotomy and with particular consideration of both class and societal inequalities. PAR does not occur in a vacuum but rather deeply considers the context of the work and the

politics and hierarchies surrounding it. Furthermore, it seeks to *empower* those who have historically lacked agency to challenge the status quo and to effect change. This is indeed ideological, principled work: an overt and meaningful consideration of such a context is both necessary and helpful. (McIntyre, 2008)

Secondly, it is true that PAR is in stark opposition to observational and detached research. It *is* immersive and involved and seeks to be fully part of the work, a dialogic reflection. Consequently, there is little doubt that PAR is intrinsically messy. The research design and methodology *emerge*, rather than being imposed, as the questions, needs, abilities, and potential contributions of all involved also emerge. This emergence, however, is not an inconsequential part of the research: it builds relationships and trust, which contribute to richer data; it explores boundaries and sets any research directly in the space of *purpose* rather than research for its own sake.

Furthermore, there is also much to be learned from the process of emergence itself: the impact of systems; organisational structures; politics and personal relationships at play, which all impact not only the doing of the research but on the way in which data might then be analysed, and the resultant conclusions. In other words, 'In participatory research, you can help people in seeing their own problems. You do not tell them, 'This is your problem', but you work with them in a way that they become active.' (Nyemba and Mayer, 2017). Cook states that 'Investigations into the 'messy area', the interface between the known and the nearly known, between knowledge in the use and tacit knowledge yet to be useful, reveal the 'messy area' as a vital element for seeing, disrupting, analysing, learning, knowing, and changing. It is the place where long-held views shaped by professional knowledge, practical judgement, experience, and intuition are seen through other lenses. It is here that reframing takes place and new knowing, which has both theoretical and practical significance, arises'. (Cook, 2009)

Thirdly, despite this messy approach and the need for a creative and dynamic approach to methodology, there is no reason that the resultant data should be inferior. Frideres seems to confuse two issues within a participatory action research approach: that of the collective approach to the creation of knowledge, where every participant can share lived experience and where all knowledge is valued equally, and the analysis and writing up of this data, which may be *led* by the collective but implemented by those with understanding and knowledge in this space. It should undoubtedly be part of the work to empower and support all those who wish to engage in this part of the process, but not every participant has to hold all roles required. This is a vital difference. McIntyre explores this modality in dialogue with PAR participants, where they explore the different skills that each brought to the

research. It was agreed by the group that McIntyre's skills and knowledge were the most appropriate: 'You gonna be the teller, but it's ours'. (McIntyre, 2008). As for the assertion of 'final authority' where Frideres asserts research participants may redact data and result findings: this surely is an accusation that might be levied at all research, both in social science and beyond, wherever research is funded externally or released by an academic or other institution, or feeding into government. The fact that this does not happen routinely is a matter of academic integrity, and it is disingenuous, and one might argue, the perfect example of classism/elitism to suggest that somehow participatory action research should not require the same integrity.

Finally, the interesting point is that PAR may be a 'failure to appreciate conclusions which originate in the application of new technology' (Court and Latapi, 1979). This is a fascinating point in the context of work set so clearly in the consideration of the digital space and the ways in which that space might disempower and disadvantage the already disempowered and disadvantaged. Given that the authors are reflecting on pre-internet technology, it would have been impossible for them to imagine the vast scope of the way in which new technology might be used and applied to replicate and amplify existing social inequalities and where data gathered might itself obfuscate reality. In fact, it is helpful that the PAR approach can indeed challenge such conclusions, offering a human approach to the creation of data.

3.3 An outline of a PAR approach

Despite the discussions presented above, with the defence of PAR as a 'moving' methodology, there is nevertheless a commonality of approach in PAR work. Indeed, some may argue that it is a research approach rather than a method in and of itself (Pain, Whitman and Milledge, 2017). As discussed above, PAR seeks to position power within research with those who are most impacted by the research itself.

Central to PAR is the use of multiple iterative cycles, the implementation of which 'causes people to advance beyond knowledge gain to understand the issues they face'. (James, Milenkiewicz and Bucknam, 2014). These cycles offer systematic opportunities for planning, action, systematically observing and reflection, after which the cycle repeats, widening out and/or honing the research questions and focus. (McTaggart, Nixon and Kemmis, 2017)

Figure 7 - Illustration of Action Research Cycles

Source: from Reconnect Action Research Kit, p16, (Crane and Richardson, 2000), p16

Cycles may start at any part of the circle but must complete all four elements. It is also common that cycles overlap as questions emerge. While the process requires significant flexibility, it is also vital that there is a sense of clarity and deliberation to ensure that the work does not lose focus. PAR is cyclical in nature: a loop of Planning, Action, and Reflection, with evaluation work at appropriate points in the work. Work is intentional, and the action is integral. This approach is intrinsically about the 'doing' and, as such, requires a commitment to change and to exploring new and different approaches. (Malcom-Piqueux, 2015)) It can be messy, with external and internal pressures impacting the flow of work: this could be organisational structures and policies, for instance; it might be the availability and capacity of research participants, all of whom have different expectations of and commitment to the work itself. PAR can also hit unexpected hurdles: staff may move on to different roles; funding contexts, especially in the third sector, may alter the direction of travel. Importantly, the work itself can lead to opportunities, new ways of doing things, and to unexpected changes, which then lead to changes in the cycles of PAR moving forward.

3.4 PAR and digital inclusion in Scotland

While personal and political motivations, rooted in socialist thinking and commitment to social justice, impacted on my decision to adopt a PAR approach, it is also important to consider why this approach is particularly suited to the context in which the research is located. Digital Participation, as discussed in the literature review, is a devolved issue in Scotland and supported at the government level by the digital strategy: *A Changing Nation: how Scotland will thrive in a digital world*. (Scottish Government, 2021a) This strategy sets out the ambition of equality in the digital domain and to ‘achieve world leading levels of digital inclusion’. (Scottish Government, 2021a) The delivery of this element of the digital strategy has, since 2016, been led by The Scottish Council for Voluntary Organisations (SCVO). SCVO is a membership organisation representing and supporting third sector organisations across Scotland through the provision of services to the sector (support and training, for example); through lobbying and campaigning around issues of policy; and through the delivery of direct support (affordable office space; information for organisations). It is uniquely placed as an umbrella organisation, informed by and committed to the sector, and is, by its very membership, necessarily participatory. It is also an organisation rooted in socialist thinking and with a commitment to social justice. SCVO’s tie to the third sector offers a unique and helpful link to those organisations working most closely with individuals who face multiple exclusions and for whom digital has the potential to be an additional barrier to social inclusion. This relationship also offers a path for the researcher into third sector organisations and to those individuals supported by them, who are experts in their field of knowledge and experience. PAR then offers us a way to pull together to address the challenges of widening digital inclusion and, vitally, to ‘do’: to explore actions and solutions together.

SCVO has also undertaken significant work in the space of addressing digital inequality and in exploring how ‘digital champions might act as trusted intermediaries who could help and support individuals to develop essential digital skills in the context of wider, holistic support. For instance, a charity supporting refugee and asylum seekers to settle safely in Scotland, engaging with a myriad of digital systems (government; NHS; benefits; education) as well as providing direct support (signposting foodbanks; accessing accommodation; providing English language learning opportunities) might also be able to offer support that person to gain the skills they need to engage independently.

There is a significant symbiosis and interdependency here, allowing for meaningful PAR. The Scottish Government has responsibility for the development and delivery of policy related to addressing both digital inequality and wider social inequality; SCVO is the umbrella organisation acting as a conduit both to and from the Scottish Government and its membership body; and the third sector organisations have trusted relationships with the individuals. By placing the individual at the heart of any work and by recognising that they have the expertise and experience to inform any research into what works and what does not in addressing digital inequality, a PAR approach allows for action and insight to have far reaching implications.

Figure 8- Intersection of Knowledge Sharing in Digital Inclusion

This figure highlights the intersection of individual actors engaged in this work, showing the different ways in which the agencies 'frame' the digitally excluded individual, and also shows possible interdependencies and opportunities for collective action.

3.5. Personal positionality, expertise, and access in PAR research

It is impossible to undertake participatory action research without considering one's own positionality. In this work, it is vital to reflect on the role of the researcher and the relationship with everyone concerned in the wider body of research. Participatory action research work requires a close and collaborative working relationship, where everyone's expertise, knowledge, and insight are given equal value, although everyone involved in the

research may contribute this expertise in different ways. Reflection on the issue of positionality is essential in order to consider academic integrity, ethical considerations, research validity, and, for the PAR approach, the effectiveness, or otherwise, of implemented actions.

Thomson and Gunterb (2011) note that academic literature has often reflected the notion of the researcher as a fixed 'instructional' position, even in the space of action approach, but they reflect that it is perhaps more helpful to consider one's positionality, especially in the context of PAR, as a fluid state (Thomson and Gunterb, 2011), or as Herr and Anderson (2012) suggest, a 'continuum of positionality' (Herr and Anderson, 2012). One interpretation of my role within this study, is as a 'practitioner researcher', with many valuable insights from this approach reflected in academic literature (Jarvis, 1999). Often, however, such clear demarcation might also be considered to contribute to a power imbalance, continuing the notion that the knowledge and insight is being extracted from the field of practice, and resultant research output only seeks to inform at organisational level, and might therefore produce what has been referred to as a 'rhetoric of conclusions', disregarding the landscape of practice, and associated challenges, thus negating any real understanding of applied knowledge in the field and inhibiting discussions of power. In her introduction to *Pedagogy of the Oppressed*, Ramos notes the risk of 'exoticizing' lived experience 'as a process of coming to voice.' (Freire and Ramos, 2017), becoming instead a narcissistic approach on the part of the researcher, failing to link lived experience to discussions on the impact of the political, social and class structures at play.

This interpretation of my role does not best reflect how I see myself in this space and is perhaps the central reason why I was drawn to the participatory action research approach. In my collaborative 'professional' space, I was engaged by the umbrella organisation (SCVO) to develop and deliver training to those trusted intermediaries who would themselves be offering direct support to individuals impacted by digital inequality. Training, which is not underpinned by practice, reflection and lived expertise, however, is not useful in the field, but rather is both limited and dogmatic, offering a one-size-fits-all with an inherent power imbalance where the trainer is delivering a pre-determined 'script' that is not open to challenge, and is also unable to flex to embrace new insight. While the inside/outside view of the researcher may be helpful and offer clarity of boundaries and roles, it does not fully represent a realistic insight into the true nature of participatory action research.

Throughout this research, my positionality was in a state of flux: my commitment was to be part of a reciprocal collaboration, with equitable power distributed amongst all research partners and equal value given to lived expertise and academic insight. The reality, however, is that I was often an outsider (an external trainer) working in close collaboration with those delivering work on the ground and a further step removed from those most impacted by digital inequality. This distance was also important as an ethical consideration. The trusted sharing of lived expertise is not something that can be gained solely through even the most reflective of ethical approval processes. Rather, lived expertise should be shared in safe, informed spaces (with obvious, meaningful, and fully explained consent). People experiencing homelessness have often also experienced high levels of trauma, which could be further impacted by a clumsy and ill-informed extractive research approach. Working with trusted and trained frontline staff, who are themselves providing support through a trauma-informed method, allows an appropriate conduit for the sharing of lived expertise. Another valuable outcome of this approach within a PAR context is a further positive disruption of power dynamics in the relationships between those supported and those providing support.

I was also often an outsider studying insiders, my least comfortable position, but perhaps the most necessary in terms of doctoral output, contributing to the wider body of academic literature, but also, interestingly, furthering the knowledge base of practice. This position, as the outsider, not only helped my own work (attending conferences, writing papers and my thesis) but also allowed me to bring wider discussions from academic literature back into the spaces in which we worked together. This role was perhaps more to the fore during periods of data collection, data analysis or during writing up, each element requiring a certain level of detachment.

Building on Herr and Anderson's table on the continuum and implications of positionality (Herr and Anderson, 2012), I seek below to show how my different roles in this participatory action research approach influence my positionality.

Table 2- Adapted table on the continuum and implications of positionality

Insider (1) _____ (2) _____ (3) _____ (4) _____ (5) _____ (6) Outsider
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Positionality	Contributes to	Application of positionality	What has this involved?
1. Insider (researcher studies own self/practice)	<p>My role as a PhD student (self and professional transformation)</p> <p>Improved knowledge base informing work developed through academic research.</p> <p>My professional role as trainer/facilitator</p>	<p>Doctoral thesis; academic papers; conferences</p> <p>Research informed training content.</p>	Practitioner research and self-study
2. Insider in collaboration with other insiders	<p>Role as a trusted delivery partner within the wider context of digital inequality work happening across Scotland, and led by the Scottish Government and SCVO</p>	<p>Contributing to the nationwide community of practice focussed on both the impact of digital inequality and ways to address this imbalance.</p> <p>Supporting organisational transformation around digital inequality.</p> <p>Informing policymaking</p>	<p>Participating in knowledge sharing events</p> <p>Developing and delivering training at a national level through co-design approaches</p> <p>Contributing to and participating in strategic work around digital inequality at a national level</p> <p>Blogs, social media</p>
3. Insider in collaboration with outsider	<p>Implementing 'surface level' approaches to addressing digital inequality through training delivery</p> <p>Exploring existing models of evaluation frameworks (such as the Essential Digital Skills Framework)</p>	<p>Using nationwide approaches and 'testing' this in-house with partners such as SCS and Neighbourhood Networks</p>	<p>Sharing insights in both directions</p> <p>Re-evaluating frameworks</p>
4. Reciprocal collaboration (insider/outsider teams)	<p>Equal participants in research</p>	<p>Fully immersed in organisations committed to a PAR approach, addressing digital inequality, action, and disruption of hierarchical structures.</p>	<p>'pure' participatory action research</p>
5. Outsider in collaboration with insider		<p>Co-design workshops</p>	
6. Outsider studies insider			

This might be further reflected by the following illustration, which shows the ways in which, in a ‘typical’ week, I navigated my positionality.

Figure 9- Navigating Positionality

3.6 Engaging partners for a PAR approach

Having established a range of helpful relationships with the Scottish Government and SCVO, the next step was to identify those organisations interested in pursuing a PAR approach to understand the impact of digital inequality and what positive intervention could look like. Given the well-documented relationship between digital and other social exclusions (Van Deursen, Van Dijk and Ebbers, 2006; Helsper, 2017; Van Dijk, 2017b), it was possible to assume that SCVO member organisations, all of which are working to address social exclusion, would also be working with people who were experiencing digital exclusion. Two further indicators helped identify potential partners. The first of these was the organisation being in the process of digital transformation, defined by Vial as

'a process where *digital technologies* create *disruptions* triggering *strategic responses* from organizations that seek to alter their *value creation paths* while managing the *structural changes* and *organizational barriers* that affect the *positive* and *negative* outcomes of this process.' (Vial, 2019, p. 1) Within the context of this research, of particular interest were those organisations whose aspiration sought not only to transform the organisation's systems and processes but rather which set out to transform the lives of the people ultimately receiving support. As noted above, digital organisational transformation can also create space for so-called 'digital disruption' a phrase commonly used in the for-profit sector to reflect 'the rapidly unfolding processes through which digital innovation comes to fundamentally alter historically sustainable logics for value creation and capture by unbundling and recombining linkages among resources or generating new ones' (Skog, Wimelius and Sandberg, 2018, p. 2). In other words, the perfect opportunity for deep and meaningful change, which, when combined with PAR, has the potential to generate both positive action and an opportunity for collective learning.

3.7 Exploring PAR

Having thus established the basic tenets of PAR and the Scottish context, it is now helpful to explore firstly explore the selection process, which was part of the initial engagement. It was my initial intention to work with multiple organisations where the individuals receiving support were those who, according to the relevant literature, were most likely to have been impacted by digital inequality. To this end, at the outset of the research, I engaged with the welfare team at a housing association, a charity for people experiencing homelessness and a charity which worked with people with disabilities and others who were also socially excluded. Although engaging with the housing association would have been strategically beneficial, initial discussions demonstrated that implementing anything like a PAR approach would be beset with challenges related to systems, structures and business objectives. PAR requires a commitment to agility and disruption, and the housing association would not have been able to engage in this way at speed.

The second organisation was Neighbourhood Networks, a charity registered in Scotland with networks across central Scotland. Neighbourhood Networks emphasises the importance of providing preventative models of support, and opportunities for mutual support, to vulnerable people who might receive little or no support and run the risk of entering significant but nonetheless avoidable crises in their lives. It has its roots firmly in the notion of the renewal or revival of neighbourhoods and the broader community as places where people do not

only share physical space but actively cooperate for mutual advantage. This overall ethos sits firmly within the notions and aspirations of participatory action research. In the first year of research, I engaged significantly with the organisation, onboarding members and staff with PAR approaches and developing and delivering training and support for staff, members and parents and carers, all of which delivered both insight and positive action and which enabled the organisation to respond incredibly to the needs of members when the pandemic hit. The challenge with the inclusion of this work in the thesis was that framing the research within the literature to consider the impact of digital inequality on a particular demographic was challenging: members came from a wide range of socio-economic backgrounds; some members had disabilities (intellectual or physical); some members were socially isolated. Therefore, I decided that, for clarity of approach and methodology, the final thesis would focus on one organisation only.

Simon Community Scotland was the organisation in which I embedded myself most significantly over the five year research period. Simon Community Scotland is a registered charity supporting individuals at risk of homelessness or currently experiencing homelessness. The organisation offers a person-centred approach to ensuring people can access and maintain safe accommodation and to support people at risk of homelessness in a holistic way. Simon Community services are offered both in a physical space, including the Holyrood Hub (Edinburgh) and the Glasgow Access Hub, both of which offer digital access through fixed computers, with a place-based dedicated digital champion offering drop-in advice and support, and through street-based outreach and home visits to temporary and fixed accommodation. The organisation also operates several supported accommodation units. Furthermore, Simon Community Scotland applies a harm reduction approach to all work, which is again explored in the opening literature review.

Simon Community Scotland has a significant task to support those at risk or currently experiencing homelessness. In 2017-2018, 34,972 applications were made by individuals declaring themselves as homeless, the first increase in nine years. Shelter Scotland (2018) suggests that 11% of homeless applications were a direct result of action by a landlord or lender and 27% for other reasons, including loss of accommodation tied to employment. Furthermore, 47% of applicants to local authorities during the period 2017-18 who were assessed as homeless or threatened with homelessness had at least one support need, defined as a mental health problem, drug or alcohol dependency, physical or learning disability, medical condition, or difficulties with skills of independent living (Scottish Public Health Authority, 2018). This highlights the multiple layers of exclusion an individual may

experience and the correlation of many complex issues, all of which might contribute to someone becoming homeless.

Additionally, research also reflects on the importance of social capital with regard to issues of homelessness (Rock Trust, 2013). Habner notes that 84% of local authorities and 80% of third sector organisations saw a link between promoting positive social networks and overcoming homelessness, that 68% of all organisations surveyed felt that supporting social networks offered the best value in the delivery of housing services and that 62% of all organisations could evidence increased likelihood of tenancy sustainment resulting from receiving social networks-based services. This research indicates the correlation between social networks in Scotland and how they may be used to overcome specific challenges related to homelessness by creating a safe, trusted space. Historically these safe, trusted spaces would be physical locations, but increasingly as a society, we replicate such physical space in the online world.

A Connected Scotland (Shelter, 2018) notes that there is a need to provide more opportunities for social interaction for those affected by homelessness, promoting the effectiveness of pathways through third sector organisations as one way of moving forward, developing social capital, and drawing on Habner's 'networked approach'. Again, the digital champion model lends itself well to this thinking. Humphry (2014) argues 'for the need to recognise the ways that life situations and circumstances of hardship, such as homelessness, factor into the patterns of mobile and internet connectivity, creating unique issues of digital access and equity', arguing for knowledge of these differences to inform digital delivery of government- again, this would be a valuable opportunity to add developed research to this discussion within a national context.

Other research studies reflect on the way in which digital technologies are used by those experiencing homelessness. Bure (2006), through her research working within a central Scotland context, established that 'homeless individuals tend to use ICTs in ways which reinforce the patterns and practices of their subculture', highlighting that 'digital inclusion is often expressed as synonymous with social inclusion, with the deterministic assumption that one process can lead to the other. However, this study reveals that people who are homeless can be relatively digitally included, especially with respect to mobile phones, while remaining socially excluded' (Bure, 2006). Partially in contrast, Roberson and Nardi (2010) outline the ways in which digital tools are used by those experiencing homelessness, noting that 'digital technology use among the homeless is linked to

collaborative practices ensuring survival and inclusion in social worlds *beyond their immediate communities*'. (Roberson and Nardi, 2010). The close partnership with Simon Community Scotland, and most importantly with those experiencing homelessness, allows access to deeper understandings of digital inclusion activity's social/cultural and economic impact when delivered by third sector partners, especially when viewed through a Bourdieusean lens.

At the outset, Simon Community Scotland had 'self-selected' for research, applying to be part of SCVO's One Digital project at an early stage, expressing an ambition to develop a digital champion model to support the development of digital skills amongst those experiencing homelessness, which is core to One Digital. The organisation was, at the outset of the collaborative work, at a stage of digital maturity which would allow for a creative approach to addressing issues related to digital inclusion, including a recently developed infrastructure (the introduction of g-suite throughout the organisation) and, importantly, securing funding for a three-year project to deliver digital skills both to staff and to those experiencing homelessness. This project was to be both replicable and scalable to other organisations working with individuals experiencing homelessness.

In conversation, we felt our work together to be mutually beneficial. Simon Community Scotland stated that collaborative research rooted in action would allow for more nuanced reflection on their funded work and would hopefully allow the space for both critical dialogue and reflective action. 'It's a win, win, really. We can make it work – sharing everything and hopefully adding value both ways.' (Jamie, Simon Community Scotland). The timescales for my research and the Simon Community Scotland Get Digital Project were also compatible. Furthermore, Simon Community Scotland also hoped to investigate ways of measuring impact – both quantitatively and qualitatively, starting their work with the aim of embedding the recently released Essential Digital Skills Framework.

This overarching approach was a useful way of addressing issues of research design. From the outset, all parties (assumptive!) were interested in building in impact indicators, which allowed us to consider the wider implications of improving practice, our ability to work as partners in research and to explore non-quantitatively elements. Finally, the organisational culture within Simon Community Scotland, with values strongly associated with participatory action research, is important.

- Compassion and hope

- Humanity and Equality
- Choice and control
- Dignity and Respect (Simon Community Values, 2023)

These values are linked to the organisational strategy shared on their website, and this document informs all the work and support offered by Simon Community Scotland. Individuals experiencing homelessness are engaged at all levels of the organisation to contribute their own knowledge and expertise, to shape services and inform decision making, and it was therefore vital that everyone was involved fully in the project.

3.8 Doing PAR': working from the inside.

As discussed above, participatory action research is an immersive approach informed by lived expertise and which explores concrete action. It seeks to address power imbalance and, as such, creating a 'level playing field' from the outset is essential groundwork. For this research, as stated above, I sought out an organisation whose values were clearly articulated and that ensured the participation of those people with lived experience at all levels of the organisation. Once Simon Community was fully engaged, the second step was to engage 'experts from within' who would be interested in a participatory action research approach: people with lived experience, frontline staff, and managers, explaining to all of those involved what a PAR approach might look like, and the way in which it could result in positive change.

It was a personal priority to ensure parity in this process from the outset, and it was interesting that the first reflection on autonomy, power and an element of academic exclusivity came, somewhat ironically, from engagement with ethics and consent at the institutional level. All research requires, of course, informed ethical consent, not only to ensure the integrity and transparency of the work and protect all parties involved but also because the process sets one immediately in the space of the consideration of power and the ownership of knowledge. Furthermore, From the perspective of the academic institution, a PAR approach often means addressing ethics and consent as an iterative process. Because PAR is not linear and often takes different directions, as new research, learning, and action move the researchers towards new research, learning and action, it is vital that ethical consideration is given to new cycles of collaboration and that consent is constantly revisited and that that consent is informed and meaningful.

It was essential, therefore, that this process, for this work which seeks to explore the creation and 'ownership' of knowledge, was meaningful for everyone involved. An ethics application was submitted, and permission for research was granted, with the request that participants sign consent forms. Even though the institution has undoubtedly endeavoured to ensure that consent forms are as clear as possible, the consent forms required by academic practice nevertheless require high levels of literacy (they are not written in Easy Read English), meaning that 'informed consent' is not as straightforward as securing the signature on a written document.

To ensure equitable participation, no assumption of literacy was made: research evidence that lower levels of literacy and other social factors are important determinants of informed consent (Sudore *et al.*, 2006). In order to ensure informed consent, infographics were created exploring the themes of participatory action research using images and clear language, reflecting the studies which show such modifications improve overall comprehension (Campbell *et al.*, 2004). These infographics were then supported by face to face discussions, offering everyone the opportunity to discuss and explore the approach before signing, consistent with the discursive approach suggested by Tait *et al.* (Tait *et al.*, 2005). As we moved through the work together, I also created a video explaining PAR which could then be used by support workers in situations where my direct engagement would impact on spaces of trust and safety and where consent and PAR could be discussed with members of staff who had already been involved in the work.

Figure 10- Everyone is an Expert in Their Own Experience

02 ACTION IS PART OF OUR RESEARCH

— We will learn things by trying out new ways of working together.
We will:

Figure 11- Action is Part of Our Research

03 BRINGING ABOUT CHANGE

— 'Never doubt that a small group of thoughtful, committed, citizens can **change** the world. Indeed it is the only thing that ever has'. (Margaret Mead)

We are hoping to be a positive disruptive influence, lighting a spark for change.

Figure 12- Bringing About Change

Figure 13- Your Time Is Your Own

Having thus established the baseline, explaining PAR and then ensuring informed consent, the research group (consisting of people experiencing homelessness, frontline staff, senior leads and me) was then able to move forward with the 'doing' of PAR.

3.9 Participatory Action Research Cycles: Simon Community Scotland

Much has been written about the 'messy' nature of a participatory action research approach, and this presents a challenge during the writing up of a fully active immersive research period, during which my own positionality often changed, where actions were responsive and would alter the course of direction to meet the needs of those with lived expertise, and which also spanned a global pandemic. It is, to this end, that I have chosen to explore this cycle in a linear way to give examples of timeframes and extenuating circumstances which impacted on the work.

I am also mindful that in this writing up, there is a need to discuss the use of collective language, including 'we' and 'our' in the exploration of findings and to lay out a defence of sorts at this stage. Part of the tension around language is rooted in 'traditional' academic thinking around the ownership of knowledge or the importance of the researcher and of the need for a doctoral thesis to be defended as the work of an individual. PAR is, as discussed

above, a different approach. Throughout the PAR research period, there was a focus on ensuring that everyone involved learned together to acknowledge and appreciate their lived experiential knowledge as valuable and as expertise. As such, language often reflects a commitment to this collective ownership. Those experiencing homelessness would, for instance, bring their expertise and knowledge to the research, 'I' would bring traditional academic insight, for instance, or knowledge from the field of practice, and frontline staff would bring their own expertise from their roles and experience from the work. In accordance with PAR, none of these 'fields' is of more 'value'. It was the ambition of the work to resist people experiencing homelessness, seeing themselves merely as 'at risk' or as 'survivors' offering passive insight, but rather as possessors of invaluable knowledge. The second stage consisted of making the knowledge produced in this research the capital of the participants. Like the experience of Shimei et al., the aspiration was that 'within the research process, the opportunity to be seen as possessors of invaluable knowledge enabled them to recognize their knowledge as their capital. As Bat-El put it several years later, 'Once they saw us as "young women at risk", and now we are in a different place. We are young activists who lecture and teach about how to assist girls and young women'. (Shimei and Lavie-Ajayi, 2021)

We used several strategies to advance this objective. We ensured that participation was a meaningful choice, revisiting consent regularly. We shared every text and presentation created with all the participants, thus giving all our research partners equal access to all the research materials and the freedom to adapt these to whatever specific uses they chose research data, for example, informed many funding reports and further bids. Third, we encouraged the participants to use the research content in different ways, leading to the development of *By My Side*, for instance.

It is also essential to consider the importance of language in this research, and, in particular, to reflect on the anonymisation of data throughout the findings. People experiencing homelessness, and people currently using drugs are highly stigmatised in wider society (Belcher and de Forge, 2012) and as a result foregrounding their lived expertise without due consideration of the potential impact of such stigmatisation is remiss. However, within the context of participatory action research, there is a concern that such a decision minimises lived expertise, transferring the 'ownership' of knowledge, or that the 'paternalistic' anonymisation might reduce an individual's power and agency.

In summary, this decision to anonymise participants, reflects the insights of Moore: ‘Rather than a slide from an ethic of avoiding harm to a paternalistic notion of protection, I suggest that questions of naming in research, and avoidance of harm, could productively be approached through a feminist ethics of care.’ (Moore, 2011), it is the aspiration of work in this space that homelessness or addiction are *temporary* rather than permanent aspects of an individual’s life and it is hoped that the decision to deeply anonymise participants is reflective of the collective ambition to minimise harm, and is informed by principles of trauma informed practice.

In contrast to the anonymisation of individuals, the naming of organisations is relevant, ensuring that those organisations and those they support are recognised *collectively* for the time and effort given to the participatory action research, allowing for the centering of expertise. SCVO, Simon Community Scotland and Neighbourhood Networks are experts in the work that they do, and committed to the research. Furthermore, many of the tools created as part of this research were created in collaboration with the organisations and those people involved in the research.

The following explores the cycles of research, the approaches and actions taken, and the data collected through the different cycles. The focus of the methodological approach was to ensure clearly identifiable cycles of action, reflection, and evaluation, where participants were empowered to act as experts in their own experience, sharing insights and evidence in ways that were meaningful to them. Throughout this process data gathering was an active exercise, drawing on data gathered in delivery, using tools such as Mentimeter and Padlet, as well as field notes. I also carried out semi structured interviews, in person (at the Hub, pre-Covid) and latterly over Zoom or on the phone. I also directly trained and supported frontline staff who had trusted relationships with those people with lived experience to including to use similar approaches to gather data for the collective research. The research project worked with a total of 236 people who were supported by Simon Community Scotland, and 211 staff, in various roles in the organisation. Data was then thematically analysed using Nvivo.

These research cycles and the research methodology allowed for further research, and direct action responding to insights from previous cycles: a process which strengthened not only the overall research but which vitally contributed to the autonomy and agency of those engaged.

3.9.1 First Cycle: Familiarisation and Problem Identification

As noted above, SCVO offered a pathway into key organisations. My dual role as a training provider and researcher allowed me access to organisations working directly with people experiencing homelessness, including Simon Community Scotland, who were at the beginning of a digital inclusion approach. At the Access Hub in Edinburgh, a drop in space for people experiencing homelessness, I spoke to 50+ people using the space to identify key challenges they experienced related to internet use and gathering 'light touch' data. I carried out semi-structured interviews with a further ten, with the latter directly related to the Essential Digital Skills Framework. We also carried out focus groups with frontline staff and senior leaders in the organisation to better understand both organisational barriers and the thoughts of staff about the implementation of a digital inclusion approach within a holistic approach to overcoming homelessness.

The first reflections highlighted a need for people experiencing homelessness to be supported with a broad spectrum of essential digital skills, though the SCVO Essential Digital Skills framework was adapted to better meet needs. There was also a very clear reflection on the need for support around data privacy and security. The first reflective period also evidenced the need for staff across the organisation to focus on digital inequality as a theme of their work and to understand how this might be embedded into existing models of work and how this might sit in existing support plans. In the first action cycle, I created space for 132 staff members to explore the relationship between digital inequality and other areas of inequality, to explore their own fears and barriers related to embedding digital skills as part of their support, and to help them with their own digital skills through training. Throughout this period, data was gathered using Padlet and Mentimeter in group sessions to inform the focus of the next action cycle and to document the insights generated by participants.

After the above interventions, frontline staff then acted as 'digital champions', embedding digital skills within their wider holistic support, with data gathered in a specifically created framework which sat in support plans. The framework will be explored in more detail in subsequent chapters, though it is also highlighted in Appendix A. In keeping with PAR action cycles, I evaluated the first cycle drawing on data gathered in the framework tool (reflecting skills-only) and used extensive interviews with frontline staff to explore their thoughts on the transfer of those 'hard' skills to wider digital understanding and to investigate the application of that digital understanding.

3.9.2 Second Cycle: Get Connected 36

The second PAR cycle took place during the emergency Covid19 pandemic response, although it also built on the learnings generated from the first cycle. From March 2020 onwards, there was an urgent need to provide support for those placed in emergency accommodation. Funding was made available by Simon Community Scotland to distribute devices and unlimited data to those individuals who wished to be part of the project and to those who had been rehoused as part of the emergency rehoming.

The second cycle was informed by the findings of the first, with frontline staff familiar with embedded models of support setting up devices and distributing them to those in need, as well as providing support directly both in setting up the devices and in helping the device recipient develop digital skills and understanding. While the first PAR Cycle worked with significant numbers of both staff and people accessing services, the second cycle worked with a smaller number of people (n=36) who were supported in emergency accommodation because of the immediate Covid-19 situation. These people expressed an urgent need to access devices and connectivity to connect with family, friends, and services, while staff expressed an urgency to help people engage with key services and agencies that could offer emergency support.

The second reflections evidenced an urgent need for different devices for different people and that the response had to be both immediate but also highly specific to ensure that people accessed what they needed at speed. The Covid context also required a different approach for staff, some of whom were now either delivering support at a distance or were delivering in difficult circumstances in a shifting context. This smaller group also meant a richer data set through varied qualitative approaches, including semi-structured 1:1 phone interviews directly with both staff and device recipients, digital questionnaires distributed to staff, which contained several open questions and data gathered from the application of the framework. Frontline staff continued to offer support as digital champions, although they needed device-specific support to set up devices for people. This was supported by bespoke 'set up' training, which I developed and delivered and which included creating accounts for device recipients and installing priority apps (identified findings of the first cycle)

The evaluation of the second cycle used a newly developed framework based on the learnings and insights from the first cycle, focussing on 'Quick Wins', which would have the maximum impact on people. This was coupled with interviews with eighteen staff, who also collected qualitative data from those receiving devices by using

informal interviews to reflect on device use. This model allowed for rich data as staff stand closely alongside the people they support and have relationships to allow for nuanced discussion, which might inform practice.

3.9.3 Third Cycle: Get Connected 100

The significant impact of the second cycle highlighted the urgency of the need for people experiencing homelessness and by the frontline staff supporting them to access digital devices, connectivity and digital champion support. To this end, funding was secured by Simon Community Scotland from Scottish Government for a further 100 devices with unlimited data to be distributed by digital champions. This third cycle also required training and support, which I delivered to other organisations that had not previously had the resources to reach people in this way and whose staff needed 'onboarding' to PAR and the overall work model. The second cycle of evaluations evidenced apps and skills specifically related to the Covid-19 context, which had been of most help to people, which informed the third cycle. By this point, staff from Simon Community Scotland were fully immersed in the PAR approach and the models for data collection and in their 'roles' as trusted intermediaries to provide support around digital skills and understanding. New organisations were inspired by the learning of colleagues from Simon Community Scotland. Case studies were beneficial in the new training model to inspire and engage staff members from other organisations who had not been part of the same digital evolution that Simon Community Scotland had gone through.

One hundred devices were set up by staff members with accounts and apps for the device recipients. The apps chosen were selected with the individual in a 1:1 context and were therefore personalised and relevant. The 'Quick Wins' tool was re-visited in training delivered at a distance, using video conferencing tools and Mentimeter to gather staff insights. Case studies and insight from those with lived experience gathered in our second cycle proved to be particularly useful in helping new organisations to understand the possible impact on people and in overcoming challenges.

The third evaluation continued to focus on the Quick Wins Framework (providing quantitative data primarily related to skills) and was coupled with 1:1 semi-structured telephone interview with 45 staff, which I conducted over a two-week period. Interviews also included staff from other charities working in this space who were 'Get Digital' partners. Again, these staff also collected qualitative data from those people receiving devices by using informal interviews to reflect on device use. This model allowed for rich data as staff stand closely alongside the

people they support and have relationships to allow for nuanced discussion, which might then inform practice. It also allowed insights from wider organisations.

3.9.4 Fourth Cycle: exploring a digital approach to harm reduction

The first three PAR cycles demonstrated a need for specific support for people currently using drugs. The fourth cycle, therefore, used learnings from all three previous cycles to create a research cycle for women currently using drugs in supported accommodation to try and understand how the Quick Wins Framework and lived experience could help explore a digital approach to harm reduction. Women currently using drugs are excluded in almost all contexts, including in the digital space. Yet, findings from the first research cycle showed clear ways in which those using drugs might use the digital space to access information and support. Interviews and discussions with staff suggested that staff might have unconscious bias, particularly related to supporting people currently using drugs with digital devices.

This reflective period also highlighted that drawing direct links between the accepted approach to Harm Reduction and the 'governing' principles would be helpful to staff in developing an understanding of a digital approach to Harm Reduction.

3.9.5 Fourth Action Cycle: A digital approach to harm reduction

Unlike the last two cycles, this fourth cycle of work was restricted to Simon Community Scotland. 16 staff were engaged in open online sessions to introduce the project and were asked to explore their own concerns. A second session then looked at the relationship between the principles of harm reduction (as defined by Harm Reduction International) and digital inclusion specifically. Women in residential services were introduced to the Participatory Action Research model by trusted staff members, working holistically. [In addition, a video was made by](#) to introduce the work and explain PAR. All forty women in supported accommodation received devices with unlimited data. The women also led workshops supported by the harm reduction team to co-design an app for women currently using drugs. They were paid for their work on this project.

The evaluation process for the fourth iteration was more complex due to applying a fully PAR approach, led by lived expertise and involving a mixed methods approach. Quantitative data was gathered again using the quick wins framework, but data was also gathered through podcasts led by the women and through shared insights gathered in informal interviews led by the women themselves and by staff.

3.10 Summary

The focus of the methodological approach was to ensure clearly identifiable cycles of action, reflection, and evaluation, where participants were empowered to act as experts in their own experience, sharing insights and evidence in ways that were meaningful to them. Throughout this process detailed above, I carried out 44 semi-structured interviews held over Zoom, telephone and initially in person; I led and participated in 23 sessions with frontline staff where data was gathered both physically (in post it notes and similar) and digitally using tools such as Mentimeter and Padlet. I also directly trained and supported frontline staff who had trusted relationships with those people with lived experience to including to use similar approaches to gather data for the collective research. Data was then thematically analysed using Nvivo.

These research cycles and the research methodology allowed for further research, and direct action responding to insights from previous cycles: a process which strengthened not only the overall research but which vitally contributed to the autonomy and agency of those engaged.

Chapter 4: Findings - PAR Cycles

As stated above, the immersive participatory action research approach can make the articulation of separate findings across a significant timeline challenging. In this chapter, the key findings span the following timeline. The dates in the table below indicate specific external drivers, as well as internal cycles of action.

2018 - Secured Scottish Government funding to create a National Digital Inclusion Programme for Scotland's Homelessness Sector.
2018 Beginning of the PAR approach with people experiencing homelessness, frontline staff and senior leadership leading to the start of the first cycle.
2018 Development of the <i>Get Digital</i> skills framework and the Digital Champion Training
2018 <i>Get Digital Scotland</i> launch and training of the first cohort of Digital Champions
2018 Digital inclusion integrated within Simon Community Scotland services and widened out to other partner organisations.
2019 First Get Digital partners organisations onboard to expand the work to other organisations.
2020 Start of the global pandemic and rapid response developed as part of research cycle 2: The <i>Get Connected</i> pilot funded by Simon Community Scotland - Get Connected Pilot: A Rapid response to Covid-19: free devices, data, and support with Quick Wins Framework
2021: Research cycle 3: <i>Get Connected 100</i>
2021 – Research cycle 4: <i>A Digital Approach to Harm Reduction</i>

Figure 14- Timeline: Cycles of Action

In order to articulate separate findings and illustrate developments across this timeline, in this chapter, I will consider each of the four distinct research cycles in turn, all run in partnership with PAR partner, Simon Community Scotland, and these are referred to as Get Digital; Get Connected or Get Connected 36; Get Connected 100 and A Digital Approach to Harm Reduction (or ADATHR). Each project evolved from the findings of the preceding cycle or cycles. I outline some of the key findings from each research cycle, followed by a thematic

analysis in the next chapter which will reflect on insights gained from the consideration of more qualitative data and explore the themes in greater detail.

4.1 Action Research Cycle 1 – Get Digital Scotland

4.1.1 Exploring the essential digital skills framework

After the Simon Community secured funding from the Scottish Government to create a National Digital Inclusion Programme in 2018, the PAR approach was started with people experiencing homelessness, leading to the development of the Get Digital programme, and Get Digital Scotland, in particular. This is the first action research cycle considered in this chapter.

Initial research engagement was at all levels of Simon Community Scotland, from people experiencing homelessness to staff members and to senior level management, to ensure that the research was led by lived expertise. In this initial phase, I directly engaged with three separate groups to seek feedback on the Essential Digital Skills toolkit. Literature highlights the usefulness of frameworks in supporting different models for digital inclusion, and within a Scottish context, SCVO's leadership of an essential skills toolkit was determined to be a useful starting point, offering a shared language developed over time and used by both Scottish and UK Governments. The toolkit is referenced in more depth in the literature review, with reflection on other frameworks. In this initial engagement, the people participating in the action research were from three main cohorts, all based in Edinburgh:

- those experiencing homelessness and attending the drop in at the Holyrood Hub;
- the senior leadership teams;
- frontline staff.

The purpose of this initial work was to establish if there was a need for support with digital skills for people experiencing homelessness; to better understand needs, challenges, and opportunities; and to understand the different challenges faced by frontline staff who could act as digital champions.

4.1.2 The expertise of people with lived experience

Feedback on the toolkit was gathered in a series of one-to-one interviews with individuals at the drop-in who were already using digital devices. These individuals were assumed to have foundation skills and were, therefore,

able to discuss the essential skills framework and the questions within this framework. The consultation was limited by the number of non-English speakers attending the drop-in (an issue later addressed when considering the implementation of both staff digital skills training and digital champion training and which will also be reflected in the thematic discussion). Individuals were asked to reflect on a visual scale of 1-5 on how important the essential skill listed was to them, with five being the most important.

4.1.2.1 Communicating

Those interviewed felt that the ability to communicate with messaging tools or email was a necessary tool for applying for jobs, receiving paycheques, and accessing information from the JCP, but also primarily for staying in touch with friends and family. One respondent noted how access to social networks (WhatsApp) was influential in providing a route out of homelessness as she received ongoing support from family members abroad who were now acting to help her return home. Another respondent indicated the way in which he accessed food and respite through the Edinburgh-based project Soul Food using Facebook Messenger to identify where and when he would be able to access meals.

Posting directly on social media platforms had a more varied response: social media was perceived to be of lesser value, with several individuals giving information about negative experiences and about the intrusive nature of social media (for instance, a bad experience with online dating, another concerned about marketing specifically related to gambling). Two younger users, who self-identified as 'millennials', felt that 'social media is no longer relevant to us. We just message people directly'. Those who viewed social media tools more positively reflected again the opportunity to stay in touch with family and friends, with other, less confident users seeing social media as a 'next step'.

Every respondent rated keeping emails and social media accounts safe as 5 (the most significant), indicating that this is valued as an essential skill. Individuals felt very strongly about the importance of passwords and privacy; a significant number stated that they felt competent in this area (a statement later contrasted with staff insight which suggested these skills are variable). One individual noted that 'Privacy is everything to me'. In the facilitated session, staff noted:

' Some women are not digitally literate and may not view the option to get online as an exciting opportunity but rather a foreboding challenge. Particularly older women struggle with digital skills at our service.' (Staff member, Simon Community Scotland)

This challenge is familiar to anyone working in the digital inequality field, that motivation presents as an obstacle, and that age is often (though not exclusively) a predictor of digital exclusion. (Beam, Hmielowski and Hutchens, 2018; French, Quinn and Yates, 2018)

4.1.2.2 Handling Information and Content

Respondents were asked about saving information on the cloud (and finding from any device). There was a lack of understanding about this question and what it meant: supporting staff had to explain a bit more about what the cloud is and how it might be useful, with some staff also struggling with this unfamiliar language. After cloud technology was explained, individuals were positive, reflecting on how it might be used to store CVs and necessary documents. Again, privacy and security were highlighted as a concern: two younger men had an extensive conversation about the risk of using cloud technology and that 'anyone could access your data and private stuff', suggesting the risk to data privacy would be a significant barrier.

Accessing entertainment was considered by the majority of those surveyed to be of importance, with YouTube highlighted as a valuable source of information and entertainment. No participants highlighted subscription services, and these were therefore considered to be of limited value in this context.

4.1.2.3 Transacting

While buying things online was considered by the bulk of participants (9/10) to be either extremely or very important, and many individuals vocalised various issues, including the challenges presented by having no address to receive deliveries, to a preference to 'shop outside', where you can see your purchase and walk out of the shop with that purchase. One individual noted that 'I think I would be able to do it, but I would be worried about buying something online and how to tell it was real'. (Person accessing services at the Hub, Simon Community Scotland)

All participants noted the necessity of using the internet for online services and in particular Universal Credit and JCP platforms, as well as passport applications, but with varying skill levels and some participants expressed that, although they knew this to be an important skill, they struggled with this, with one individual noting 'I have used

all the online forms a lot, but I don't know how to use them myself'. (Person accessing services at the Hub, Simon Community Scotland) His access to Universal Credit was always supported by someone else with the skills to navigate the platform.

Online banking was an important skill, with several individuals realising the benefits of digital banking and others keen to do so, with one participant highlighting that online banking would allow him to carry out banking transactions out of hours, which he considered of particular importance. Three respondents noted that they lacked the skills to use digital banking properly (with issues related to passwords or basic digital skills) but would be very keen to develop the skills necessary for this.

4.1.2.4 Problem Solving

Using online chat to ask for help was relatively important, but feedback and engagement with this topic were limited. Again, most participants felt it was important to be able to use the internet to be able to solve problems, with many citing YouTube as a meaningful tool. All respondents used a search engine, and all referred to Google in particular rather than alternative search engines. Using digital to assist with navigation and travelling was extremely important to participants, with reference to Google Maps. One participant noted: 'I get lost a lot, so Google Maps helps me find my way'. Another noted that: "Google Maps is my tour guide in Scotland" (also highlighting online street tours he does for fun).

4.1.2.5 Being Safe and Legal

As highlighted above, being safe online was a key concern for all the participants, though, in this section of the toolkit, several expressed an awareness of their own limitations in how to recognise suspicious web links. One participant noted that: 'I don't feel confident doing this, and it makes me worry: sometimes things look true but aren't. Another noted: 'I don't know how to do this, but I know it is very important.' Passwords were also seen as critical, and examples were given of strong password protection: 'I know this is very important, and I use different passwords for lots of things.' (Person accessing services at the Hub, Simon Community Scotland)

All ten participants reflected on the importance of checking whether online information is true or false, rating this as 4 or 5 in importance. Two younger service users spoke at length on this issue and how hard it is to assure veracity - citing examples such as Wikipedia and how they themselves could doctor that information as an author. They also talked about how (with Wiki) you can then check on authors and other edits they have done. Both were

very concerned about truth and transparency. Other respondents mentioned concerns with 'fake news', scam emails and websites, with one user highlighting how she did not feel confident in working out whether things were true or false.

4.1.2.6 Summary

The insights from those impacted by homelessness evidence the need for support to be *contextualised*, with an understanding not only of the digital systems and processes which individuals are required to access to receive the most basic support (accommodation/finance/food) but also the different ways in which concerns around trust, transparency and privacy are articulated, and show how negative experiences in real life might transfer to the digital domain. The insights also evidence the way in which systems are 'done to' people experiencing homelessness and the sense of disempowerment this leads to. There are also helpful personal motivations and suggestions for websites, applications and opportunities which might practice.

4.1.3 The Framework and Toolkit: feedback from staff and senior leadership teams

Staff were incredibly optimistic about the ways in which essential digital skills might positively impact individuals experiencing homelessness, with examples such as positive social contact with family and friends and the consequent reduction of social isolation; developing a network of support; accessing information; supporting those with anxiety around social interaction; enabling access to welfare support, developing transferable skills which could be applied to a journey towards employment; accessing up to date information, including pending transactions giving individuals a 'real' understanding of their finances, which might thus help with debt management. It was also felt that the potential learning experience undertaken to enhance essential digital skills would support the development of social skills as well as boosting confidence, contributing to greater overall wellbeing. Regarding the framework, staff felt that foundation skills for Simon Community Scotland's engagement should also include the following:

- an introduction to the basics of language around ICT- e.g., what is a mouse;
- how to type on a keyboard;
- a basic introduction to apps and how to download an app;

- how to reboot (turn off); and
- how to log out.

Staff noted that communication tools are vital to those experiencing homelessness, highlighting the need to engage with Universal Credit and JobCentrePlus (or JCP) as examples and maintain social connections that they felt were essential to mental wellbeing. Staff also noted that digital offers a unique and beneficial communication tool for those experiencing social anxiety. Staff highlighted that passwords are an ongoing issue with people accessing services: individuals regularly forget their password and are logged out (and locked out) of their account, and regaining access can be complicated. Staff may have valuable solutions for this, which could form the basis of best practice for the organisation, and which might be replicated.

Staff broadly agreed with the content of the framework with regards to handling information and content, in particular, the need for individuals to be able to access important information from different devices and to be able to attach files to emails and other documents. Again, these skills were felt to help individuals engage with online welfare services. Staff felt online transactions have a significant impact on those experiencing homelessness- and again, the toolkit could be tailored to reflect skills such as the ability to bid for houses online, send messages on Gumtree, order food, using Edinex and EEA Settlement scheme applications (all staff examples).

The ability to support individuals with applications for Universal Credit was defined as a key skill - all staff need to be supported in accessing training on moving through the Universal Credit form and in the ability to use digital tools to check benefits entitlements. Staff also felt that individuals could be supported in comparing and understanding their rights using the internet. Some staff noted further that the opportunity to sit alongside individuals and help them with complex applications affords greater support. Staff felt that the internet affords the opportunity for individuals experiencing homelessness to manage all aspects of their health and that the toolkit should also reflect a health specific element for the purposes of Simon Community Scotland's project. This element would include accessing 'safe' health and wellbeing resources (including the NHS) and how to, book appointments online and order electronic prescriptions etc.

Staff discussed the importance of Google Maps and Google Streetview. In addition to supporting individuals in navigating the city to access different welfare and support services, staff also use Google Maps and Streetview to

support individuals in visualising potential properties before bidding, as the bid process gives very little property information. In addition to issues related to passwords (already noted), staff also mentioned the issue with communal computers and that individuals often fail to log out of these shared computers, compromising their own safety and security. Possible solutions that were suggested included an automatic logout and clearing of any saved data or 'Have you remembered to log out?' stickers on computers.

Staff also discussed issues of accountability and risk for individuals experiencing homelessness and that this should be built into any training and support offered (also referred to as 'responsible communication'). Academic and grey literature highlights that staff in any support role for individuals with vulnerabilities (including people with disabilities, young people in care, for example) express concern about the provision of support for online activity and how this might impact those they support. (Scholz, Yalcin and Priestley, 2017; Blank and Lutz, 2018). Furthermore, both pieces of literature highlight issues such as privacy and security and how, even when confidence in online security is high, this does not necessarily translate into action. ((White and Carnegie United Kingdom Trust, 2017) (Chadwick and Quinn, 2016)

Staff indicated a concern around the time needing to be spent on this agenda with individuals experiencing homelessness - while there is a recognition of the need to support those individuals in developing digital skills, there was a concern that it may detract from other areas of support. Staff felt, therefore, that any programme of support should highlight that the development of digital skills is part of the already holistic and person-centred approach offered by staff across Simon Community Scotland rather than something given priority over other support available.

To sum up, staff identified the positive outcomes for individuals gaining digital skills: from social connections, finding information and accessing key services or support to health and wellbeing benefits and personal development. However, staff also identified the risks in terms of privacy and security and felt that there was a need for some critical frame setting to avoid digital skills competing with other areas of support for resources or priority.

4.1.4 Beyond the Framework

Staff also identified specific challenges and issues particularly related to the people supported by Simon Community Scotland.

4.1.4.1 Addiction

'Working with people with addictions can mean it's really hard for them to do anything- we see them for a short period of time, and it's just not their priority.' (Member of staff at the Hub, Simon Community Scotland)

The nature of addiction impacts heavily on an individual's ability both to engage with opportunities such as digital, as well as with more pressing concerns (accommodation, health, food). A further issue identified by staff is that, while access to devices may be a challenge which might be met, 'feeding addiction is the priority (those struggling with addiction) will be likely to sell or pawn devices to feed addictions' Addiction came up with every group and is a particular challenge for staff, and while we discussed various strategies (especially the 'opportunistic' approach highlighted above) it will nevertheless be an ongoing issue.

4.1.4.2 Motivation

Lack of motivation is identified as an issue with people experiencing homelessness - there are so many other challenges to be overcome that digital is one issue in a long list of issues where there are competing priorities. Furthermore, many of those supported have had negative experiences in traditional learning environments and are fearful of engaging with learning. Additionally, some staff mentioned that service users are often concerned about the internet and that many will have a 'fear of the internet and not wanting to share information'; a fear which staff set in the context of data gathered through the welfare and other systems. Staff also expressed the fact that many individuals are at the absolute beginning of their digital journey and lack even foundation skills. Several staff felt that individuals starting at this level would need additional specialist support, which could possibly be provided at the new Hub.

4.1.4.3 Additional Support Needs

Numerous additional support needs amongst service users were flagged during this phase, including lack of basic literacy (again highlighted in every session), dyslexia, memory loss and the challenges of supporting people who have limited English language skills. Mental health was also raised as a challenge. While these issues were reflected by staff, they are also reflected in the wider literature, including Chadwick and Quinn (2016).

4.1.4.4 Challenges related to resources and technology.

Unsurprisingly, time available to provide support came up as a concern for staff, with some expressing the challenge of 'adding in' what some perceived to be an extra role. Staff members did not reject the idea of digital skills support sitting as part of holistic work, but rather that time is a constant pressure. Staff explained that staffing is often tricky - 'e.g., Parkhead is very understaffed'.

When we discussed this issue, we would focus on the person-centred discussion and the small steps towards digital change, which could also be undertaken as part of an everyday engagement. One staff member also commented that the organisation needs 'digital thinking as default: we need to get to digital as a starting point, with digital embedded across the board and with greater awareness of the benefits'. Staff in several sessions referred to challenges regarding resources and technology, and, as sessions moved forward, several members of staff stated that 'there are not enough computers' or that in certain services (e.g. supported accommodation), the equipment was not fit for purpose. Staff also described several situations where connectivity is an issue - both in temporary accommodation - and in supported tenancies. The fact that some service users did not have a digital device did come up on several occasions as a challenge. However, one staff member noted that 'this isn't necessarily an organisational challenge as individuals also need a sense of ownership and responsibility' (Member of staff, Simon Community Scotland), and other staff noted that individuals in supported accommodation have both a device and connectivity.

4.1.5 Action phase (first cycle)

All these insights informed the 'action' phase of subsequent work during the first action research cycle when digital champion training was implemented across the organisation, which used a reformatted digital skills framework to both baseline the skills of people engaging directly with support and allowed for the triaging of digital champion support (see Appendix B). All frontline staff were asked to act as digital champions, embedding digital skills support as part of their holistic work. Digital champions also received training informed by this lived expertise through a digital champion training module and offered digital tools and resources to help them in their role.

With the insight of the lived expertise as detailed above, the following actions were undertaken:

- The creation of a revised digital skills framework (see Appendix B). The digital skills framework would be part of the individual support plan to ensure that everyone accessing services would be able to have a guided conversation around digital skills and could be benchmarked accordingly and then offered subsequent support;
- Wholesale digital skills training for staff at the same time as a digital organisational transformation: Simon Community Scotland transitioned to Google Workspace and rolled out Chromebooks, distributing them to all staff. Support needs were identified as part of staff 1:1s (using the digital skills framework itself), and workplace digital champions were identified in the organisation to allow for staff members to be partnered up with others who had more skills and confidence;
- A digital drop in at the Hub in Edinburgh, offering connectivity and access through desktop computers with support from digital champions (data here was collected through a Tally Sheet, see Appendix C). This also necessitated the creation of a Digital Zone Fair Use Policy (see Appendix D);
- Digital Champion training was developed and delivered to 65 digital champions, which focussed on the different elements of the new digital skills framework and offered a range of digital resources to support digital inclusion activity, in line with the insights shared in the research phase above;
- Digital skills support was offered as part of holistic support, with data to be gathered as part of support plan meetings with data held by Simon Community Scotland in internal systems.

Findings from the implementation of the above actions were complex and less clear than hoped for at this early stage in the research. Digital transformation was undoubtedly helpful for several reasons. The significant investment meant that staff from senior leadership and middle management had committed to change and felt such change to be necessary and urgent, with a notable awareness of the impact of digital inequality on those accessing the services. Furthermore, staff were highly engaged in the digital space, accessing new technology themselves and therefore exploring their own digital skills and confidence, creating a greater understanding of the issues facing those using the services.

The first engagement with the assessment tool was challenging. It worked well within the organisation to identify staff training needs due to the requirement of inputting the data into a separate document sitting outside the online tool for support plans. It was less successful in gathering data for people accessing the services. The

confidence and skills across staff were varied, with significant numbers identifying a need for support with their own digital skills. Many staff at Simon Community Scotland also have lived experience of social inequality and are consequently also impacted by digital inequality. Staff articulated a need for additional support in cybersecurity and in the use of cloud-based tools, including Google Workspace. Follow up 1:1s indicated clearly that when less confident staff members were matched with a workplace digital champion, they were able to have open conversations about challenges and receive meaningful and personalised support, which boosted confidence and capability.

The implementation of the assessment tool for people accessing the services was more challenging. In the first instance, the assessment tool was created as a Google Form, with access signposted in the existing reporting structure for support work. Staff found jumping out of the main online system and into the form, an additional hurdle, and therefore, the initial data was not reflective of the number of those receiving support. Furthermore, the ambition of the framework was longitudinal, designed to be revisited to mark progress as skills were developed, but the reality was that gathering data in a few months was highly challenging. Often people had moved on from the service or might have changed support worker. Sometimes change was rapid, immediate outcomes achieved, and staff and end learners would lose focus on widening skills and instead only deal with the immediate crisis. Sometimes the person did not feel ready nor feel that the time was right to explore the online space, and consequently, the initial commitment waned. A further challenge in the early stage of the research was that many of those accessing the services did not have consistent access to devices or data and were coming to the Hub to make use of the connectivity and computers that were available.

This meant that the drop in at the Hub became a helpful space for a general understanding of the impact of the work to address digital inequality. The Hub is an incredibly busy space which serves multiple purposes. People come to access urgent information, advice, healthcare, support around benefits and emergency accommodation, and to get a warm meal. The Edinburgh Hub also supports a significant number of refugees and asylum seekers who are drawn to the capital city. The fact that the service offered computers and open Wi-Fi was also a draw at that point, and significant numbers of people would come to access these. For this reason, Simon Community Scotland engaged a member of staff to act as a paid digital champion, as well as volunteers. Gathering quantitative data again proved a challenge, despite the use of a tally sheet for ease of collection, and data gathered was therefore qualitative, through interviews primarily with staff, as details on people coming in and out

of the Hub did not allow for interview, nor would it have been appropriate due to the 'drop in' nature of the service.

The challenges in practice when directly supporting those facing digital inequality are often the limits on how, practically, an organisation can deliver and the day-to-day reality of that delivery. The following examples of pressures were shared by staff. Access remained an issue. The urgent need for more computers was swiftly actioned, increasing access from two computers to eight. Despite this, the computers were often busy and, although staff did not want to impose any restrictions, it became clear that this would be necessary to ensure that everybody who needed to access the internet would have the opportunity to do so. This was particularly important for those who needed to access Universal Credit journal entries, which have time limited submission requirements: to miss a submission date means that the individual is sanctioned with immediate impact and reinstatement of benefits can take weeks, during which that individual will have no access to money. To avoid such a negative impact and recognise that unrestricted use was not feasible within that context, as part of the research and in partnership with those using the Hub, a Fair Use policy was developed and implemented (see Appendix C). This restriction also negatively impacted an exploration of what 'meaningful' use might look like for those experiencing homelessness. Instead, despite best endeavours, this drew the work into a 'systems led' approach, in direct opposition to the ambition of the work. This restriction also had a negative impact on autonomous use: staff gave the following example:

'She comes in every week to access her benefits, and I help her every week, and I try and show her what to do so she can do it the following week. But then the next week, she's forgotten it all and no wonder. How could you remember all that stuff? It's just too much.' (Staff member at the Hub, Simon Community Scotland)

Outwith claiming benefits and exploring possible tenancies, the computers were, to a limited extent, used for a range of other things. People primarily used the devices for connecting with family and friends, predominantly through email and Facebook (WhatsApp was not installed on the desktops). As noted previously, YouTube was also a key platform for gaining information. Staff found it very hard to engage people in the Hub who were not using the internet. The computers were busy, and the atmosphere made concentrated learning difficult. An additional complexity, as noted above, was the number of Hub users who did not have English as a first language.

4.1.6 Digital Champion Training

With the insights shared in the first part of the research, a digital champion training programme was designed and implemented (see appendix D), developed and led by me, with sessions delivered in locations in Edinburgh, Glasgow, and Perth. This participatory approach meant that learning focussed on sharing challenges and exploring solutions was key, as well as boosting staff confidence and sharing resources which would immediately benefit users/learners. These resources included (but were not limited to):

- Learn My Way: a beginners guide to using the Internet;
- Internet Matters: a range of safety resources aimed at children and families, but which could be used by staff in support settings to easily walk through complex issues. Internet Matters also held helpful guides on YouTube and other social media apps;
- The NHS Apps Library: a catalogue of apps (for instance, related to mental health) which had been vetted by the NHS for use and which might then be applied in practice;
- Hollieguard: a personal safety app;
- Google Translate (live demonstrations of the practical application of this tool were particularly well received as many staff knew of Google Translate but had not used functions such as simultaneous interpretation or live document translation). It was important to note at this stage that Google Translate had many limitations: sometimes translations were inaccurate, for example, and should not be used for the translation of legal documents. A further example was that it would not support the many iterations of Romani used across the Roma population, who sometimes access Simon Community Scotland services, again demonstrating the ways in which technology can further marginalise;
- Live interactive safety exercises, including passwords, like the Google phishing quiz; and
- Accessibility features and how basic settings on the computer could be used to support people with literacy issues (colour inversions, increasing font sizes, using speech recognition technology such as the Google Microphone).

Staff were also encouraged to share positive examples of skills and tools used in the work, and some helpful examples were given, including:

- WhatsApp for people engaging in transactional sex, as a safety tool to let others know where they are, as well as to share images of violent, abusive or non-paying customers;
- YouTube as an active tool for completing a benefits form;
- Facebook groups to support people on a sobriety journey.

Each of these shows the immediate transferability of tools from one area of need to another. The digital champion training was incredibly well received and appeared to meet an urgent need. Based on the detailed feedback of 26 respondents, 100% noted that the training enabled them to reflect on the way in which digital inequality impacted on people experiencing homelessness and felt more confident in their own ability to provide support in this space. Staff comments included:

‘I thoroughly enjoyed this training, and everyone in my team that has attended has said the same thing. It wasn't what I expected - it was far better. Really useful information that can benefit work and personal life. The time flew by as we were having fun.’

‘The course helped me to change the way I think about supporting people. Prior to the training, I didn't think much about using digital to enhance the support I provide, and now I do. Sometimes the environment can be a barrier to using digital effectively, and I'd like to give this more thought/discuss more.’

Staff also noted that further support on safety and security online was needed. A further research outcome was a redesign of the internal learning platform to include all the resources needed for digital champions at Simon Community Scotland, offering ready access whenever needed.

4.2 Action research cycle: Get Connected or Get Connected 36

4.2.1 A pandemic response

In 2020, the rapid response to the global pandemic led to the development of the Get Connected pilot. This is the second action research cycle considered in this chapter. The fact that the participatory action research in this space had begun pre-pandemic and that Simon Community Scotland had already made significant leaps in their organisation's digital transformation and commitment to addressing digital inequality meant that when Covid-19 necessitated urgent change, frontline staff were already well placed to respond. On a practical level, there was a

rapid rehousing for rough sleepers across Scotland, with all rough sleepers brought into accommodation which was made immediately available in the now-empty hotels across the hospitality sector. Frontline staff at Simon Community Scotland were classed as vital frontline workers and, despite the risks of the pandemic, continued to work alongside those in need of support, offering a lifeline service to people in urgent need of support, delivering food, medical supplies, and extensive psychological and emotional help for people in desperate, isolating and often terrifying circumstances.

It was immediately recognised that the internet would offer a lifeline service, and, as quickly as possible, the organisation procured thirty-six (36) smartphones with unlimited data for immediate distribution by those frontline staff. Unrestricted data was vital to ensure that people did not have to make difficult choices about what was important. This active response also allowed space for a consideration of the limitations of the first cycle of work and to explore a different approach to the digital skills framework and reflect on the data that might be the most useful. Working collaboratively, a new *outcomes*-focussed framework was developed (see Appendix D) with an emphasis on getting people to the information they needed as quickly as possible.

Devices were distributed with extensive work done beforehand to ensure that the phone was ready to go, out of the box. To ensure that this was a uniform approach, digital champion training also offered support around device set up. This included a person-centred focus on helpful apps (to be pre-installed); necessary, safe information with regard to Covid-19. NHS Inform and Scottish Government were both installed as bookmarks on every device and added to the home screen to ensure ease of access, as was a direct link to the individual's UC Portal if this was relevant. Staff were also encouraged to focus on accessibility features and increase font and app sizes, and demonstrate different options. Staff were asked to support the device recipient in enabling fingerprint access to overcome challenges from previous work with regard to password and passcode access. A decision was also taken to install Google Translate and DuoLingo to help those for whom English was not a first language. Special attention was also given to the privacy and security of Google accounts, including challenges related to Google products and Google Maps, which at the date of research, automatically tracked geo-location.

4.2.2 Evaluating Get Connected

This cycle of research was incredibly positive, with the following overarching statistics taken from the Get Connected Evaluation questionnaire:

- 100% of those receiving a device stated that it positively impacted their life;
- 84% felt more confident;
- 100% found the support of digital champions useful;
- 81% increased their use of digital tools.

97% of those using the devices highlighted the significance of those devices as a form of immediate connection with people and organisations. People extensively used the device to connect with family and friends and to access support from Simon Community Scotland staff, as well as other essential services (e.g., for benefits, DWP, JobCentre Plus). Learning was also a key outcome. For many people receiving a device, this opportunity acted as a catalyst for developing a new skill (a surprising number of people engaged with DuoLingo, even those who spoke English as a first language). Some people access formal learning institutions, for instance, by doing their college work or making a college application. This insight also resulted in action directly with colleges outwith the project.

It was also clear that the devices enabled people to access significantly more support. People receiving devices could contact support workers easily and more frequently than before the pandemic, as well as directly engage with other significant support agencies (e.g. the NHS or local authority). Notable also was that the research reflected an increase in confidence in the use of the device and in expanding the tools people with devices used. Furthermore, access to the connected device empowered people to do things on their own, increasing autonomy and independence and often impacting the type of support Simon Community Scotland was offering, in a positive way, with people moving away from 'task-based support' (for example, a staff member 'doing' a quick digital task for the person accessing services) to more resounding, more personal or emotional support. Devices were also used for entertainment, with online leisure activities including listening to music, watching videos, reading, and playing games, all of which contributed to an increased sense of well-being and enjoyable use of free time. Challenges in this cycle were limited. Some of those receiving a device reflected the challenge of using a new device and of the unfamiliarity. However, the person-centred approach, the device set up, the unlimited freedom of use and the focus on a new framework exploring high impact 'Quick Wins' made a significant difference.

4.2.3 Staff Feedback on Get Connected

Staff feedback was overwhelmingly positive, even from those staff members who thought that the people they stood alongside might struggle using a digital device. Providing support with digital skills during social distancing was challenging and took time, but staff also reflected on how much people engaged independently with their own learning and moved forward quickly. From a staff perspective, there was a noticeable increase in the support worker's ability to reach service users to provide support, as well as service users initiating contact with Simon Community Scotland staff and other agencies. Historically, contact with people was often fragmented and difficult as people did not necessarily have access to a device. If they had a device, they often did not have the necessary data or call package to make contact easy. A further consideration was that the rehousing also meant that all device recipients had the necessary access to power to ensure devices were always charged. Staff also noted that English is a significant obstacle for many people accessing services and, consequently, for staff members. The use of translation apps (Google Translate) and language learning tools (DuoLingo) was a huge benefit. A side issue was that staff reflected how genuinely thankful people receiving devices were to be part of the project. This made staff feel highly valued as they were delivering powerful and immediate impact, although there was a notable discomfort amongst staff with the awareness of this power dynamic, with one staff noting, 'I didn't want people to thank me for something they needed so much, that so many of us have and take for granted'. Staff were also surprised at the fact that people learned how to use digital tools very quickly, even those with very low levels of digital skill and confidence. Staff felt it was ownership of a connected device that was the catalyst for rapid learning.

4.3 Action research cycle 3: Get Connected 100

The third action research cycle to be considered in this chapter followed Get Connected (also known as Get Connected 36) in 2021 with the Get Connected 100 programme.

4.3.1 Insights from Interviews

The success of the pilot work in Cycle 2, and the immediate results gathered from a streamlined and effective process meant that Simon Community Scotland was then able to secure additional funding to support a further one hundred people with devices, unlimited data, and digital champion support. Again, the Quick Wins Framework underpinned the work, with hard data gathered at the commencement of the pilot and 6-8 weeks

later and complemented by narrative data, again through interviews (see Methodology). The following insights were gleaned from the results of the digital skills framework questionnaire responses from those people with devices and gave a broad insight into the immediate impact of the intervention. This data is helpful as an overview, which is then complimented by the richer data from the qualitative inquiry. The following insights were shared by device recipients, who were asked by frontline staff how the devices had impacted their lives.

Figure 15- Impact of Devices on Participants' Lives

Source: Simon Community Scotland

Even with a larger sample size, the results of the questionnaire supported the positive experience of those in receipt of devices, the ability to find information and use digital tools (including those used to access support) and support improvements in health and wellbeing, in this case in terms of increased personal confidence. These findings resonate with findings from preceding research cycles, particularly in the first cycle - Get Digital. This also showed overwhelming support for the digital champion model. Diving into the information, it is possible to explore the purposes for which the devices and data were used with the following insights:

Table 3- Data on purposes for which the devices and data were used (Simon Community Scotland)

Email	68%
Telephone Calls	58%
Messaging	65%
Video Calls	57%
Social Media	72%
Person or Group	Percentage of People

Friends and Family	74%
Support worker	65%
Government Services	49%
Online Communities	35%
Information Type	Percentage of People
News and Updates	70%
Health Info	52%
Information from Authorities	45%
Tools for Managing Finances	Percentage of People
Online Banking	34%
Paypal	10%
Benefits	34%
Shopping	32%

(Simon Community Scotland)

The data supports the narrative explored in preceding cycles, namely that social media and connections with friends and family and support workers are some of the most positive experiences of those in receipt of devices. The skills framework demonstrates better access to information, though not used by all to access health information or information from authorities; the fact that access to these sources was enabled by the devices is important. Further, the extent to which people with devices use them for online banking, accessing the benefits system and shopping further underscores the findings from the first research cycle, particularly in respect of how digital usage can exceed staff expectations.

4.4 Action research cycle 4: ADATHR

Finally, and running concurrently with the Get Connected 100 programme, A Digital Approach to Harm Reduction (or ADATHR) is the fourth action research cycle considered in this chapter.

4.4.1 Digital inclusion work in a harm reduction context

As noted above and elsewhere in this thesis, a significant sub-group within those accessing services at Simon Community Scotland consists of people currently using drugs. To tackle the impact of digital exclusion on vulnerable groups, A Digital Approach to Harm Reduction facilitated the provision of seventy devices (60

smartphones, ten tablets) and unlimited connectivity for 12 months to women currently living across four Simon Community Scotland-supported accommodation services alongside support from trained digital champions. The project was a wide ranging one, drawing on holistic care (beyond the scope of research, but highlighted below to add insight and context) and exploring the impact of digital inclusion work in this space as part of this wider work. This also focussed on the women's lived expertise.

In this cycle, the digital skills framework was adapted to consider the digital resources and tools that exist to inform and educate people about their drug use. A 'Quick Wins' database of harm reduction information was developed, allowing digital champions to signpost people to a wide range of online, evidence-based information and services. This meant that staff were able to focus on the content of greatest relevance to those using the service and further empowered individuals to search for and locate evidence-based information that met their needs at the time they chose.

4.4.2 Insights from project participant data

Data was gathered both from the direct work related to digital inclusion and the evidence coming from the application of the Quick Wins Framework. The digital connection was found to be a key benefit for women engaged in the project. 97.3% of participants said that they utilised their device for telephone calls, 70.3% of participants said that they utilised their device for video calling, and 100% of participants said that they utilised messaging tools on their device, such as WhatsApp. Prior to receiving a device, each participant was set up with a unique email address and supported to use this address to receive communications regarding their care, with 73% of participants going on to use their email addresses in varying capacities throughout the project. 73% of participants used social media, and communication tools like WhatsApp and Facebook Messenger proved popular:

'It felt amazing. I could see my daughter. If it wasn't for the phone, I'd be lost because that's the only contact I've got [with] my daughter, through Facebook.' (Woman in supported accommodation with Simon Community Scotland)

Digital provided a way of enabling women participating in the project to connect with loved ones, as well as ensure they related to their wider community and services that were currently supporting them in their care. This relational aspect is a vital element in the implementation of the Medically Assisted Treatment Standards (MAT

Standards), which will be explored in more detail in the thematic analysis. The other statistics from this research were as follows:

4.4.2.1 Addressing social isolation:

- 97.3% communicated with friends and family.
- 89.2% communicated with their support worker.
- 75.7% communicated with government services, specifically regarding health and benefits.
- 35.1% connected with online forums, groups and supports.
- 100% felt more connected with the people in their life.
- 100% felt more connected with services and organisations that they needed.

4.4.2.2 Engagement with services:

- 62.2% interacted digitally with Alcohol and other Drug services.
- 75.7% interacted with Care Managers, Caseworkers or CPNs
- 59.5% interacted digitally with mental health services.
- 37.8% interacted digitally with sexual health services.
- 94.6% felt it useful to be able to access services digitally.
- 71% utilised their device to link in with recovery communities.

4.4.2.3 Accessing safe and reliable information

Through implementing a harm reduction approach within supported accommodation services, it became clear that women who had used drugs historically throughout their lives had little or no access to harm reduction information that represented their needs, spoke to their experiences, or was presented in an accessible format. Additionally, women had little access to evidence-based harm reduction information and advice due to not having reliable access to the internet or knowledge of what resources were available. The database of essential apps and websites, and the accompanying digital skills framework, formed the early foundations of an app, By My Side, which was to become a key outcome of the project. This app was co-produced alongside women engaged with the project and collated all evidence-based information into one easily accessible digital space. By My Side was developed to offer flexibility and choice to ensure women at risk of harm have easy access to information that they may need in a format that is right for them. Research among participants found that:

- 97.3% felt more informed being able to access information on their device;
- 60% used their device to access apps to support their mental health;
- 25.7% used their device to access overdose awareness information;
- 17.1% used their device to interact with safer injecting information;
- 25.7% used their device to access general drugs information; and
- 25.7% used their device to access tools to track their alcohol or other drug use.

Due to an increased commitment to harm reduction across Simon Community Scotland, it was possible to ensure the implementation of By My Side within women's supported accommodation services by offering specific training to frontline staff as part of a digital champion training and by highlighting the way in which By My Side could support staff to develop their practice and provide immediate evidence-based information and interventions to women they were supporting who experience problem drug use. The ownership of the app, and the co-design approach, meant that Simon Community Scotland was able to take learning from the key themes that were arising throughout the project, enabling staff to respond to the challenges that the women were (and are) facing. The content on the app was frequently updated to reflect information women were telling staff they needed to access, such as information to support those experiencing domestic violence and harm reduction information for women engaged in transactional sex. This allowed women to feel empowered to find educational material in an accessible format, alongside their Support Worker or in their own time using their digital device. As one woman stated: 'By My Side gives you the option of self-help if you're struggling to access services, giving yourself knowledge. A self help guide if you need it to be. It's informed me so much and helped me with my needs.' A further outcome was that this access also created greater autonomy for the women who were able to access the information they needed independently and at the point of need rather than accessing this information through a staff member. Once again, this supports the implementation of the MAT Standards by offering autonomous, independent information and, indeed, care when needed.

4.4.3 Co-production as a Tool to improve outcomes

This final cycle of research was the one in which a genuine PAR approach was most evident. Having seen the huge impact of PAR in the previous three cycles between 2018 and 2021 and the way in which both people accessing services and frontline staff were more able to effect meaningful, autonomous change if a PAR approach was

taken, Simon Community Scotland employed a Digital Harm Reduction Coordinator to support the facilitation of A Digital Approach to Harm Reduction and further develop the harm reduction strategy within the organisation. Some time was spent onboarding the member of staff to the research, exploring together the principles and applications of a PAR approach and the way in which, through adopting a co-production approach, this project put the voices of women who use drugs at the centre. To this end, and to set the work in the field of practice, we utilised the Social Care Institute for Excellence's definition of co-production:

‘Co-production is not just a word, it’s not just a concept, it is a meeting of minds coming together to find a shared solution. In practice, it involves people who use services being consulted, included, and working together from the start to the end of any project that affects them.’ (SCIE, accessed April 2023)

The model of practice involved working with a key cohort of women within Simon Community Scotland services over a twelve-month period through a series of collaborative workshops, as well as through the wider work offering devices and connectivity.

These workshops were led by harm reduction practitioners, and in these ‘Design Labs’ the women looked at critiquing existing harm reduction material and explored the shared challenges and barriers women who use drugs in Scotland face. ‘Design Labs’ often took place on a one-to-one basis, offering the opportunity for relationship-based practice, a key element of the project for women who were often disclosing intimate and sensitive information based on their own expertise in navigating the system of homelessness. These workshops used a mix of blended delivery, taking place both digitally, using video platforms such as Google Meet, and in person. This allowed easy adaptation to the ongoing Covid-19 pandemic and national lockdown regulations. The promotion of digital skills among women involved in the project offered a layer of flexibility and choice for women who wanted to carry these out in the privacy of their own homes. Although these workshops initially intended to build educational resources to provide information about how to use drugs safely, women, understandably, were more inclined to discuss their wider experiences of trauma and loss stemming from systemic violence and historical traumatic events in their lives. Repeatedly, women shared their experiences of domestic violence and sexual violence, loss of contact or custody with children through social work involvement, societal stigma, transactional sex, poor mental health, contracting blood borne viruses, engaging with the criminal justice system, and

navigating homelessness and healthcare. Each of these themes was linked contextually to women using drugs to manage the negative emotional and psychological impacts of trauma.

This led to the development of a range of resources to support other women with their drug use, developed through two specific formats: educational and informative advice on how to maintain physical and mental wellness while using drugs and resources based on women's personal experiences. The latter saw the development of a podcast series, where women were able to speak transparently about what they had gone through, with the aim of helping other women and reminding them that they are 'not alone'. Through utilising a co-productive approach, women could share their stories while retaining full control of the finished product. This, in turn, provided a sense of ownership and catharsis for women who have engaged with multiple services throughout their lives and historically had their experiences and stories captured in case notes, files and referral processes. 'If it will help one person...' was a phrase repeatedly heard throughout the project, with women finding comfort that other women with shared experiences may learn from their insight and knowledge.

Exploring models of peer employability, women were compensated throughout the project for the time and effort they contributed to the development of resources, to value their contributions as expertise and follow a truly co-productive model of working in equal partnership for equal benefit. The latter six months of the project saw the development of a woman's harm reduction programme to provide the opportunity for women not engaged in Simon Community Scotland residential services to be involved in co-production work. This provided an additional layer of experience as women in the wider community came together to contribute and raise awareness of the key barriers and challenges they face as women who use drugs. Looking closely at a 'peer educator' model of involvement, women were able to exercise facilitation skills alongside other women and carry out a 16-week programme of learning that focused specifically on relationships, personal safety, mental health, alcohol and other drug use, empowerment, and sexual health. This space also allowed a unique opportunity to invite external partners to work alongside women involved in the project, including the Scottish Drugs Forum and Sandyford Sexual Health Clinic. Additionally, staff were able to provide overdose awareness training for women, focusing on both opioid overdose and the use of Naloxone in an emergency, as well as stimulant overdose training.

The harm reduction programme allowed for an exploration of opportunities for employability for women.

Throughout the project, staff have heard the challenges women face accessing employment while engaging in

Medical Assisted Treatment, highlighting the need for more meaningful, paid opportunities for people who use drugs to engage in service design and delivery. As noted above, building upon the combination of the digital harm reduction framework and co-production work alongside women, a key project output was the creation of a new, digital harm reduction app 'By My Side', pulling together the most reliable, evidence-based harm reduction resources that exist and hosting them within one digital space. This resource was intended to support the harm reduction approach within Simon Community Scotland and staff with their learning and development, ensuring all resources staff may need to support someone with their alcohol or other drug use are hosted in one place with easy access. The project, the training and the app were recognised for their substantial impact at the 2023 Digital Health and Social Care Awards. These form the basis of the Scottish Government's work to minimise drug related death through the work of Digital Lifelines, a national approach which seeks to 'improve digital inclusion and to design digital solutions that better meet people's needs, to improve the health outcomes for people who use drugs, reducing the risk of harm and death.' (Digital Lifelines, 2023)

4.5 Findings from the Framework

Throughout the research period, there was a need to create a framework by which some empirical data might be collected for funders specifically. Such a framework might also inform staff specifically about the types of engagement that would be most beneficial to those with lower levels of digital skills and would be most likely to lead to tangible outcomes in a short time. To this end, as noted above, the Quick Wins Framework was developed and offered a framework with recommendations for staff to explore high impact apps and websites in their holistic support, each of which contributed to a specific tangible outcome which might then be reflected back to funders, as well as informing research. The following section presents findings from the research that align with the five areas explored in the Get Connected framework. These are:

- (i) Communication and connection;
- (ii) Money matters
- (iii) Leisure and Education
- (iv) Finding information
- (v) Health

These are all considered in the context of staying safe online. I will also highlight some findings from the research in relation to digital literacy.

4.5.1 Communication and Connections

In all of the research cycles, one of the primary outcomes of digital inclusion work has been that those receiving support through the projects used digital access to connect with family, friends and loved ones. In this regard, the work broadly reflects trends in outcomes like wider work engaging people who are offline, with examples, for instance, reflected in research conducted by French et al. in partnership with Good Things Foundation (French, Quinn and Yates, 2018). Access to social networks is a common motivation for people who are offline. However, in the context of homelessness, where people are often impacted by multiple layers of social inequality and by highly complex personal and often traumatic situations, the importance of these networks is different, as can be seen in the following examples:

‘It means that I can get in contact with my family; I’m contacting my family every day whereas. I didn’t have a good relationship with them, but now I do because I’ve got a phone, and I’m able to Facetime my nephew and stuff like that. It also helps me talk to my workers.’ (Man accessing support from Simon Community Scotland)

‘I really appreciate it; it’s such a lifeline; as I said, having to phone my mum, I’d have to go to the nurses’ station, and you can’t really speak privately because they can hear, but having my own phone I can contact her from my room.’ (Man accessing support from Simon Community Scotland)

‘It means that I can keep in contact with my brother and the rest of my family. I’ve not been connected to in a long time, to anybody, anything. It makes me feel great.’ (Man in supported tenancy, supported by Simon Community Scotland)

‘The best thing was getting in touch with my son and arranging my first-ever visit for the first time in two years.’ (Woman in supported accommodation with Simon Community Scotland)

In each of these examples, what is reflected is not simply a simple call but is a call of tremendous personal significance enabling an individual to have a life-altering connection with a family member. It is well documented that a breakdown in social networks can be part of a highly complex picture of why someone may experience homelessness (Belcher and DeForge, 2012; Somerville, 2013; Phillips, 2015) and that social networks can also be a part of recovery from homelessness. The experience of chronic homelessness can lead to what has been referred to as a 'social network decay' (Golembiewski *et al.*, 2017): maintaining social networks through digital means, therefore, is of deep significance and an incredibly important outcome of digital inclusion work.

Findings from the first (Get Digital) and second (Get Connected) research cycles meant that a greater focus was given to the impact of connection as the research work moved forwards and, in particular, the way in which research participants might be supported in developing and maintaining a network of support. Frontline staff, acting as digital champions, were given space in training and support sessions (which I led) to explore the importance of connection, particularly the relationship between *lack* of connection and addiction. This session was supported by the articulation of this message in a YouTube video of the well-known speaker Johann Hari who articulates that: 'The opposite of addiction isn't sobriety, it's connection.' The contextualisation of digital inclusion and harm reduction was particularly important. According to Faulkner-Gurstein, a successful programme of intervention of drugs such as Naloxone (a peer-administered potentially life-saving drug administered in the situation of overdose) is dependent on the application of 'social logic', that is, the support of relational interdependencies. (Faulkner-Gurstein, 2017). It is perhaps unsurprising, therefore, that staff immediately highlighted the ways in which digital tools supporting relationships might be useful in the context of harm reduction and, more particularly, in the context of the field-based practice of 'never use alone'. Garcia highlights the significance and importance of 'relationships of dependency', and rather than viewing this as a weakness, it might also 'be presented as a resource for being included, loved, and cared for.' (Garcia, 2014, p6) Furthermore, if one is aware 'of normative notions of morality (and the ethical purchase of personal choice and autonomy in drug recovery (...)), it might be hard for some to surmise such dependency as moral, especially given the status as 'addicts'. But to dismiss (...) insights into the life-sustaining aspects of dependency would not only flatten our understanding of this complex domain but would also refuse to acknowledge its vital importance' (Garcia, 2014, p.6). In other words, the support people using drugs might offer each other is vital.

There are several ways in which social connection, and the digital space, might be used to support people who use drugs, and all staff cohorts reflected this. Not only does accessing tools such as Facebook and email, for example, strengthen and facilitate existing networks of relationships with family and friends, and offer a sense of 'social belonging' often lacking for people currently using drugs (Schlosser and Harris, 2020) but it can also be used, especially in the Covid-19 context, to maintain sobriety journeys through peer support from twelve step programmes or to create 'safe spaces' where people using drugs might do so in the company of another person. All these examples were cited by staff as helpful in the context of practice.

Time and again, research participants articulated the vital importance of this network of support, and the fact that being digitally connected allowed them to maintain these networks and even expand them in a way that was previously closed off to them. Staff also articulated that *their* support with individuals was strengthened and that if a person had access to a device and connectivity, they were more able to stay in touch, even when circumstances changed. One example given was that a person who had received a device experienced a period of extremely poor mental health, which subsequently resulted in admission to a secure unit, and the member of staff was able to maintain a stable connection with that person.

Reaching out to services and making connections not only with family members and loved ones but with networks of professional and informal support was also a repeatedly evidenced outcome. One example was the following insight from one research participant:

'I'll be honest with you as well, I'm in recovery, and this means I can take part in my meetings. I'm part of several men's groups, and I do stuff with SAMH and an Agency called FIRST through Microsoft Teams. I have meetings with those guys at least once a week, along with another agency called DAPL. I use loads of services. WhatsApp, Facebook, Amazon, the list goes on.' (Young man, accessing support from a Get Connected partner)

A further example was articulated by a staff member, explaining the way in which access to devices, data and support was a lifeline for those cut off by Covid-19:

'Chris is also in recovery, though, and normally recovery stuff is all face-to-face, but obviously, this hasn't been able to happen, and this has enabled him to 'not fall off the wagon' as he calls it. He's joining in NHS Group sessions and using CGL services. But he's also in another recovery connected group that he joins

once a month. I didn't find that for him. He's been researching himself and found it. He's good at doing that kind of thing. I'm seeing a difference in him in terms of his recovery, and he's more likely to acknowledge the hard bits now, to get in touch with someone and speak to them when it's hard.' (Staff member, Simon Community Scotland)

A final example is that one woman, in supported accommodation, at a point of crisis in a recovery journey, was able to make use of her device to access a support group in a different global time zone in the middle of the night when there was no available group in the UK to offer help. Each of these examples not only highlights an individual accessing services to which they are directed (the referral process often being a key part of the work of staff members) but also, autonomously, using the device, connectivity and digital understanding to exercise choice and autonomy in finding meaningful personal solutions to meet need.

Many of those supported by Simon Community Scotland have experienced and continue to experience complex trauma. Accessing services is often challenging due to previous negative experiences, lack of trust and relationships. Throughout the project, digital offered a way of bringing services directly to people, enabling people participating to access support in a way that worked for them. By aligning with the MAT Standards, for example, women were supported to use their devices to engage with agencies working with them, as well as access new services that could provide additional support for any challenges they were facing. For many participants, owning a digital device allowed them to communicate with services currently engaged in their care and utilise the digital skills and tools they had gained:

'It's the first time I set myself up an email address; I was getting emails from the women's project I was in, my keyworker.' (Woman accessing support from Simon Community Scotland)

A further finding was the participatory action research approach also impacted the women to give their time to the project. Initially, the project sought to explore digital inequality specifically, but of particular interest was the way in which, when the women felt a greater sense of understanding of the potential of the digital space, they were immediately keen to widen out their work and use that space not only to share their own stories, which they felt would positively impact on the lives of others facing similar challenges but also to advocate for their own rights and the rights of others.

‘By My Side has taught me there's other women out there with other issues, the same as me, and the same problems, and I find that comforting. Being able to have a platform to share my stories and to help other women, and hopefully it does.’ (Woman in supported accommodation with Simon Community Scotland)

Building on from the immediate work of the research group, the women engaged also created a range of online content, including podcasts hosted in the By My Side app detailed above, to share their stories and advocate for change. Staff also noted the way in which participation in the programme empowered the women in more practical ways, for instance, in asking for a change to their care in the supported accommodation.

Within the By My Side app, staff worked with partner organisations to bring a series of ‘virtual hellos’ to women using the digital tool. These ‘virtual hellos’ introduced women to organisations that can provide interventions, with staff working within these organisations providing an overview of what to expect when accessing their service, as well as what support would look like. The aim of this was to tackle the challenges women face accessing services and reduce anxiety throughout the process, recognising the relational bridge that exists between Simon Community Scotland and partner organisations and how staff can then encourage people to seek support that is right for them.

4.5.2 Money matters

As is noted in the literature review, there is a direct correlation between an individual being impacted by poverty and their ability and opportunity to engage in the digital space. (Goggin, 2017; Van Dijk, 2017b) This is further compounded by the impact of the introduction of digital systems to gatekeep access to benefits such as Universal Credit and housing benefits and even access to tenancies and housing. (Holmes and Burgess, 2022). Holmes and Burgess extensively consider the way in which an individual’s offline experience, and in particular their experience as a victim of poverty, is exacerbated by the impact of online digital systems. This was also reflected in the research, with one staff member commenting:

‘I get so annoyed when I see on the telly or whatever DWP saying go online, and I think you don’t even know. Digital poverty means you can’t even get on the internet. I can only get funding for £10-£15 phones... our organisation could help with a basic burner if someone is in need... but anything above or

with internet connection I can't. People aren't in the position to just buy these things. But they need them.' (Staff member, Simon Community Scotland)

At the outset of the research, frontline staff reflected on this impact and on the way in which it affected the individual. Staff time, both at the Hub and in frontline work, was often consumed by supporting people in navigating these systems, with the staff member often taking the lead. Many staff reflected that those needing to access the systems would never be able to do so without support: there was a sense of hopelessness that people were being trapped in a system whereby poverty was the reason *why* they needed to access the systems, and simultaneously that their experience as a victim of poverty was the very reason why they would not be able to access them. People were coming to the Hub once a week to a fixed desktop computer to engage in highly complex, highly intrusive digital systems to access their basic needs because they did not have the personal means to do so autonomously. Staff would also articulate the way in which people would feel confused and frustrated, unable to retain the knowledge from the previous week, as they had not been able to consolidate their skills nor explore their skills in a less public environment. Managing money online was, staff felt, very far from a realistic outcome when even accessing benefits was such a challenge. However, over the period of the research cycles, there were a significant number of changes in this regard, as the following examples given by staff highlight:

'But the financial thing has really been the biggest surprise for me. It's not something I expected at all. People have dropped from three food parcels a month to one, or none, just because they can see, in real time, their money, their balance, how much they have.' (Staff member, Simon Community Scotland)

'And I didn't think I would say this, but the DWP app is a breeze. It's so useful. It used to be sanction after sanction, with people getting behind because they had to get me to come to me, so I could help them online. But now, if the work coach contacts them, they just get a message on the app, and they can access their journal so easily. They can see their payments, when the money is coming in, and stay up to date with what they need to do.' (Staff member, Simon Community Scotland)

'One thing that C has always found hard is staying on top of his finances, and I wasn't sure how a phone would help - but it's made such a difference. I've helped him with his budget. He's set up a payment plan

for his rent arrears and is sorting this out online with Aberdeen City Council. It's just amazing.' (Staff member, Get Digital Partner organisation)

It is interesting to reflect here on the way in which the outcomes above were *different* to staff expectations. Prior to the implementation of Get Connected, staff experience was, as highlighted above, that using digital tools to manage finances was *rarely* positive and that individuals could not do so without help. It is, therefore, interesting to reflect on the way in which the reality that resulted was, in fact, *highly* positive when people were given devices, data, and person-centred support to develop digital understanding. This insight around the expectation of failure (based on experience in the field) was a helpful space to explore in terms of addressing unconscious bias. What was also interesting, again, was the individual's ability to exercise agency and control in changing their situation when given the opportunity to do so, expanding into areas beyond only managing money, instead improving a range of circumstances.

'He's done this, but he's also really sorted himself out financially through using the phone to help with budgets. He's got his online banking app, so knows how much money he's got exactly, and doesn't need the help of food parcels anymore. He's been shopping online - even organising a delivery from Iceland to stock up. And the furniture for his flat, he's got that online too.' (Staff member, Simon Community Scotland)

'He's using Utilita and has set up to pay his bills monthly, and he has to give meter readings every month on it too. He's good with money, really, and trying to work it all out himself, how to set up direct debits and that.' (Staff member, Simon Community Scotland)

As one staff member noted:

'I can see that with her having her tablet, in six months or whatever, she won't need me, won't need my help for things like Universal Credit, and that's a great thing, it really is.' (Staff member, Simon Community Scotland)

Addressing digital inequality enables a decrease in dependency and instead allows an individual to explore solutions for themselves, increasing agency and autonomy.

4.5.3 Leisure and Education

This category within the digital skills framework was created in response to a recognition not only of the potential of transferability of skills from one digital domain to another (Park and Park, 2017) but also that the collective ambition of the research was to explore *holistic* models of approach and to gather insights accordingly. It has historically often been the case that an individual's use of the digital domain for 'leisure' activities, such as gaming or watching online media, is considered of lesser value than engaging, say, with those activities which immediately evidence pathways into employment or engaging with online systems such as Universal Credit, and much funding was directed towards a push of people towards these systems, with examples including the 'Work IT Out' Programme 21, a 2015 contract financed by HMRC for delivery of a programme to support people access Child Tax Credit, Child Benefit, Working Tax Credit, Tax & National Insurance in local UK online centres.

The priority in the work at Simon Community Scotland was to ensure that there was no agenda, or drive, towards a particular outcome, but rather to explore what opportunities an individual might access themselves and how this might then transfer into improving their situation. There are several helpful examples that can be drawn from the data of the ways in which popular media was accessed by people and the way in which that also helped them in other areas. What was particularly interesting is that in each of the following examples, people (both staff and those using the devices) were immediately able to see the way in which a 'skill' impacted on a vital outcome.

'I can go on my Tiktok, play my games; it helps with my mental health.' (Woman in supported accommodation with Simon Community Scotland)

'He's taking music classes online with Crisis, and he's speaking to a counsellor on Zoom calls. This is a change - he wasn't doing it before. The tablet makes it easier for him to engage with services - he wasn't taking music classes or seeing a counsellor before.' (Staff member, Outreach Support, Simon Community Scotland)

'He's really into his music, and he downloads music and puts on his earphones and goes out walking. It's really good for his mental health, being out walking instead of, you know, lying in bed and sleeping when you're not well. He's even able to go into the shop with his headphones on, and he says it's stopping him worrying about what people are saying about him.' (Staff member, Outreach Support, Simon Community Scotland)

'B also keeps pigeons in the back garden and uses the tablet to find out things about pigeons and to talk to other people about that kind of thing. The tablet, the internet- it makes him feel like everyone else, part of society, I think.' (Staff member, Outreach Support, Simon Community Scotland)

'J told me he's joined this app, where he can meet people. He's taken up fishing over the last year and has now met a whole bunch of other people who are interested in fishing, and they share pictures, talk about waders, fish, allsorts. It's just such a change.' (Staff member, Outreach Support, Simon Community Scotland)

'S has also been using his phone to join an online community of people with an interest in abandoned buildings, and he's taken the most amazing photos around Aberdeen. Honestly, they're that good. I'd have one of them on my wall. He's also been joining in some social media group called something like 'I travelled this far to say I love you'. I don't really understand it properly, but it's a community of people who share images from landmarks all around the world to show how much they care about someone else. He really enjoys it and is always taking photos of Post-it notes in front of castles or whatever. It's amazing to see him feeling so much better about things.' (Staff member, Outreach Support, Simon Community Scotland)

There are two things to consider here: the first is the immediate transference of digital activity to a different outcome, reflecting the 'collateral outcomes' evidenced in literature (Van Deursen & Helsper, 2018). In the first example, TikTok offers an opportunity for distraction which was highly positive for many of the women in the harm reduction piece, as it offered respite from often damaging thoughts and feelings. In the second example, using the device to create music and join in classes opened a new space for support which had not previously been explored. In the third, the digital tool enabled the person to deal with everyday situations, which caused significant social anxiety. In the fourth, the person's digital engagement allowed him to widen his social connection, minimising the impact of social isolation so acute amongst people experiencing homelessness or

addiction (Christie, 2021). This is significant as research shows that ‘distinct types of support, from different support sources, are associated with higher levels of mental health.’ (Rea, 2023, p465)

A second point for consideration is the ability of both the people in receipt of devices and support and the staff alongside them to clearly express that correlation, even though the interviews did not guide them into doing so. The participatory approach that was taken empowered research participants to ‘tell their stories’ and, by imbuing them with the knowledge that they are experts in their own experience, sets this within a shared exploration of digital inequality. This has meant that they have immediately articulated the findings in a highly impactful way, drawing clear relationships between one activity and another. For anyone involved in research, this is undoubtedly a significant benefit.

The examples above also clearly speak to the way in which digital can positively impact on mental health and wellbeing, minimising the impact of social isolation (often amplified in situations of homelessness) and increasing an individual’s sense of self-worth and value.

Further insight on the theme of ‘leisure and education’ was evidenced in the use of the language app Duolingo, which gameifies language learning. This app was pre-installed on distributed devices in recognition of the number of device recipients who did not have English as a first language. This app was very popular and used extensively across the cohort, not only by speakers of languages other than English. Instead, what was demonstrated was that other people engaged with the app., ‘just for fun’, enjoying the process of language learning in and of itself. One person accessed Gaelic learning, as it was something they had always wanted to do but did not know where to begin.

Some of the device recipients were also in access courses at college, and to this extent, the devices offered a concrete pathway to education. What emerged, however, especially during the pandemic, was that while data and connectivity afforded an individual access to the college platforms, this did not mean that individuals then had the ability to engage with the online learning tools used, such as Moodle. Frontline staff, and people supported, expressed frustration at the complexity of these tools and the variability of use, as well as the fact that there appeared to be no clear pathway to support at the colleges to offer help with digital skills. What was also demonstrated was that many people with lower levels of digital skills would ordinarily have masked these challenges by engaging with networked peer support in physical buildings by, say, asking other students for help

navigating the systems. However, social distancing measures imposed during the pandemic removed this network of support, and individuals then struggled to maintain coursework without the capability or skills to use the particular online learning tools used by the educational institutions.

4.5.4 Finding Information

This evaluation element was particularly valuable during the Covid-19-related lockdown and in the context of harm reduction. These situations both required particular types of information, which allowed research to explore how best to support individuals in finding accurate, safe, and accessible information of immediate relevance. The development of By My Side was also helpful in this regard and will be explored in more detail below. It is also beneficial to explore the other ways people use the devices to access information. For example, YouTube came up repeatedly as an accessible resource to help people explore new things, and as a pathway to learning, even from the outset of the project, when I watched one person using the Hub to access an information video on the Universal Credit process while on a separate tab, engaging with the Universal Credit portal. A staff member gave a further example:

‘The phone is also helping him be a dad. He’s been using YouTube to learn how to cook and is now more than able to cook a meal for him and his son. It’s amazing.’ (Staff member, Outreach Support, Simon Community Scotland)

Common examples of the purposes people used devices to find information related to:

- Hobbies and interests
- Tenancies
- Mental health
- Recovery and harm reduction

The central challenge around finding information was the need to access safe and reliable information and explore with people receiving devices how they might assess the quality of information. To this end, during this project iteration, bookmarks were used (with these added to home screens) to increase the likelihood of access to safe and reliable information.

4.5.5 Health

The onset of Covid-19 evidenced the significant impact and risk of misinformation as UK citizens searched online for health information about the cause, spread and possible mitigation of Covid 19, which led to nationwide confusion around misinformation mixed with genuine health information. (Ferrara, Cresci and Luceri, 2020; Roozenbeek *et al.*, 2020). This was also evident in frontline work at the time: initially, staff struggled themselves with misinformation (which came to the fore in digital champion training sessions) which then meant it was even more difficult to support those moved into emergency accommodation. The participatory action research nature of the work meant, however, that there was an opportunity to effect immediate change by adding NHS Inform as a bookmark to all devices and exploring the platform live with frontline staff. This, as well as the Scottish Government's own information space, and latterly Test and Protect, all gave people a safe source of information without the complexity of Google or other search engines. People receiving devices clearly expressed that they did indeed turn to these 'safe' spaces because they appeared on the phone as an app and were, therefore, immediately visible.

People also searched for other health information and for information about mental health. Again, it is well documented that a significant number of people experiencing homelessness also struggle with their mental health. (Waugh, 2020) There is also evidence that frontline staff in these services also face high levels of mental health issues (Lemieux-Cumberlege and Taylor, 2019). Again, it was helpful to both those receiving devices and those in support roles to collectively explore the varying digital tools to support mental health and wellbeing and to discuss the ways in which different apps may be more or less useful or relevant. The research also evidenced, again, a new level of choice and agency whereby those in receipt of devices found their own solutions to the challenges they faced, which surprised many of the frontline staff.

'I do my therapeutic meditation on it, and I do my sleep insomnia because I've had insomnia ever since I came off meth the first time around. I can stay awake til 4 in the morning, and there's days that I don't sleep from seven o'clock at night right through. The tablet helps me do my meditation.' (Woman in supported accommodation, Simon Community Scotland)

'C is also in recovery, though, and normally recovery stuff is all face-to-face, but obviously, this hasn't been able to happen, and this has enabled him to 'not fall off the wagon' as he calls it. He's joining in NHS

Group sessions and using CGL services. But he's also in another recovery connected group that he joins once a month. I didn't find that for him; he's been researching himself and found it. He's good at doing that kind of thing.' (Staff member, Outreach Support, Simon Community Scotland)

'She just gets on with it. She's amazed me. She uses Google and YouTube. And the NHS. I downloaded the NHS app, and she uses that too. She has diabetes and complex health stuff, but she's used it to find out information about controlling her diet and healthy foods and things.' (Staff member, Outreach Support, Simon Community Scotland)

Similar to the position in relation to health information in general, and Covid-19 in particular, the Harm Reduction team reflected that there is a lot of misinformation and many myths around drug use and drug use practices and that recent evidence from the WAND initiative in Glasgow highlighted that many people lack basic harm reduction knowledge around safe injecting practices (Scottish Government, 2021b). Staff supported people in accessing extensive online resources (guides, websites, videos), which could then help people to be informed about harm reduction practices and which also included information about safer injecting practices, drug trends and information around drug harm. Much of this evidence-based information would also appear in a more user-friendly app, *By My Side*, illustrated below, which gave women easy access to life saving support with one click.

Figure 16- Illustration of the basic functions of the app designed by women for women

The app is an essential output of the wider work of participatory action research and an example of the way in which those women who were part of the group sharing their lived expertise were able to develop appropriate levels of critical media literacy to meaningfully support the development of the app itself. The women not only chose the style and presentation of the app but worked in groups to shape the content. They developed a tool which is now in use across Scotland to offer support to anyone impacted by drug use, from frontline staff to people using drugs and those who love them. The women chose the information they felt was of primary importance and, in particular, highlighted the need for the 'check on me' function, which would allow an individual to request immediate support with one click. The app has audio and video content, as well as offers signposting to key services in health and the third sector and to apps which might support an overall sense of wellbeing, for instance, research-informed apps to support mental health. The app represents the way that, if appropriately supported, work to address digital inequality can lead to tangible outcomes with positive impacts for people in the offline world and also shows how the women involved developed the agency to use their acquired digital capital to improve their social capital.

4.5.6 Online Safety and Risk

In the digital champion training sessions, there was a significant focus on the risk of online harm, as staff were afforded the space to explore what might go wrong and what risks might be more or less likely to impact on the people supported. There were many examples given here, drawn from the lived experience of staff: the negative impact of social media on mental health; the dark web for illegal buying and selling of drugs; catfishing; misinformation; scams; fraud; sexual abuse; abuse of geolocation by people selling drugs to those on recovery journeys; refugees and asylum seekers drawn into trafficking. Staff shared worrying stories of the multiple ways in which they had directly experienced the impact of online harm.

Simultaneously, staff conversely, cited many examples of ways in which digital tools were also being used by people experiencing homelessness to keep themselves *safer*. Examples include:

- People involved in transactional sex using WhatsApp to share the location and details of clients;
- Basic video tools are being used to record harassment and assault;
- Basic blocking features on social media apps and websites;
- Tools recommended by Women's Aid for women who were victims of domestic abuse.

These examples were not tools introduced by staff but rather solutions people had found for themselves to keep themselves safe. What is of interest, however, is that there were very few examples in the data gathered during the research period reflecting actual online harm experienced by those participating in the projects, and these were mostly limited to issues with passwords (an issue which is common in the public at large, rather than specific to this demographic). There could be several reasons for this: it could be that there was an unconscious bias in the work where interviews and group work did not create appropriate space for this issue to be meaningfully explored. It might also be that the desire for the project to be a 'positive' experience inadvertently dominated the narrative and that neither staff nor the people involved in the project wanted to highlight negative impacts. This latter suggestion seems unlikely, especially in the last cycle of work, which was fully immersed in a relational approach to digital inclusion, with staff who literally lived with women using drugs.

A further possibility is that the intervention of staff acting as digital champions, creating safe spaces to talk about online harms and risks, did, in fact, impact positively and that people felt empowered to control their digital environment with access to the necessary tools to do so. What might also be considered is that the risks to people in the real world were more dominant, and everyone was involved in addressing the physical manifestation of harm: making it safer for people to inject drugs, for instance, by directing people to helpful resources; getting people into supported accommodation rather than rough sleeping; fulfilling basic needs such as food and finance. This would be a helpful space to explore specifically in future research. There was some evidence, however, of devices going missing during the period of research, with a staff member commenting:

‘It has been a wee bit mixed, to be honest. We think a couple of the devices might have ended up in the pawn shop, but we worried this would happen. It just could be a cycle. Pawned when they needed to, and then got it back, and maybe pawn it again. But it’s hard. Just maybe not the right time.’ (Staff member, Simon Community Scotland)

‘We saw one woman lose her phone on the bus, which was devastating for herself and staff. She had lost the one thing keeping her connected that had helped her in such a short time.’ (Staff member, Supported Accommodation, Simon Community Scotland)

Staff across all three cohorts reflected concerns related to the loss, damage or selling on of devices. Such concerns would be relevant in any digital inclusion project with device and data distribution, and it would be helpful for future research to explore the loss/retention ratio. To a certain extent, this issue, more than any other, suggests an element of unconscious bias specifically related to digital, with some staff seeing digital, in this context, solely as a costly (and tradeable) material asset rather than as a tool by which can be used to unlock support, opportunity, and vital health information. What was of particular interest was that in the facilitated sessions, staff were also able to share positive experiences and, thus, to reflect collectively on preconceptions and their own role as ‘gatekeepers’.

As we moved through this work together, we gave more space to these conversations around risks versus reality, and in particular, the way in which staff expectations of positive or negative outcomes might impact on people accessing services or support. We also built into the work consideration of the way in which even a missing device was an opportunity for an open, trusting conversation rooted in empathy, and which might allow for a deeper relationship. This second example highlights a different way of reflecting on loss:

‘A few weeks back, his flat was broken into, and his phone was stolen, and he was so devastated and so scared that he wouldn’t be able to contact his son and that he would lose this link. We managed to sort out a new phone and sim card, and I feel really happy he’s keeping his connection.’ (Staff member, Outreach Support, Simon Community Scotland)

This ties into the ‘incremental’ approach evidenced in wider harm reduction approaches and by Marlatt et al., who refer to a philosophy of ‘compassionate pragmatism’ in harm reduction work, whereby meeting a person ‘where they are’ in terms of their personal needs and goals, and doing so without judgement but with compassion is an approach which can lead to lasting change. (Marlatt, Larimer and Witkiewitz, 2011)

4.5.7 Digital Literacy

In the facilitated session, staff noted that:

‘Some women are not digitally literate and may not view the option to get online as an exciting opportunity but rather a foreboding challenge. Particularly older women struggle with digital skills at our service.’ (Staff member, Supported Accommodation at Simon Community Scotland)

This challenge is familiar to anyone working in the field of digital inequality, that motivation itself presents as an obstacle, and that age is often (though not exclusively) a predictor of digital exclusion. (Beam, Hmielowski and Hutchens, 2018; French, Quinn and Yates, 2018) The most recent Lloyds Consumer Essential Digital Skills Report continues to highlight that accessibility remains a key predictor of unlocking the potential of the internet and particularly at the foundation level of the essential digital skills framework. (Lloyds Bank Third Edition-

Benchmarking the Essential Digital Skills of the UK, 2021). It should be unsurprising, therefore, that staff reflected that accessibility is a key issue for those who are offline and engaging with the project. Accessibility issues particularly related to literacy were highlighted, including dyslexia, illiteracy, and poor English language skills.

Awareness of this issue is vital to ensure that not only that devices are adapted to meet needs from the outset, with staff exploring and demonstrating different settings alongside the device recipients, but also that accessibility is a primary concern when exploring online resources pertinent to harm reduction. Practitioners in the field should consider this issue when creating resources to ensure that they are not replicating systemic and structural inequalities through the creation of inaccessible materials or creating resources that disempower the individual through exclusion. Referring again to wider literature, the digital confidence of staff and carers supporting accessibility is often a potential barrier (Chiner, Gómez-Puerta and Cardona-Moltó, 2017), and training therefore prioritised building key skills in this area through demonstration and practical application.

Chapter 5: Findings and Analysis

In the previous chapter, I framed the findings using ‘themes’ drawn from the evaluation framework used in *Get Digital Evaluation: Connection; Money matters; Leisure and Education; Finding Information, Health, Staying Safe and Legal Online and Digital Literacy*. In this analysis chapter, I will provide a detailed analysis of those overarching findings in conjunction with the literature by focussing on issues of empowerment, the relational aspect of Digital, Digital Capital and Digital Inequality, digital champions and harm reduction. This will then be followed by further insights on the broader themes coming from the research of the pressure of use or expectations, accessibility to sources of information, learning in partnership and the democratisation of the digital domains, reduction of stigma and the intersection of digital inequality, health inequality and harm reduction.

5.1 Empowerment

‘Through doing really simple things like including a woman we support in an email thread with her worker, we are promoting a sense of empowerment and collaboration, making sure that decisions are made with her and alongside her as opposed to without her input or consent.’ (Staff member, Supported Accommodation, Simon Community Scotland)

Staff in both cohorts discussed the ways in which access to online services and digital tools, in general, might contribute to the wider empowerment of people currently using drugs. For example, staff highlighted that such connectivity and skills mean that people might have a greater ‘ability to be more independent, make own phone calls, emails, appointments.’ And, furthermore that this would lead to ‘easier transitions to move-on due to independence and ability to stay connected to services’ (Staff cohort, Padlet). Staff also gave concrete examples of ways in which the digital domain has been utilised by some women to re-establish control of their situation, including access to support plans; claiming benefits; direct correspondence with key agencies, including courts, social work and housing.

5.1.1 Education

All cohorts of staff reflected on the way in which participation in the online space might be particularly helpful for the women receiving devices, giving them access to key resources and information, but only if the resources used

were contextualised for people who are currently using drugs and useful. The research included a facilitated session (using 'film reviews' as a technique) exploring resources, including the app Dose and websites Crew, Know Drugs and Talk 2 Frank. Many apps and websites discussed by staff were considered to have issues related to the context of application for people currently using drugs and living with issues related to addiction. One such example was Talk2Frank, for instance. While the language used was felt to be accessible and clear, it was nevertheless felt to be aimed at 'recreational' drug use. In contrast, the information on Know Drugs was considered useful and appropriate. Still, staff raised the issue of literacy and the overall accessibility of the site for those receiving support. However, one suggestion was a photo search which staff noted would be 'revolutionary' in terms of immediate benefit. Staff also noted that on-site clarity and transparency around the research and sources for the drug-related information were vital in ensuring confidence for practitioners.

Interestingly, Crew, an Edinburgh-based agency which has decades of field based experience in supporting people using drugs in a harm reduction context, was felt by staff to be the most valuable site: 'accessible; informative; a good resource for staff; useful for staff and service users; quick access to information; 'search tool' for nicknames' (Staff cohort, Padlet). That this site, in particular, was felt to be more useful may also be due to existing on-the-ground trusted relationships between different third sector organisations and those behind Crew.

While staff acknowledged the potential of these resources, they also offered vital insight into the context of people currently using drugs. In particular, the following issues were reflected in the sessions:

- The digital resources were variable in their application to the field (they were often too reflective of recreational drug use rather than reflective of the context of those living through addiction)
- Many digital resources expected high literacy levels and presented accessibility issues. There was very little video content, for example.
- Many of the digital resources did not give necessary, life-saving information (such as the administration of naloxone, safer injecting techniques or wound care)
- Many of the digital resources were explicitly aimed at professionals rather than for the people who most needed access to the information therein, leading to a 'gatekeeping' of knowledge. This was felt by all to be the stigmatisation of people currently using drugs to be incapable of accessing and applying information to their own situation.

These insights highlight how the digital space, for those not afforded access and privilege of use, fails to serve those who might immediately benefit and demonstrates the replication of *offline* inequality and marginalisation *online*. The insights also suggest the need to democratise online knowledge. This insight led to the creation of an app, by the women, for women currently using drugs to inform their drug use but also to support their overall wellbeing and connection, which will be explored later in the thesis.

5.1.2 Data Privacy and Security

Staff immediately flagged up the issue of privacy and security in accessing and using these apps, highlighting the potential risk, particularly for people currently using drugs: with Dose, for instance, staff noted that ‘Women could be scared to say what they're taking and for it to be recorded and who might see it (Staff Padlet, 2021).

This reflected earlier discussions with people in the project, who had highlighted their concerns about privacy and security in the digital space, particularly in those apps and websites that collect data. While the literature already reflects that concerns around privacy and security present a barrier for digital inclusion, in the context of people currently using drugs or experiencing homelessness, this concern is heightened because of the risk of ‘negative actors’ and the possible use of private information. Staff and women with lived experience cited examples of the way in which access to information around drug use might be used against them in access to their children, for instance. Others gave examples of how the state might use data against refugees and asylum seekers, location tracking, or social media surveillance. A further example still would be those who may be fleeing abuse and that such abuse might continue in the digital domain. What this means, therefore, and what this contributes to existing research is that there is a necessity for the contextualisation of digital inclusion work; trusted intermediaries must work closely in the context of holistic support to explore possible offline risks and then consider how much risk might play out online. By exploring this alongside the person most impacted, the transfer of critical digital understanding will be more meaningful as it is contextualised.

5.1.3 Agency, autonomy, dignity

An overwhelming theme of the research was the way in which the digital domain opened the space for individuals to exercise greater agency and autonomy in the challenging situations in which they found themselves. Staff and

those accessing the services consistently reflected the ways in which people who had been given support to develop the necessary digital skills and digital understanding were able to transfer those skills in a meaningful way to create tangible outcomes.

'J is quite young, he's sofa surfing just now, and that's why he's with us. He used to come to get on the computer, but now since he got the phone, he's doing everything himself, and I just think, 'No way, you don't need me anymore. You're doing it all.' He's bidding himself on houses on Key to Choice. He's sorted all that out himself and looking at flats, and I think he'll get something soon.' (Staff member, Get Digital Partner)

It was evidenced that devices in shared spaces were not particularly helpful in supporting people to access the internet independently, and there was a significant difference when the individual was afforded their own device with unlimited data, enabling them to experiment with the online space and consolidate skills. These findings align with Van Dijk, particularly the assertion that the quality of physical access remains a priority, as it enables an individual to consolidate digital skills and understanding and diversify the media they might engage with. (Van Dijk, 2017b) Furthermore, this example highlights the way in which individuals can be disempowered by digital systems, which, ironically, are intended to offer support, even though no consideration appears to have been given to those without digital skills or access to devices and connectivity. The 'digital by default agenda is a systems-first approach rather than an approach to ensure that individuals can fully participate in those systems that will impact them.

'But now, with this phone, she's been sorting stuff out totally on her own, without me. She's been speaking to the Council, doing all that. She's been accessing support through Gingerbread, who've been doing Zoom calls and support, and she's been in touch herself with Homestart and has a weekly call with her support worker. And with social work.' (Staff member, Outreach Support, Simon Community Scotland)

Staff and those using Simon Community Scotland's services would also articulate issues of privacy, dignity, and respect around digital use. The organisations support people in immensely difficult and deeply private situations, and staff were able to explain how digital tools enabled people to address their issues in an appropriate social setting. The following examples highlight this:

‘ So, S is in her 30s; she’s been using our service for a while. She had one of those £10 phones that she needed to top up, but usually, she couldn’t and had to come into the Hub all the time to use the internet. She doesn’t really like doing that - a lot of people are like that; when they have accommodation, they don’t like coming into the Hub. But she’d had to come in because she had a court case, a video call, about access with her son. It was a really big deal, and she came to the Hub, and we were setting it up for the morning session at the court, but it wasn’t working properly, and we couldn’t get on. The phone arrived at exactly the right time. I couldn’t believe it. We set it up in the Hub there, and then she was able to join the afternoon session at the Court from home. And speak to them there, where it’s more private, better for her.’ (Staff member at the Hub, Simon Community Scotland)

‘Beforehand, she didn’t like me logging into her universal credit because she’s a private person, which I totally understand. I’m like that. I mean, I wouldn’t like it if I went in somewhere and someone turned a laptop round and said, ‘put your password in there,’ especially about finances and things because that’s private. But now she can do it herself. She’s reset her universal credit login herself and can log into that now when she needs it. And she’s phoned the bank, she’s done it on her own, and reset her online banking. She doesn’t need me to do it, and that’s so much better for her.’ (Staff member, Outreach Support, Simon Community Scotland)

These examples sit the research within the space of that literature reflecting on the correlation between digital rights and human rights, such as the right to access information, the right to freedom of expression, the right to privacy, and the right to security. In 2014, Mathiesen reflected that human rights are increasingly enacted and enabled in the digital space or diminished or negated. (Mathiesen, 2014) Livingstone, too, calls for the application of the rights of the child to be enacted in the digital domain (Livingstone, 2014), and disability researchers also engage in similar discussions.(Goggin, Ellis and Hawkins, 2019)What is clear from the findings of this particular research project is that embedding digital rights in discussions of human rights is, therefore, a necessity.

Such discussions also sit alongside emerging literature exploring digital ethics, such as Taylor, who calls for the connection of connecting digital rights, freedoms and ethics, noting that ‘although data-driven discrimination is advancing at a similar pace to data processing technologies, awareness and mechanisms for combating it are not. ‘ (Taylor, 2017, p 1). The PAR approach taken here not only allows for the enactment of rights but also for an

exploration of digital ethics directly with those most impacted and also offers opportunities to develop both awareness and mechanisms for combatting such intrusions.

5.2 The relational aspect of digital inclusion and digital champions

Much has been written about the role of the trusted intermediary in digital inclusion work (P. et al., 2013; Haight, Quan-Haase and Corbett, 2014; Yu et al., 2016; Dodel and Mesch, 2018), and this research shows a clear contribution to existing literature supporting this approach. What makes this approach different, however, is the fact that digital champions in this context were working in a trauma-informed way within a harm reduction context. These are deeply trusting and empathetic environments, with staff highly skilled in creating safe spaces and in acknowledging challenging issues, including power dynamics.

‘I expected this project to work, to be good, and it has been. I’ve been a single mum myself, and I know how hard it is and how massive a thing it is to have a phone. I mean, I use it for everything. It’s a big thing to try and juggle everything, trying to do it all, and to try and do that without a phone or with no data... I don’t know. This has been good; I knew it would be good. With the folk I work with, I’m not there to deskill them. I want to help them get skills. I’m not there to hinder them, to take power away from them. I want to show them that they **can** do stuff. I know that in my job, the more you do, the less they know, and they can get tongue-tied. Think they can’t do things. Sometimes they’re scared, they’ve come from domineering partners or whatever, but I want them to be independent, to see it’s baby steps.’ (Staff member, Outreach Support, Simon Community Scotland)

This example highlights many of the threads running through this work which might be seen as a contribution to existing research: the individual staff member’s ability to relate another’s situation to their own, an expectation and aspiration of positive outcomes, a recognition of their power and the need for empowerment and the way in which an individual’s social context can inhibit actualisation. These are deeply insightful statements which reflect the intensity of the relational approach. Furthermore, *kindness and love* are clearly articulated values across the organisation, embedded in induction.

‘S is an older guy who’s been in jail for 23 years and isn’t clued up about technology. He hasn’t grown up with technology and feels it almost goes against the grain, and I had to really talk to him about even

taking the tablet because he wasn't sure at first. I think it was me showing him, visually, without all the jargon, me just sitting, showing him the potential of it, helping him see the positive, not the negatives, letting him see it and take it all in; that's what maybe made the difference and got him onto it.' (Staff member, Outreach Support, Simon Community Scotland)

'The biggest surprise for me has really been that all five devices are still there. I thought maybe they would be sold on, and I was worried, but I'm so pleased that hasn't happened. But I think people, when they get one, they must see, they must know, how good it is having it. It's amazing because they've had nothing, and then they have this. It's a lifeline.' (Staff member, Supported Accommodation, Simon Community Scotland)

Kindness, empathy, and love are increasingly present in practice, in frontline work, and articulated in academic literature and discussions of policy in Scotland in particular. In *Radical Help*, Cottam reflects extensively on what happens when people are given different tools to make a change in the context of human connection and considers the way in which *relationships* contribute to practical solutions and transitional change, upending power dynamics for the better and ultimately revolutionising the welfare state which has become distant from those it should serve. (Cottam, 2018). From the outset, it was intended that this research be conducted in practice and, more importantly, that it should focus on empowering people experiencing homelessness, or those currently using drugs, to effect radical change as part of the wider work to address digital inequality. While, as discussed above, trusted intermediaries are a known part of meaningful digital inclusion work, what is of particular interest in this approach is that PAR dissolved many of the existing power inequalities which often exist in the structure and delivery of support services (even though this may be unintentional). Furthermore, that PAR was, in this very particular context, rooted in harm reduction and trauma-informed practice has led to strengthened relationships, deep insights, and an evidence base reflecting the genuine impact of such an approach on the lives of others.

Harm reduction and trauma-informed practice both have abstract concepts underpinning their pragmatic approaches: specifically, kindness, empathy, and compassion. The practice of kindness and establishing everyday relationships are increasingly present in the rhetoric around Scottish policymaking and articulated in the Scottish Government's National Performance Framework. (Scottish Government | National Performance Framework,

2023) This research emphasises the positive change made possible by the application of kindness in praxis. As Ferguson et al. described, kindness has 'both ordinary and extraordinary characteristics, is both prosaic and potentially radical, is rooted in individual interactions and is deeply social.' (Ferguson & Carnegie United Kingdom Trust., 2019. p.11)

This research operated in a space which met Ferguson's three prerequisites of kindness. Firstly, by operating from spaces of supported accommodation, Simon Community Scotland was able to create physical space for people to connect, often across distance, and through the PAR approach, to become aware of the needs of others and thus to feel able to ask for, offer or accept help. Secondly, PAR also requires that attention be paid to all the relationships within the boundaries of the research and to the importance of all interactions, whether outcome focused or not. Perhaps most importantly, for me at least, was the observation of genuine kindness at all levels across the organisation, which enabled all involved 'to feel more able and willing to take the necessary affective or *relational* "leaps of faith"' (Ferguson & Carnegie United Kingdom Trust., 2019, p30).

Time and again, the relational aspect of digital inclusion was reflected in the data: the digital tools were not just a pathway to engage with systems but also a way of opening meaningful, human connections on deeply emotional levels. Relationship building has always been integral to the work of frontline staff, especially for those working in services supporting people experiencing homelessness. What was evident in this work was not only the opportunities to explore spaces where things were difficult but also to explore spaces of joy together.

'When we set up the phone and added on his Gmail, he couldn't believe all the old photos that came up, like a blast from the past, and we were talking and going through the old memories of past boyfriends and stuff and laughing about what ones he should get rid of. It was a big surprise that they were all there. I don't know how that's all still there.' (Staff member, Outreach Support, Simon Community Scotland)

Digital tools could also be used by both parties as practical solutions to communication challenges and, in turn, strengthening relationships and networks.

'R is really looking forward to his dad coming over and wants me to meet him - I think I'll need to be relying on using a translation app for this as I don't speak Polish, and his dad doesn't speak English.' (Staff member, Outreach Support, Simon Community Scotland)

It is also essential to recognise that it is particularly important that the relationships built in support work are reciprocal and interdependent. For example, staff would speak openly of their concerns for people they could not reach and the way in which they would often carry these worries with them outside work. Digital inclusion work, which gets or keeps a person connected through devices and data, could mean that staff themselves could feel more at ease or reassured about the safety of those people.

‘C is a young guy, he’s quiet, and he’s had a really hard time. I haven’t spoken to him as much recently because his dad has passed away, and he’s taken it really bad. His phone arrived at the right time, too; he’s another one. He used to get data from his dad, but when he died, he had nothing, no data, and so this was so useful. He’s just moved into his own tenancy, and they look lonely when they get into a new flat. And I worry. But with this, he has YouTube, films, and it’s good to know he can still talk to people, to me, when he wants to. It takes away my worry a bit. That lifeline.’ (Staff member, Outreach Support, Simon Community Scotland)

‘I’m seeing a difference in him in terms of his recovery, and he’s more likely to acknowledge the hard bits now, to get in touch with someone and speak to them when it’s hard.’ (Staff member, Outreach Support, Simon Community Scotland)

This reciprocal and interdependent relationship is particularly important in this field. People working in the space of homelessness are particularly impacted by the trauma they see as part of their role, which can also damage their own mental health and wellbeing. Lemieux et al. evidence the need for a psychologically informed workplace (Lemieux-Cumberlege and Taylor, 2019) and this research shows how digital connectivity and a relational approach can support such a workplace.

As noted above, these investigations not only add to the strength of existing literature related to the impact of the trusted intermediary in digital inclusion work but also develop that understanding. For instance, the writing of Mariën and Van Audenhove (2012) reflects that ‘every individual within a community, within society, has some kind of ICT-knowledge and just needs to be incited to share that knowledge within his own social networks, the community or society at large’ (Mariën and Van Audenhove (2012) p.4). While it is true that many individuals within a community or society may have some level of digital skills, it is also important to recognise that not

everyone may feel comfortable or confident in sharing their knowledge with others. Additionally, some individuals may not have access to the necessary technology or resources to effectively share their knowledge. This is particularly the case in organisations such as Simon Community Scotland, where those with lived expertise in social inequality are employed. Therefore, due to the impact of that inequality on their previous experiences and opportunities, staff may not have had appropriate or equitable opportunities to develop the digital skills and understanding for this role. Therefore, it is important to not only invite individuals to share their knowledge but also to provide them with the necessary support and resources to develop skills and for organisations to ensure that this is the subject of continuous reflection to ensure that people are kept up to date. This is in line with the findings of Wagg and Simenova, who highlight in their policy level perspective the various challenges with 'digital champion' approaches, including limited opportunity or application of knowledge-sharing, lack of access to devices and connectivity for frontline staff as well as a lack of funding to ensure that organisations have staff with the necessary skills and confidence to provide digital skills training and support within the context of holistic support. (Wagg and Simeonova, 2021)

Time as a finite resource available in holistic support was an ongoing theme in the exploration of digital champion support specifically. Those engaged in the provision of digital skills support often reflected that a substantial amount of time was spent engaging and supporting an individual to set up a new device, install applications and then familiarise themselves with basic online tools such as search engines. Throughout the second cycle of active research, different resources were developed to support digital champions and those receiving holistic support to simplify and support this process. These included set-up guides (Simon Community Scotland; Connecting Scotland), how-to videos with the precise models of devices being distributed (Simon Community Scotland; Connecting Scotland) and additional resources, including step-by-step guides to setting up Google accounts in both printable copy and video formats. These were shared before the implementation of digital support. Perhaps most significant was the third participatory action research cycle with Get Digital Scotland, where (as a result of findings from the previous cycles) there was a shift in focus in the evaluation framework from skills to outcomes, with an accompanying guide to clearly signposted resources and accompanying issues and challenges that might need to be considered.

The overall consideration of time is an essential consideration for field-based practice. The research showed, first, that there was an impact of time on staff members. The amount of time and length of time spent by staff

providing support to individuals varied significantly depending on the skills and confidence of that individual. Recent literature evidence that workplace digital literacy is a challenge across the U.K., with 21% of the Scottish workforce lacking the digital skills they need for work (UK Consumer Digital Index 2021 | Lloyds Bank, 2021). It might be considered that this figure is higher in organisations prioritising lived experience in their recruitment process, as that experience of systemic inequality will also have impacted directly on applicants. This means a consequential increased likelihood that those who are recruited have experience with relevant challenges related to the digital domain. This PAR approach included staff upskilling through buddying and direct training, and the implementation was, as noted above, supported with practical tools such as video guides, increasing accessibility and the opportunity for staff to explore the tasks at their own pace.

Second, the research showed clearly that time spent with the recipient of the device was often intensive, but the staff and those receiving devices noted that this time meant individuals felt more informed and more in control. It was also helpful in establishing relationships and in building a positive atmosphere around the introduction of digital support. What was beneficial in this work was that there was no external time pressure: Simon Community Scotland supports relational approaches, and therefore there is recognition within the service that individual needs vary, as does time required to meet those needs.

5.3 Digital Capital

5.3.1 Digital Capital and Digital Inequality

Bramley and Fitzpatrick, in their analysis of the structural causes of homelessness, note that ‘in the UK at least, homelessness is not randomly distributed across the population, but rather the odds of experiencing it are systematically structured around a set of identifiable individual, social and structural factors, most of which, it should be emphasized, are outside the control of those directly affected.’ (Bramley and Fitzpatrick, 2017 p.114) They identify a lack of social networks and experience of systemic poverty as predictive risk factors. The research contributes to the existing discussions reflected in the most recent literature on digital inequality and to those discussions related to Bourdieu’s consideration of digital capital (Park, 2017a; Carlson and Isaacs, 2018; Ragnedda, Ruiu and Addeo, 2019; Lindell, 2020). As digital technologies become ubiquitous, those with greater access to digital capital are likely to have significant advantages over those without. For example, individuals with a better bank of digital capital may be able to use digital technologies to access job opportunities, educational

resources, and social networks that are not available to those without. However, digital inequality can limit access to that digital capital, reinforcing and replicating existing social and economic inequalities. In the latter cycles of research, the issue of 'access inequality' was addressed, and participants received smart devices with unlimited connectivity as well as support to explore the different ways in which the internet might support them in addressing other inequalities. Helsper notes that 'for access to be a true indicator of inclusion in digital societies, it should be high quality as well as ubiquitous' (Helsper, 2021, p53). To this end, the data was unlimited, meaning that individuals did not have to 'choose' between different activities. One example here was that an individual on a recovery journey did not have to choose or prioritise different video calls (to family, to sponsors, to health professionals, or to support services): instead, access afforded him the agency to access all the support he required. Participants could also choose between tablets and mobile phones, empowering them to choose the type of device that would benefit them the most.

The research also highlighted a direct and immediate correlation between the absence of digital capital and economic opportunity, mirroring the findings of Yates et al., who note that those services used by individuals to access, accumulate and consolidate wealth are primarily online. (Yates, Kirby, and Lockley, 2015) Time and again, participants reflected on their challenges in accessing employment and benefits through 'gatekeeping' portals such as Universal Jobmatch and Universal Credit and their sense of being 'locked out'. Conversely, the research evidenced that when given the opportunity and support, individuals were ultimately able to engage autonomously with these systems and to fundamentally change their financial situation. One example of this was an individual who had been dependent on receipt of food parcels to live but was able to use the device to manage his finances in such a way that he was able then to eke out his limited income and become more in control of his situation.

Online banking is another digital system which is intended to automate and optimise aspects of economic life. With access and understanding, people can see and manage their income, budget within apps, and maintain economic stability: those with greater access to digital capital may be better positioned to take advantage of these opportunities, as they are more likely to have the skills and knowledge required to work with these technologies. This research showed that despite initially high levels of mistrust in online banking across the cohort, individuals who accessed online banking saw immediate positive benefit.

5.3.2 Digital Capital and Education

When considering the correlation between digital capital and education, it is helpful here to differentiate between informal and formal education and the way in which the research considers both. Many people experiencing homelessness have, often as victims of systemic poverty and systemic inequality, been excluded from 'mainstream' or formal education. (Somerville, 2013) Again, this contributes to Bourdieu's notion of 'habitus', which refers to how individuals internalise and embody the cultural and social norms and values of their social class. Those from privileged backgrounds are more likely to have engaged in formal education; those from households impacted by systemic poverty are less likely.

Over the last decade, and never more so than during the pandemic, the way the digital space impacts traditional or formal education has become increasingly obvious. As was noted in the findings from the research, online education systems and pathways can exclude people from education, replicating yet again the educational inequality that has long been evidenced (Van Deursen and Van Dijk, 2016). This research also showed that even the trusted intermediary, or digital champion, often found online education systems difficult to navigate and inaccessible. However, in contrast, throughout the research period, there were many examples of the ways in which people would use digital means to access informal education, from learning languages on Duolingo to accessing videos on safer injecting. Throughout the work, lived expertise was shared to highlight educational sources which were of most relevance to people in the context in which they were living.

5.3.3 Digital Capital/Inequality and the Erosion of Social Networks

By far, the most significant finding in the research was the way in which digital exclusion immediately impacts on an individual's ability to meaningfully connect with others, and in particular, the way in which lack of digital access contributes to the 'social network decay' of people experiencing homelessness (Golembiewski *et al.*, 2017).

Individuals in this situation often present with traumatic life situations and are often removed through choice or necessity from traditional social networks. Time and again, participants reflected on a myriad of ways by which digital afforded them the ability and opportunity to connect with family, friends, loved ones, and services. These social resources give an individual informal social capital which can have life-changing impacts.

Nevertheless, as also noted by Helsper, the research demonstrated a notable discrepancy in the social uses of information technology and the use of the tools most accessed by individuals. (Helsper, 2021) WhatsApp was

commonplace across the research group, but email was not. Staff worked hard to ensure that email was embedded across the learning, and in particular, they created email accounts which were then on the distributed devices. Access to email was not the key issue. These email accounts were used to correspond with external agencies, including social work, health professionals, and the justice system. However, it could be argued that email is a form of codified engagement from which people are often excluded due to a lack of resources to engage. It is interesting to reflect on the way in which this mode of inclusion impacted on the correspondents: some professionals were uncomfortable engaging in an email exchange where the person was copied in, for example, highlighting a power dynamic where those without access were entirely powerless even in issues related to their own care.

In summary, the research throughout reflects the more general findings that digital capital is an increasingly important form of capital in the digital age. It includes both the hardware and software components of digital technologies, as well as the human expertise required to use them effectively. However, digital inequality can limit access to digital capital, perpetuating existing social and economic inequalities for those experiencing homelessness. Those with greater access to digital capital are likely to have significant advantages over those without, both in economic and social life. As such, addressing digital inequality is essential for creating a more equitable and just society. The following image, taken from Simon Community Scotland's final report, encapsulates the way in which the 'Get Connected' approach, and in particular the way in which supported access through holistic care, can contribute to an accumulation of capital which meaningfully impact on a person's circumstances in the offline world.

Figure 17- Positive support leads to positive outcomes

Source: Simon Community Scotland, 2022

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5.4 Harm Reduction

Bayles notes that harm reduction as a model of treatment to address substance use behaviours was first implemented in a meaningful way in the early eighties to address the spread of HIV. Bayles further notes that harm reduction does not take an abstinence only approach but is instead 'designed to meet people "where they are at"' (Bayles, 2014 p.1). Hawk et al. further suggest that those operating in this space adhere to an identified set of principles, including 'humanism, pragmatism, individualism, autonomy, incrementalism, and accountability without termination' (Hawk et al., 2017 p39). As such, harm reduction does not have one clear model. For the purpose of practice, the research team drew on the Harm Reduction International definition:

'Harm reduction refers to policies, programmes and practices that aim to minimise negative health, social and legal impacts associated with drug use, drug policies and drug laws. Harm reduction is grounded in justice and human rights. It focuses on positive change and on working with people without judgement, coercion, discrimination, or requiring that they stop using drugs as a precondition of support.' (Harm Reduction International).

One of the primary findings of the fully immersive PAR approach was the clear evidence that work to address digital inequality could significantly contribute to positive outcomes for people who are using drugs, even though there may be challenges in implementing such a programme. Women time and again, shared the myriad of ways in which unrestricted digital access as part of holistic support impacted not only on their recovery specifically (if they had chosen this path) but also overall in terms of their wider social inclusion. The digital approach to harm reduction evidenced the ways in which digital access might literally save lives:

'If my head's going one hundred miles an hour and I want to use I can just go through the tablet and look at 24-hour suicide things or phone anybody I've got from CA or workers. So, aye, it's definitely helped me.'

'It means a lot to us because I've been in recovery now; I've got more access to connecting online to things that help me in my recovery. The staff looked up CA meetings locally, and that's how basically when I'm on the tablet now, I can look up CA.'

‘[The best thing about having a device is] being able to talk to my worker every day and get outside support, which I really need.’

5.4.1 The Intersection of harm reduction and digital inclusion.

Within a Scottish context, harm reduction with regard to people currently using drugs is a challenging area. While there is a political commitment to reducing harm, legislation and, in particular, criminalisation can have an adverse effect on the delivery and support of clear harm reduction approaches. In practical terms, one might consider harm reduction specifically in terms of health management. A Scottish example of this has been in the management of an outbreak of botulism amongst people who inject drugs which found that a pragmatic approach to harm reduction, including targeted and accessible information to help those injecting drugs to do so safely in the context of the outbreak, had a positive impact in terms of managing infection rates. (Trayner et al., 2018). However, it encompasses much more than this. It is a holistic approach which can sit alongside other models of person-centred support and which encompasses several fields. The following table aligns the guiding principles of harm reduction referenced above (Hawk et al., 2017), which are commonly used and familiar to practitioners in this field, alongside the ‘principles’ of an approach to supporting digital inclusion.

Table 4 - Alignment of principles of harm reduction and the overlap with digital inclusion, based on Hawk et al. 2017

Principle	Definition (Hawk et al., 2017)	Definition (from a digital inclusion perspective)	Approaches (Hawk et al., 2017)	Digital inclusion approach (mine)
Humanism	<p>Providers value, care for, respect, and dignify patients as individuals.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> It is important to recognize that people do things for a reason; harmful health behaviours provide some benefit to the individual, and those benefits must be assessed and acknowledged to understand the balance between harms and benefits. Understanding why patients make decisions is empowering for providers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Digital champions value, care for, respect and dignify every ‘learner’ as an individual It is important to recognize that people are often offline for a reason- they may be negatively impacted by wider digital systems (such as online benefits systems) Understanding the unique barriers and challenges for individuals using services can make for a better and more informed service for all. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Moral judgments made against patients do not produce positive health outcomes. Grudges are not held against patients. Services are user-friendly and responsive to patients’ needs. Providers accept patients’ choices. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‘Forcing’ people online through a systems first approach does not engage people. Services are user-friendly, welcoming, and responsive to the needs of individuals using those services, rather than engaging a ‘one size fits all approach Providers accept and value different choices with regard to internet use, meaning that engaging with systems (such as UC) is not given priority.
Pragmatism	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> None of us will ever achieve perfect health behaviours. Health behaviours and the ability to change them are 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> None of us will ever be able to engage with every aspect of the internet, and few of us will be ‘digital experts. Online behaviours and the ability to change them are influenced by 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Abstinence is neither prioritized nor assumed to be the goal of the patient. A range of supportive approaches 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Being ‘fully’ online, and in particular engaging with government/healthcare systems, is neither prioritized nor assumed

	influenced by social and community norms; behaviours do not occur within a vacuum.	social and community norms; behaviours do not occur within a vacuum.	is provided. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Care messages should be about actual harm to patients as opposed to moral or societal standards. 	to be the goal of the learner. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A range of supportive approaches is provided, encompassing different learning styles and understanding different barriers. • Messages around online risk should be about actual risks for individuals as opposed to moral or societal standards. • It is valuable for digital champions to understand that the internet can present experiences of moral ambiguity since they are essentially supporting in an online space where individuals might encounter risks that may impact negatively.
Individualism	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Every person presents with his/her own needs and strengths. • People present with spectrums of harm and receptivity and therefore require a spectrum of intervention options. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Every person presents with his/her own needs and strengths. • People present with spectrums of knowledge, barriers and receptivity and therefore require a spectrum of support and learning options. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengths and needs are assessed for each patient, and no assumptions are made based on harmful health behaviours. • There is no universal application of protocol or messaging for patients. Instead, providers tailor messages and interventions for each patient and maximize treatment options for each patient served. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learning is person centred, and needs and skills are assessed by the learner, for themselves, in dialogue with the digital champion. No assumptions are made about destinations for the learning path. • There is no universal application of a learning plan or learning outcomes for people. Instead, digital champions tailor messages and interventions for each individual and maximize and explore opportunities for every person.
Autonomy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Though providers offer suggestions and education regarding patients' medications and treatment options, individuals ultimately make their own choices about medications, treatment, and health behaviours to the best of their abilities, beliefs, and priorities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Though digital champions might offer suggestions and education around internet use, digital skills, and risk to the best of their abilities, individuals ultimately make their own choices according to their abilities, beliefs, and priorities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provider-patient partnerships are important, and these are exemplified by patient-driven care, shared decision-making, and reciprocal learning. • Care negotiations are based on the current state of the patient 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive partnerships between individuals and digital champions are important, and these are exemplified by a focus on lived experience, shared decision-making, and reciprocal learning. • Learning is based on the individual's desire at any particular point in time.
Incrementalism	<p>Any positive change is a step toward improved health, and positive change can take years.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It is important to understand and plan for backward movements. 	<p>Any positive change is a step toward improved digital literacy, and positive change can take years.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It is important to understand and plan for backward movements often related to changes in circumstances. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Providers can help patients celebrate any positive movement. • It is important to recognize that, at times, all people experience plateaus or negative trajectories. • Providing positive reinforcement is valuable 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Providers can help people celebrate any positive development of digital skills. • It is important to recognize that, at times, all people experience plateaus or particular challenges in their learning and acquisition of digital skills. • Providing positive

				reinforcement is valuable
Accountability without termination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patients are responsible for their choices and health behaviours. • Patients are not 'fired' for not achieving goals. • Individuals have the right to make harmful health decisions, and providers can still help them to understand that the consequences are their own. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individuals are responsible for their choices and behaviours online. • Accessing wider support is not dependent on an individual's digital journey, and there is no expectation around achieving particular outcomes • Individuals have the right to make mistakes online in ways that might negatively impact on their emotional/financial/social well-being, and digital champions can still help them to understand that the consequences are their own and provide meaningful pathways of support. 	While helping patients to understand the impact of their choices and behaviours is valuable, backward movement is not penalized.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • While helping people to understand the impact of their choices and behaviours online, valuable, backward movement or negative online interaction is a potential opportunity to widen digital understanding and to for lived experience to inform support and identify gaps.

In a paper reflecting on the impact of harm reduction work in the context of Covid 19, Csák et al. highlighted that 'strong pre-existing relationships with clients meant that' (frontline staff working to a harm reduction model) 'were able to reach sometimes marginalised groups with COVID-19 prevention and care where other services were failing to connect'. (Csák et al., 2021 p.3). Again, this has been evidenced in this thesis. What is useful to those practitioners is that digital inclusion work is articulated clearly as part of their everyday approach, as in the example above.

5.4.2 Digital Inclusion and MAT Standards

It is also possible to align digital inclusion activity with the medically assisted treatment (MAT) standards. The following model is one developed for the project to ensure that frontline staff could directly apply their work on digital inclusion to the requirements of practice. Such an approach is vital as it embeds digital inclusion work in support in a way that is immediately meaningful.

Table 5- Alignment of MAT standards with digital inclusion activity

<p>Implementing the MAT Standards through digital inclusion</p> <p>Standard: All people accessing services have the option to start MAT from the same day of presentation.</p> <p>People accessing services should be supported with a device and unlimited data, which both directly and indirectly supports the commencement of medically assisted treatment.</p> <p>This could include pathways such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NearMe video call for consultation with medical professionals from a range of locations • Supported access to online prescription services, which allows for greater autonomy and control. • Digital calendar for appointments • Email for confirmation of treatment (putting people at the heart of care)
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Standard: All people are supported to make an informed choice on what medication to use for MAT and the appropriate dose.

Accessible online resources can enable people to explore MAT in safe spaces with trusted individuals, allowing for informed decision-making and exploring both possibilities and potential risks.

Digital communication with practitioners can also offer a record of discussions which can then be revisited. Furthermore, accessible online resources can be revisited at appropriate opportunities and times, informing future decisions and exploring alternative pathways.

Apps such as Dose might be used in practice to help individuals keep track of medication and better understand poly-drug use.

Standard: All people at high risk of drug-related harm are proactively identified and offered support to commence or continue MAT, and people are offered evidence-based harm reduction at the point of MAT delivery.

The internet offers an opportunity to explore up-to-date, evidence-based harm reduction options at point of MAT delivery alongside the person accessing that support.

Standard: All people will receive support to remain in treatment for as long as requested.

Access to devices and connectivity allows us to maintain relationships with people even though they may be unable to present physically.

One example from this research is that the device enabled frontline staff to stay connected to an individual detained under the Mental Health Act, allowing for the continuation of trusted relationships.

Standard: The system that provides MAT is psychologically informed (tier 1), routinely delivers evidence-based low intensity psychosocial interventions (tier 2), and supports individuals to grow social networks.

All our research in this space evidences the various ways in which the internet and digital tools can be used to support low-intensity psychosocial intervention and can be used to support people to both grow and maintain social networks.

Examples from practice include:

Promoting and linking people to online services that place emphasis on support from mutual aid and other recovery networks, allowing people increased choice and opportunity to engage at the right time, from the right place. Using digital tools and apps to develop and maintain a network of support available to the person, including with key people in their life, such as family and friends. Digital tools also allow staff to have a collaborative, transparent process in place to document the experiences of people who engage with services that can be revisited by that person whenever they might choose. Digital tools also allow staff to evidence through shared care planning that the person's views have been sought, documented, and acted on (copied correspondence, for instance).

Standard: All people have the option of MAT shared with Primary Care.

Digital offers an accessible and straightforward way of communicating and sharing information with primary care practitioners whilst simultaneously putting the person at the centre of all communications.

Standard: All people have access to independent advocacy and support for housing, welfare, and income needs.

Evidence from Get Connected and Simon Community Scotland's Digital Approach to Harm Reduction clearly demonstrates that access to devices, connectivity and person centred support to develop digital understanding allows people to access a range of services. These include advocacy; housing; benefits systems such as Universal Credit; online banking and budgeting; education; employment; health, and wellbeing. Conversely, lack of access completely disempowers individuals, requiring 'assisted digital' where staff access these services on behalf of that person, creating further barriers and replicating existing hierarchies of power.

Standard: All people with co-occurring drug use and mental health difficulties can receive mental health care at the point of MAT delivery.

Access to the internet allows for several positive digital interventions to support positive mental health, which can complement face-to-face services, and allows individuals and practitioners to explore a range of person-centred tools to meet a spectrum of conditions. NHS Inform has a range of self-help guides and signposts into other research-informed apps and websites which can support positive mental health and well-being.

Examples of these include Living Life to the Full (CBT); Breathing Space; Calm Harm; Overcoming, Breathe, Meditation, and Journaling tools.

As highlighted above, access to the internet can also support people in accessing wider psycho-social support, which will also contribute to positive mental health. The research has also evidenced the way in which the internet might be used to access opportunities to support physical health and well-being (for example, exercise sessions on YouTube).

Standard: All people receive trauma informed care.

Supplementing the application of the MAT Standards with digital inclusion also offers a greater opportunity for widening out a person-centred approach to working with people who have experienced trauma, underpinning the following principles of trauma-informed practice:

Safety: access to the internet and digital tools can allow people to feel safer and more in control of their environment. This might be through creating social groups to share locations, accessing digital services, or using specific digital safety tools (such as Hollieguard).

An example from practice is the 'Check on Me' function in the By My Side App, which allows individuals to digitally request a well-being check.

Trustworthiness: the research has shown the way in which a digital approach to harm reduction can support the development of trusted relationships, offering new ways to open conversations and discussions. It also affords the opportunity to explore 'digital' trustworthiness, such as the creation of a transparent system of data recording where practitioners check the accuracy of the information directly with the people experiencing trauma prior to any documentation in formal records and where everyone is included in correspondence, facilitating greater transparency.

Choice: as detailed above, digital tools and access to the internet clearly increase a person's choices in all aspects of their lives, supplementing those services that are available face-to-face or within working hours. Digital access enables people to make more informed choices and allows for greater flexibility (for instance, video-calling rather than in-person consultations can mean that an individual can be more in control of their own environment). Our multi-agency engagement across this research project has maximised choice for people, expanding the options available and facilitating the ability of our own and other services to respond to a wide range of needs.

Collaboration Shared use of digital tools can contribute to addressing power differentials between different staff groups and between staff and the people experiencing trauma. Digital tools such as WhatsApp, Google Meet, Teams and Zoom have all been used in this project for both formal and informal use of peer support and mutual self-help.

Empowerment: the research in this space evidences the way in which digital tools and digital services can empower individuals to take control of their lives in the way that they might choose to do so using digital tools.

One staff member reflected that being part of a digital approach to harm reduction had highlighted that they had inadvertently been acting as gatekeepers to information and resources by failing to recognise the way in which digital might be used as a tool in a wider harm reduction approach.

These examples evidence both the need and relative ease of transferring work to address digital inequality to standards, policies, and practices of the workplace and, in so doing, enable staff to relate digital inclusion activity to key priorities. This insight extends the considerations of existing research reflecting on models of support (van Deursen, Courtois and van Dijk, 2014; Rains and Tsetsi, 2017; French, Quinn and Yates, 2018) by pinning down concrete examples of digital actions which can be applied as part of holistic care, and which are already identified as a key priority. Such examples might also be used to develop digital inclusion work where other standards of care are set, such as those outlined by SSSC or by The Promise in Scotland, both of which articulate the needs and priorities of communities of people impacted by inequality and the accordant policy and practice frameworks.

5.4.3 Who is a service really serving?

At the most fundamental level, this research evidenced the direct relationship, and, indeed, causality, between homelessness and digital inequality due to the impact of a systems-first approach on the individual. 'The process of applying for a housing association property, known as bidding, is often primarily done online. Therefore, given that living in certain forms of temporary accommodation makes it very difficult to get online, this creates a significant obstacle to bidding on a more suitable property, and thus it remains very difficult to get online. (Holmes and Burgess, 2022) The highly complex nature of homelessness means that an individual in this situation will have to engage with a myriad of digital systems that act as blockers to meeting essential needs, including Universal

Credit, again a digital only system by which people access benefits needed for food and shelter. As noted by Millar and Bennett:

‘Universal Credit fails to connect with the realities of life, particularly life on a low income, not least because it intended to change that reality’. (Millar and Bennett, 2017, p. 178)

At the beginning of our work together, a staff member raised the workplace application of Maslow’s Hierarchy of Needs, a guiding psychological/philosophical model used by many staff engaged in work on social inequality, and based on the premise that much human behaviour is goal directed. At the most basic level are needs relating to the survival instinct (need for food, shelter, clothing, etc.); then comes the need for safety and security, followed by social needs such as family and other social support systems, and then, when a significant percentage of these needs are met, an individual might then aspire to meet what Maslow and others describe as self-actualization needs, or, in other words, achieving full potential as a person and thus satisfying self-esteem. The staff member, understandably, highlighted the fact that digital, as she and many of those she supported understood it, did not meet the most basic physiological and safety needs and might only reasonably be included as part of ‘self-actualization’, at the peak of the pyramid, which only those individuals having significant elements of the baser layers met, might reach. Engagement with the internet, she argued, might be considered irrelevant to someone without somewhere safe to stay. In the days before digital, this logic would undoubtedly hold fast as finding accommodation and support was a facilitated process based on human-facing communications. Digital, however, is a wildcard here, a new domain and, one might argue, a new key to unlock each of these layers. It does not sit as an aside nor as an aspiration at the top of the pyramid alongside self-actualization, but rather is a dome arching over Maslow’s pyramid.

Figure 18- Maslow’s Hierarchy of Needs with an Overlay of Essential Digital Skills

The digital by default agenda means that, without essential digital skills, an individual is 'locked out' of meeting their basic needs. Digital is the means by which the individual now 'unlocks' food, shelter, health information, personal safety, employment- and indeed, maintaining social contacts and developing our sense of connection. We claim benefits online, apply for housing and employment opportunities, pay bills, and order prescriptions. Just fifteen years ago, no such digital systems existed. While Maslow's model has its critics, mostly objecting to the lack of empirical data informing this model, it nevertheless offers a helpful insight into individual motivation and engagement. People do indeed have essential basic needs, and the most vulnerable people in society, for instance, those people experiencing homelessness, are clearly not having those needs met. It is, therefore, unsurprising that it is incredibly challenging to engage people with digital, an activity which may be perceived by many to be 'aspirational' or an element unrelated to meeting urgent and desperate need. But internet access and the use of essential digital skills now form the starting point for meeting basic needs, either through assisted digital (with a support worker, carer or friend engaging with online systems) or by the individual themselves engaging.

Many of those supported by Simon Community Scotland have experienced and continue to experience complex trauma. Accessing services is often challenging due to previous negative experiences, lack of trust and limited relationships. Throughout the project, digital offered a way of bringing services directly to people, enabling people participating to access support in a way that worked for them. By aligning with the MAT Standards, for example, women were supported to use their devices to engage with agencies working with them, as well as access new services that could provide additional support for any challenges they were facing. For many participants, owning a digital device allowed them to communicate with services currently engaged in their care and utilise the digital skills and tools they had gained: 'It's the first time I set myself up an email address. I was getting emails from the women's project I was in, my keyworker.'

Within the By My Side app, staff worked with partner organisations to bring a series of 'virtual hellos' to women using the digital tool. These 'virtual hellos' introduced women to organisations that can provide interventions, with staff working within these organisations providing an overview of what to expect when accessing their service, as well as what support will look like. The aim of this was to tackle the challenges women face accessing services and reduce anxiety throughout the process, recognising the relational bridge that exists between Simon Community Scotland and partner organisations and how staff can then encourage people to seek support that is right for them.

The research also evidenced that for some people, their devices allowed them to find creative ways of managing their own health needs, as opposed to accessing services to provide support. Women supported by these projects often face struggles with their mental health, and digital tools provide a way for women independently use their devices to manage this:

‘I do my therapeutic meditation on it, and I do my sleep insomnia because I’ve had insomnia ever since I came off meth the first time round. I can stay awake til 4 in the morning, and there’s days that I don’t sleep from seven o’clock at night right through. The tablet helps me do my meditation.’ (Woman in supported accommodation at Simon Community Scotland)

This is the ideal of ‘patient activation’ extensively promoted in work across the NHS. (Hibbard and Gilbert, 2014)

Such examples reflect, in particular, the urgent need for services to meaningfully consider how they might draw on best practice in digital inclusion not only by developing services truly informed by lived expertise (rather than a systems first approach) but also how a networked approach to digital inclusion and public-third sector partnership can positively impact on those with unequal opportunity.

5.4.4 Keeping people alive

This final theme is one which is difficult to evidence but was nevertheless articulated consistently in the research and which is integral both in the Scottish context, which has the highest number of drug related deaths in Europe, and more widely in harm reduction work. Evidencing what has *not* happened is an impossibility, but what became obvious was the way in which the digital domain increased opportunities for relationships and social connection, more informed use, immediate access to emergency support (especially through the ‘Check on Me’ function requested by the women in the By My Side app. Since introducing policies of Harm Reduction and High Tolerance, Simon Community Scotland has seen a decrease in the number of deaths in supported accommodation. We collectively believe that by embedding digital inclusion as part of this picture, we are creating helpful contexts for lasting change.

5.5 The ‘Pressure of Use.’

Staff highlighted that participation in the digital space might also create additional pressures for people currently receiving support, including the pressure of participants meeting higher expectations of behaviour implicit from digital participation or bias resulting from non-participant’s lower expectations in relation to participants’ ability to

participate. This was because digital participation may create a false and unrealistic expectation about a user's ability, day after day, to maintain the same levels of digital participation. Users might sign up for services but not return or be online uninterrupted or for some time. Staff reflected on issues related to the often complexity of context for people currently using drugs, in that circumstances could vary incredibly from one day to the next. One example given by a staff cohort reflected that:

'Brilliant to make their own appointments - but hard for the women maybe to keep track of them and this can lead to confusion with practitioners'. (Staff cohort, Padlet).

Similarly, a second cohort noted that there is a risk of 'forgetting appointments due to not putting them in the diary' and that this presents an additional 'risk' by contributing, for instance, to a wider prejudice viewing people using drugs as incapable of managing their lives.

In the context of the principles of harm reduction, incremental change is vital: the use of an online calendar, for instance, might be considered a step forward. There should be no expectation of perfect use, and practitioners engaging with people currently using drugs and who may also engage with those people through digital means may also need to take this into consideration.

It is helpful to set the findings of this research into the context of harm reduction specifically, and to this end, staff were asked to consider in what ways participation in the online space might specifically contribute to existing models of harm reduction practice highlighted in academic research. This approach is also useful in both helping staff address and explore their own unconscious bias related to the 'gifting' of a digital device to someone currently using drugs and offers a pathway into exploring the relationships between digital inequality and wider inequalities. In other words, digital inclusion work was made explicitly and meaningfully part of the 'day job' through the alignment with current ways of working.

5.6 Learning in partnership: the democratisation of the digital domain?

A particularly interesting theme that emerged throughout the research, due to the combination of participatory approaches and digital inclusion as part of holistic care within a genuinely reflective space, was the apparent democratisation of the digital domain. This occurs when individuals become interchangeable as learners and

leaders. This is an obvious aspiration of any PAR approach, but there were many examples throughout the research cycles where those accessing the services offered their own expertise in new digital domains, finding new solutions to challenges without direction or support and teaching those who had, in the first instance, taught them. Although staff would provide the initial tools and influence the first steps that a person might take, once that individual had developed confidence in that space and was then able to apply that knowledge with the necessary practical tools, they were able to immediately transfer that knowledge to other spaces. This subtle but important shifting of power was particularly evident during lockdowns, where staff had no choice but to engage with a myriad of new tools and often felt uncomfortable doing so. In digital champion sessions, staff were encouraged to share those feelings of anxiety and nervousness with those receiving devices, which led several device recipients to articulate how this honesty allowed them to feel more confident: the 'assumed expert' status had been challenged.

This theme might be considered in relation to some of the discussions posited by Carmi et al. who collectively call for an exploration of qualitative methods to explore the ways in which we might co-design spaces for the exploration of proactive digital citizens (Carmi *et al.*, 2020). Throughout the work, the individual's social context was of primary importance, with significant emphasis placed on relationship building rather than simply 'support work'. The research also evidenced multiple ways in which activities undertaken, networks developed, and knowledge gained in the online world would immediately impact offline, primarily (in this research) to the benefit of that individual.

These insights also justify the participatory action research approach and the initial alignment with Friere, who emphasized the importance of dialogue and collaboration in the learning process and argued that these are essential for promoting social change (Freire and Ramos, 2017). Working together in the participatory research project, we all had different experiences and changed in different ways, impacted by the knowledge and learning of others involved in the project. This research promoted both dialogue and collaboration and facilitated the sharing of knowledge and resources. It was interesting to witness the emergence of critical consciousness across the group, encouraging each of us to question the varying powers at play and how digital inequalities are perpetuated and reinforced. The research also contributes to reflections in the playfully entitled *Pedagogy of the Oppressed 2:0* (Frag, Greeley and Swindell, 2021), the authors of which call for a modernisation of Friere's definition of literacy to include critical media literacy.

The various frameworks reflected in the literature review often consider a definition of digital literacy which aligns primarily with traditional literary skills. In other words, these describe frameworks of identifiable tasks. Such frameworks fail to reflect the ways in which Helsper's exploration of critical media literacy (Helsper, 2021) might play out in terms of an individual's engagement with both digital systems and the wider digital society at large. This research developed a model by which one might reflect on both concrete outcomes for individuals and explore the impact of digital systems on people whilst also considering levels of critical digital literacy. Polizzi notes that both functional and critical digital literacies 'are essential for engaging with and evaluating online content in addition to reflections on the nature and origin of information, contextual knowledge, and the practice of using multiple sources. The way functional digital literacy intersects with critical digital literacy is indicative of how digital specialists deploy skills and knowledge. This can vary depending on their professions, ranging from the practical ability to use digital technologies to knowledge about what the internet affords and its implications for society.' (Polizzi, 2020, p26)

5.7 Reducing stigma

'It felt uncomfortable that the women were grateful for receiving the devices when I see access to digital as something everyone should have.' (Staff member, Supported accommodation at Simon Community Scotland)

One staff cohort noted that 'Having a mobile can just make (people) feel included'. The ubiquity of mobile phone use means that the lack of a device is a physical/visual signifier, leaving one unable to access everyday services and opportunities, communicate freely, and participate in cultural and educational activities. This was articulated repeatedly, not only in the harm reduction cycle but across the research cycles and contributed to wider discussions on inequality. It also sets the person apart from the rest of society, further emphasising their outsider status in social norms. This stigmatisation is also an important contribution to the discussion on digital capital and the way in which the domain of an individual's experience impacts on use, access and opportunity.

5.8 The Intersection of digital inequality, health inequality and harm reduction

Being engaged in treatment is a protective factor for people who use drugs. Yet, in Scotland, only 35-40% of people who are using drugs are engaging in treatment (Scottish Government, 2021). Many support services and health-based services, including the NHS and treatment services, are now offering (in some cases exclusively) online service delivery. Video calls with doctors, health professionals, and support workers are now commonplace, clearly demonstrating the way in which those who are facing digital exclusion can also face health exclusion.

This research evidenced that, with appropriate support, people currently using drugs can be supported to access better healthcare to meet their needs. The research here evidences that this approach enables people to access information about different treatments that are available to them, as well as the range of services available locally and online resources such as support groups, recovery community groups, mutual aid groups, online forums, and clear advice and information to enable informed decision making about drug use.

The research also evidenced that for some people, their devices allowed them to find creative ways of managing their own health needs, as opposed to accessing services to provide support. Women supported by Simon Community Scotland often face struggles with their mental health, and digital tools provide a way for women independently use their devices to manage this:

‘I do my therapeutic meditation on it, and I do my sleep insomnia because I’ve had insomnia ever since I came off meth the first time round. I can stay awake til 4 in the morning, and there’s days that I don’t sleep from seven o’clock at night right through. The tablet helps me do my meditation.’ (Woman in supported accommodation at Simon Community Scotland)

Within the consultation of Medical Assisted Treatment Standards (a policy driven framework for the support of people currently using drugs), there is an emphasis on ensuring people have choices in their treatment plan and information to make informed choices around their care. Within this research, and as part of the training specifically for frontline staff, I implemented an approach to clearly align digital inclusion with the MAT Standards.

5.9 Conclusion

Throughout this chapter, the participatory action research approach taken has given a rich insight into the complexities, challenges and opportunities of implementing a digital inclusion approach which centres around lived expertise. The voices of those who have led and shaped the project have also clearly articulated not only the multi-faceted impact of their exclusion and how this impacts on outcomes in both the virtual and physical domains, but also the possibilities of the myriad of ways in which the internet might also be used to improve their lives. The evidence created clearly links the development of digital understanding to tangible outcomes which might then transform an individual's life, contributing to the literatures exploring digital capital. It has also demonstrated the way in which the trusted intermediary might create a space for shared learning in the context of holistic care, again adding to the existing literature, but adding greater insight through the centring of lived expertise.

Chapter 6: Conclusion

At the outset of this research, I was focused on ensuring that the voices of those with lived expertise would be forefront, with their evidence informing those research questions we set out together to explore through direct action and reflection. The conclusion summarises the findings, the contribution to knowledge, the limitations of the work and also offers some suggestions for both further research and for policymakers, concluding with both a coda, highlighting my personal experience of being part of this approach and an epilogue which touches on the multiple ways in which the findings here have been immediately incorporated into national approaches, in ways that, at the outset, none of us involved could possibly have imagined.

6.1 The research questions addressed

Throughout the period of research, it was important to return to the central questions to ensure that the data gathered, the insights, reflections and movement towards further action remained focussed, despite the fast-changing pace of fieldwork, the pressures of funders, the aspirations of those collectively engaged.

6.1.1 What is the impact of digital inequality on people who are already socially excluded and on those currently experiencing homelessness?

This thesis examines the link between digital inequalities and other inequalities and the varying ways digital tools and digital systems can negatively impact people experiencing homelessness, compounding various hardships and, in several instances, making things worse. What the thesis has demonstrated, particularly through the detailed insights of those experiencing homelessness, is the intersectionality of inequalities and the direct correlation between digital inequality and 'real world' impact, including access to affordable housing, employment, health information and health services, education, social networks and wider support services. This examination adds to the significant body of research evidencing that link.

Digital inequality is both a consequence and a cause of wider social inequality. For people experiencing homelessness, who lack the opportunities of data, devices and support as part of the holistic model evidenced in this research, many of the possible routes out of homelessness are closed. Without the possibility of participation in the online space, individuals are denied agency and autonomy, and their ability to access basic rights is minimised.

6.1.2 What role do digital tools and technologies play in addressing compounded social inequalities?

Furthermore, this thesis also demonstrates that those creating digital systems and services often fail to take digital inequality into account in any meaningful way, offering poor and often inaccessible alternatives (such as the 'phonenumber' for Universal Credit). In doing so, they fail to see the way the creation of such systems in this way, rather than offering people a pathway out of poverty, instead negatively diminishes that person's access to opportunities which might materially, culturally and socially enhance their lives. This insight links clearly to existing literature reflecting on digital capital. Individuals with high levels of digital capital are more likely to be able to use digital technologies to access information, communicate with others, and participate in economic and social activities, but as this thesis shows, those without simply cannot and instead remain trapped in the systemic oppression of a system built on existing privilege.

This then is inequality by design. As we increasingly realise our rights online, and actively participate as citizens in the digital space, individuals without digital privilege will remain not only materially disadvantaged in the short term but also, as we move towards the application of AI informed by existing (biased) data gathered from those already benefiting from the internet, will continue to see that disadvantage and inequality amplified.

6.1.3 What is the most effective approach to involving those affected by such inequality in designing and developing digital initiatives designed to address social (and digital) exclusion? In what way does the trusted intermediary (or 'digital champion') contribute to or minimise existing power structures and hierarchies?

The deliberate intention from the outset of this research was to prioritise those most impacted by digital inequality, seeking not only to engage them as experts by experience but also as actors within the space whose engagement might genuinely effect change, but also to explore this through the trusted relationships of those around them participating in relational, holistic models of care. It is this model which offers some hope. It demonstrates that when people are supported through a profoundly relational approach to digital inclusion that is rooted in kindness and empathy, the digital space might also afford access to social, financial, cultural, and educational capital that can lead to significant material change. The PAR approach offered a closer examination of the role of the trusted intermediary that is often reflected in the literature and allowed for an exploration of the many ways in which an individual's autonomy and agency might either be minimised or enhanced by support

services. Staff reflections showed that, before the research period, they might unwittingly have disempowered those they sought to empower by failing to recognise individual capacity and possibility in the digital space, blindsided by what often presented as unwillingness to engage, but what was, in fact, a historical lack of access, opportunity and support. The PAR approach, the 1:1 relationship within the context of non-judgemental, empathetic, safe and open holistic care, lead not only to overwhelmingly positive outcomes in the digital domain but also to participants feeling in greater control of their lives and able to challenge negative systems of power, whereby they also became able to demand the implementation of their rights.

6.2 Contributions to Knowledge

As has been noted throughout, much has been written around the link between digital inequality and wider social inequalities, exploring systems and devices at the root of digital and wider social inequality: however, the literature in this has not focused with the same intensity on relational approaches to digital inclusion or intersectionality. In the course of so focussing, this research adds weight to the findings from literature in this sphere, demonstrating how the digital space, or the lack of access to it, contributes to the weight already borne by those impacted by systemic inequality.

Moreover, the PAR approach offers a detailed insight into those most affected, allowing us to understand the correlation between systems and effects; on barriers and opportunities. This might best be summarised by Helsper, who notes that ‘Digital societies will not become equitable until traditional socio-economic inequalities are tackled. Nor will we stop the amplification of existing inequalities unless we consider the impact of an unequal distribution of digital resources’ (Helsper, 2021, p193)

The research contributes to the body of Freirian and PAR research. Freire maintained that dialogue was an inherent part of the learning process: this research constantly engaged in reflective dialogue at all levels, and all participants shared their own experiences and perspectives. This dialogue not only empowered participants to develop critical digital understanding (rather than just skills) but also empowered them to take action and question the powers impacting their lives in the real world rather than solely in the digital domain. In line with the other PAR approaches, this action-oriented work, centred on lived experience, has effected permanent change in

Simon Community and beyond, informing the work of national projects such as Connecting Scotland and Digital Lifelines

The thesis also contributes meaningfully to discussions on digital capital, and in particular to research by Ragnedda and Park (Park, 2017b; Ragnedda and Laura Ruiu, 2017; Ragnedda, 2018) demonstrating the way in which digital capital, specifically, gives advantages to those in possession, and disadvantages those who do not, and that this is cumulative in its negative effect. The research demonstrates the way in which digital capital is linked to economic, social and cultural capital and directly corresponds to wider health and social inequalities. It also evidences, however, the way in which individuals might be supported to acquire and develop the necessary skills even though they 'might be hidden behind a mask of disinterestedness' ((Ragnedda and Ruiu, 2020)

The thesis, and the 'doing' of research also contributed significantly to the field of practice. Through this work, I developed and delivered training and resources for frontline staff which then informed work at national and international levels. Resources, created responsively and co-designed throughout, included training materials, internal policies, frameworks, videos, blog pieces and articles.

6.3 Limitations of research

While this research was part of the largest project to address digital inequality for people experiencing homelessness in Scotland to date, there were nevertheless many limitations. In the first research cycle, participants did not have access to devices and data, which undoubtedly impacted on findings. Latter cycles worked with smaller cohorts as funding was drawn into the work, meaning the participant numbers were fewer. The research was also limited by staff time, not in their participation in the project as part of their holistic practice, but in securing the necessary time to focus on collating and reflecting data as PAR researchers themselves. The device recipients were all actively engaged, received payment for their expert input, and were keen to engage in dialogue, design and planning. However, future research proposals might secure a more significant allocation of staff time to engage in PAR approaches in order to strengthen the overall work.

The pandemic also, ironically, contributed to an urgent *necessity* to engage in this work, as the world moved immediately online for all levels of civic, cultural, health and social engagement, but the findings, perhaps, might not be the same had this context been different. To this end, future research should explore similar approaches, particularly in the context of the rapid advancement of digital services accelerated by the pandemic and the cost

of living and mental health crises left in the wake of the years of lockdowns. Furthermore, despite the staff concerns flagged up at the start of the research around issues related to online safety, the research shows no real materialisation of negative impacts. While this may truly have been the case, especially with the focus on a relational, holistic approach, it may also indicate that future research might helpfully explore this specific area in detail.

Another limitation of the research is that the majority of the PAR was focused on one key partner, Simon Community Scotland, particularly in later research cycles, and a relatively small group of participants, both individuals experiencing homeless and support workers, from which to determine findings. However, the strength of the findings from that research has been the depth and understanding gained from the time spent with a smaller group rather than the typical numerical and binary data that is available from much wider groups. Support workers were also able to verify as part of the PAR approach that the findings from the research were representative of their experience.

As a PAR project, it was inevitable that the research would be drawn into territory beyond the core focus of the research questions. The benefit of the PAR approach is that it allows the research to be shaped to a significant degree by the research participants, and this was often the case with the research for this thesis. However, I would also argue that this was to the benefit of the overall research. At the outset, it was not expected that the focus in future cycles would be on harm reduction specifically: this was led by participants. In order to maintain integrity, however, engagement also focused in on key research questions, exploring these in new contexts. The liberty afforded participants gave their responses a strong sense of depth and allowed themes to emerge which would otherwise not have been explored.

Finally, as discussed, it is impossible not to recognise in the research conducted for this thesis that the PAR approach carries certain unalienable risks: my participation as a 'trainer' involved in the project, and my status as an academic amid frontline staff who were offering such incredible holistic care for participants themselves experiencing homelessness, could be said to have had an indirect influence on findings. However, an awareness of those limitations allowed me to mitigate the impacts, and the reassurance of cross-verification of findings from different groups within the PAR addressed this.

6.4 Recommendations for funders, policymakers and practitioners

Align digital inclusion work with human rights, and include approaches that consider applying digital ethics through this lens, ensuring that people are included and shaping the digital landscape.

- Ensure addressing digital inequality is a collective imperative and that organisations across private, public and third sectors are required to engage in positive action, particularly as they develop digital services.

6.4.1 Recommendation for policy: Devices and data still matter. The first level digital divide should be reflected in policy

The first level digital divide that of access to devices and sufficient data, continues to be an essential consideration. The research has also shown that public access computers in shared community spaces do not necessarily empower individuals to become autonomous in their internet use, as this 'gatekeeping' impacts experiential learning. However, many pandemic responses to digital inequality *did* build in device ownership models and accompanying data packages. In its first twelve months, in partnership with SCVO, Scottish Government funded and implemented Connecting Scotland, a national approach which supported 1,047 organisations to deliver 4,917 projects. In total, 30,462 Chromebooks, 29,697 iPads and 51,021 MiFi Devices were issued to households across Scotland.

Emerging post-pandemic data, however, shows that connectivity, in particular, is an issue for those most impacted by structural poverty and made worse by the cost of living crisis (Holmes and Burgess, 2022). If we accept that digital inclusion is a fundamental right, then the mechanism by which we might access these rights must also be available to all. Work must therefore be done to ensure that devices and data are available to all, and that this commitment is reflected in policy, particularly in such policy impacting on marginalised groups.

6.4.2 Recommendation for Funders: Invest in participatory action research projects that disrupt existing hierarchies of power and social class led by those with lived experience.

Lip service is often given to the value of lived expertise, sometimes intentionally, when the creation of a system is there to serve not an individual but rather an organisation or political power, and sometimes accidentally, such as

when funding bodies lay intended outcomes at the heart of their offer, which fails to allow for real disruption of existing hierarchies. Only through open funding offers, which helps participatory action in all its' messy glory to evolve, can such disruption occur. This thesis has demonstrated the value of such disruption and the capacity of such disruption must effect change and opportunity for people who have been victims of systemic oppression through poverty. Therefore, funders seeking to support social justice work should embrace such approaches and understand the value of smaller scale work to inform larger scale models. Furthermore, this research has engaged both people with lived experience and staff as researchers, resulting in rich data which clearly draws the lines between digital skills and outcomes, allowing us to understand the direct impact of work in this space.

Embedding support for organisations to develop their skills in PAR approaches would undoubtedly be a meaningful way to further research which might inform policy going forward, rather than simply engaging in short-term consultations.

6.4.3 Recommendation across Private, Public and Third Sector: Digital inequality should be a shared responsibility.

The research has also shown how digital inequality impacts every area of life, across education, health, housing, employability, social connections, civic engagement, access to justice and across all contemporary social issues: it is not a niche area but rather entirely intersectional. To this end, every public service should consider how digital inequality plays out in their particular domain and how every service must consider action to address that digital inequality, not only through the provision of material access but also through the provision of networked support. Again, setting such discussions in the Human Rights framework may help in this regard.

Policymakers across all directorates should ensure that policy seeks to not only counteract the impact of digital inequality, and in particular in those directorates already tackling wider social inequalities, such as homelessness and poverty, but also to actively empower marginalised communities through centering lived experience in the design of digital public services. Services should also be required to ensure that they are designed in such a way that they do not amplify, create or contribute to further inequality.

6.4.4 Recommendation for policy: The intersection of digital rights, human rights and digital ethics should be reflected across policy

Further research might also, through similarly participatory approaches, explore whether such an approach can minimise the risk of online harm, as indicated here. Finally, as this thesis has examined the impact of digital systems on individuals, there is also an essential space for future field-based practice and collaborative research to consider the application of discussions around digital ethics through a digital inclusion lens to ensure that those in most need of support are not further marginalised by emerging technology, nor exploited in the digital domain. By aligning digital rights with human rights, as is increasingly common in both academic literature and practice, there is a resultant necessity to protect those rights in human rights in the digital space, including rights such as the right to access information, the right to freedom of expression, the right to privacy, and the right to security. This necessity is helpful for those impacted by inequality and those walking alongside, as it gives a language and framework by which change can be effected collectively.

Digital ethics, or the ethical principles that might consequently guide the development and use of digital services, as well as applications and websites, should also frame this discussion in the practice field. As those with lived expertise and frontline staff have become critically engaged through this study, they have begun to explore principles such as the principle of privacy, the principle of non-discrimination, and the principle of transparency collectively, particularly through the creation of the app.

Exploration of both the application of digital rights and the consideration of digital ethics should be a core part of digital inclusion work moving forward, and in particular, both research and policy should centre lived expertise to gain insight and knowledge about the 'real-life challenges and impact.

6.4.5 Recommendation for practitioners: Supporting the 'trusted intermediary': aligning digital inclusion work with the 'day job.'

To support relational approaches to addressing digital inequality, staff require not only the space and time to develop meaningful relationships with those they walk alongside (and the language of both harm reduction and trauma-informed practice can help here) but also the training and opportunity themselves to continue exploring the digital space, where new technologies will undoubtedly continue to replicate systemic inequality.

Furthermore, aligning concrete *digital* outcomes to existing policies, principles and practices which already inform

frontline roles, such as, for instance, those outlined by SSSC, The Promise Scotland and the MAT Standards, mean that digital inclusion is embedded in the roles of staff in an actionable and practical way. It is vital that we continue to develop and support models of digital inclusion work which focus on the inter-relational development of critical digital understanding.

This is essential also across the public sector, and in particular should inform the work of the NHS, which moves increasingly towards technology enabled healthcare as a standard. It is essential that those 'prescribing' digital tools to manage health conditions are equipped with the skills and resources to meet people where they are at in the digital domain and build meaningful trust to ensure that digital tools for wellbeing are not only for those with privilege.

6.4.6 Kindness, love and empathy matter in both policy and practice

Finally, without doubt one of the most significant insights here is the way in which kindness is indeed a powerful agent of change, particularly in working with people who have experienced systemic abuse, stigmatisation, and marginalisation and who are consequently disempowered. Such principles often do not feature in models of digital inclusion work, yet these are the tools that lead most clearly to tangible outcomes. For example, I was recently asked to be part of a project led by the private sector to engage people offline with the digital space. Unsurprisingly, the organisation has a clear agenda: to encourage individuals to engage in digital systems which will benefit the company. Staff from the participating bank were trained as 'digital champions' but still found the relational aspect challenging to understand until they began their work directly with people, with the 'permission' to engage freely, on a human level and without agenda. In the wrap-up of the session, staff reflected immediately the myriad of ways that they now saw the impact of the digital domain on peoples' lives and how, through the sharing of lived experience in an atmosphere of empathy, curiosity, and shared learning, they better understood how they might be part of a solution.

Relational approaches, rooted in kindness and empathy, affect meaningful and lasting change, which flows both ways. The sharing of stories, of lived expertise, matters. It is heartening to see such themes emerging in public policy in Scotland; however, it is vital to ensure that this is no empty promise but rather an intrinsic approach to addressing inequality.

'True solidarity is found only in the plenitude of this act of love, in its existentiality, in its praxis. To affirm that men and women are persons and as persons should be free, and yet to do nothing tangible to make this affirmation a reality, is a farce' (Freire, 1972, p 50)

6.4.7 Recommendation for future research

Participatory action research and other immersive approaches offer the field of study an opportunity not only to explore and highlight intersecting inequalities, placing lived expertise at the heart of the work, but also the opportunity to understand the interventions that might meaningfully offer a positive change in the direction of travel. It would be interesting to explore similar models with partners in public health, for instance, to explore the ways in which digital inequality impacts on access to technology enabled healthcare. Socio-anthropological approaches would also offer deeper, meaningful insight, and again is an approach which seems to be absent in the field of study.

Such approaches disrupt power imbalances and offer greater opportunity for collective advocacy through shared understanding and collective action.

6.4.7 Final remarks

This research has been integral to my professional, academic and personal life for the last five years, especially during the unprecedented turmoil of the global pandemic, which brought digital inequality into sharp relief, and brought me to tears at my kitchen table. The research has profoundly impacted each of these domains: it has both informed and consolidated my personal politics and my commitment to social justice work; it has impacted the organisation I work with, Mhor Collective, and how we articulate and explain the work we do, as well as the way in which we do it. Academically, I have learned much from the doctoral research process, from engaging with literature to patient discussions with my supervisor.

However, I have learned far more through the methodological approach, which enabled me to make the space to listen and learn from those who have much to teach and who may not see themselves as experts. I have seen first-hand the way in which participatory action research can empower people who are marginalised and

oppressed by systemic inequality and how, by giving them a voice in the research process, not only do they feel more in control of their lives but also that they can lead on change. I have also seen the incomprehensible levels of kindness, love and empathy of frontline staff who walk alongside people in the hardship of their circumstances, and that this open-hearted and non-judgemental relational approach is essential to effect change. Only through positive disruption in the spirit of genuine, loving solidarity might we challenge the existing systems of power that replicate and magnify inequalities both in the digital and offline domains.

Epilogue

It would be remiss to conclude this thesis without a reflection on the extent to which the participatory action research approach taken here has informed not only the work of Simon Community Scotland but also the work of SCVO, Mhor Collective and the Scottish Government in ways that we could not have imagined at the outset. Over the last six years, by centring the voices of those they walk alongside, Simon Community Scotland has become a European leader in ensuring that people experiencing homelessness are supported in accessing the opportunities of the internet, supplying devices, data and one-to-one holistic support for *everyone* accessing their services. The digital champion training developed for this work continues to evolve and is delivered by the organisation I work with. Simon Community Scotland is dedicated to addressing digital inequality as part of their work to help people overcome homelessness.

To the best of my knowledge, the Digital Approach to Harm Reduction is one of the only projects in Europe to link Harm Reduction, digital inclusion and participatory action research, and it received the Digital Health and Social Care Award for Best Digital Inclusion initiative in 2023. It, too, has grown, and colleagues recently travelled to Portugal to work with others in the space to embed the model in Lisbon, drawing on the expertise given by the women in Scotland. SCVO and the Scottish Government have also adopted the model as part of Digital Lifelines, a national project which 'seeks to improve digital inclusion and to design digital solutions that better meet people's needs, to improve the health outcomes for people who use drugs, reducing the risk of harm and death.' (Digital Lifelines, 2023) and the app, created by the women in the project, is now being developed to be offered nationally, in the hope that it, too, will minimise the number of people dying in drug-related deaths by providing safe and accessible information around drug use, mental and physical health and connection to services. The app also centres the women's voices, with experiences shared through podcasts, to minimise the isolation many

women who use drugs often feel and ensure they do not think of themselves alone. Furthermore, in partnership with Simon Community Scotland and Mhor Collective, Digital Lifelines is collaborating on a digital inclusion playbook for organisations working with people in a harm reduction context, to give them some of the tools that might be useful in embedding digital inclusion as part of holistic care.

As stated earlier in the thesis, SCVO continues to lead and inspire the sector to support and advocate for digital participation for all. Not only did the organisation meet some of the unprecedented needs of the offline population during the pandemic through the development and delivery of the Scottish Government's Connecting Scotland, supporting thousands of digital champions using the training developed as part of this research, but they also continue to deliver extensive programmes of work to address digital inequality across Scotland, increasingly focussed on rights-based approaches. We are lucky enough to be active colleagues in many of their initiatives.

The organisation I work with, Mhor Collective, continues to work across the devolved nation, but also across the U.K, and most recently, our work has taken us to Canada to work with the newly formed GEO Nova Scotia, where we are supporting their implementation of a Canada-wide digital inclusion project through co-design, development and delivery of digital champion training. We, too, embed lived expertise in all of our work, taking PAR approaches wherever possible. We have become bolder in articulating digital inclusion as a fundamental right and in advocating for collective and direct action by every organisation (public, third and private) seeking to implement digital systems or services as part of their work . We continue to work alongside The University of the West of Scotland on action research approaches, most recently writing together on digital ethics, and currently evaluating a place-based approach to digital inclusion in Renfrewshire.

Every piece of my professional life has been impacted by the learning from this PAR approach, and it is overwhelming to see that shared experience resonate and inform so widely.

Bibliography

Access and Inclusion in 2018 (2018) Available at:

https://www.ofcom.org.uk/__data/assets/pdf_file/0018/132912/Access-and-Inclusion-report-2018.pdf

(Accessed: 16 January 2019).

Alabi, A.O. and Mutula, S.M. (2020) 'Digital inclusion for visually impaired students through assistive technologies in academic libraries', *Library Hi Tech News*, 37(2), pp. 14–17. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/LHTN-11-2019-0081>.

Bauer, J.M. (2018) 'The Internet and income inequality: Socio-economic challenges in a hyperconnected society', *Telecommunications Policy*, 42(4). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.telpol.2017.05.009>.

Beaunoyer, E., Dupéré, S. and Guitton, M.J. (2020) 'COVID-19 and digital inequalities: Reciprocal impacts and mitigation strategies', *Computers in Human Behavior*, 111, p. 106424. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2020.106424>.

Belcher, J.R. and DeForge, B.R. (2012) 'Social Stigma and Homelessness: The Limits of Social Change', <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/10911359.2012.707941>, 22(8), pp. 929–946. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/10911359.2012.707941>.

Blackwell, C. *et al.* (2023) 'A Minimum Digital Living Standard for Households with Children: Summary'.

Blank, G. and Lutz, C. (2018) 'Benefits and harms from Internet use: A differentiated analysis of Great Britain', *New Media and Society*, 20(2), pp. 618–640. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444816667135>.

Bourdieu, P. (1986) 'THE FORMS OF CAPITAL', in, pp. 241–258.

Bowyer, G. (no date) *Switched On Exploring the challenge of adequate digital access for all children and young people*. Available at: https://d1ssu070pg2v9i.cloudfront.net/pex/carnegie_uk_trust/2019/02/21143338/LOW-RES-3999-CUKT-Switched-On-Report-ONLINE.pdf (Accessed: 26 March 2019).

Bramley, G. and Fitzpatrick, S. (2017) 'Homelessness in the UK: who is most at risk?', <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/02673037.2017.1344957>, 33(1), pp. 96–116. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02673037.2017.1344957>.

Campbell, F.A. *et al.* (2004) 'The effect of format modifications and reading comprehension on recall of informed consent information by low-income parents: a comparison of print, video, and computer-based presentations', *Patient education and counseling*, 53(2), pp. 205–216. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0738-3991\(03\)00162-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0738-3991(03)00162-9).

Carlson, A. and Isaacs, A.M. (2018) 'Technological capital: an alternative to the digital divide', *Journal of Applied Communication Research*, 46(2). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00909882.2018.1437279>.

Carmi, E. *et al.* (2020) 'Data citizenship: Rethinking data literacy in the age of disinformation, misinformation, and malinformation', *Internet Policy Review*, 9(2). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.14763/2020.2.1481>.

Castells, M. and Cardoso, G. (2005) *The Network Society From Knowledge to Policy Edited by*. Available at: <http://transatlantic.sais-jhu.edu> (Accessed: 28 October 2019).

Cerf, V. (1999) 'The Internet is for Everyone', in *e Computers, Freedom and Privacy Conference 7 April*.

Chadwick, D.D. and Quinn, S. (2016) 'Perceptions of the risks and benefits of Internet access and use by people with intellectual disabilities', *British Journal of Learning Disabilities*, 45, pp. 21–31. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/bld.12170>.

Chiner, E., Gómez-Puerta, M. and Cardona-Moltó, M.C. (2017) 'Internet and people with intellectual disability: an approach to caregivers' concerns, prevention strategies and training needs', *Journal of New Approaches in Educational Research* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.7821/naer.2017.7.243>.

Christie, N.C. (2021) 'The role of social isolation in opioid addiction', *Social Cognitive and Affective Neuroscience*, 16(7), pp. 645–656. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/SCAN/NSAB029>.

Citizens Advice Bureau Scotland (no date) *Locked out: the Smartphone Deficit*.

Cook, T. (2009) 'The purpose of mess in action research: building rigour through a messy turn', <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/09650790902914241>, 17(2), pp. 277–291. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09650790902914241>.

- Correa, T., Pavez, I. and Contreras, J. (2018) 'Digital inclusion through mobile phones?: A comparison between mobile-only and computer users in internet access, skills and use', *Information Communication and Society* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369118X.2018.1555270>.
- Cottam, H. (2018) 'Radical Help – Hilary revolutionise the welfare state', 1.
- Court, D. and Latapi, P. (1979) 'THE RESEARCH PROCESS'.
- Covid-19 is magnifying the digital divide - The BMJ* (2020). Available at: <https://blogs.bmj.com/bmj/2020/09/01/covid-19-is-magnifying-the-digital-divide/> (Accessed: 25 September 2020).
- Crane, P. and Richardson, L. (2000) 'Reconnect Action Research Kit'.
- Van Deursen, A., Van Dijk, J. and Ebbers, W. (2006) 'Why E-government usage lags behind: Explaining the gap between potential and actual usage of electronic public services in the Netherlands', *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)*, 4084 LNCS, pp. 269–280. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/11823100_24.
- van Deursen, A.J.A.M., Courtois, C. and van Dijk, J.A.G.M. (2014) 'Internet Skills, Sources of Support, and Benefiting From Internet Use', *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/10447318.2013.858458>.
- Van Deursen, A.J.A.M. and Van Dijk, J.A.G.M. (2016) 'Modeling Traditional Literacy, Internet Skills and Internet Usage: An Empirical Study', *Interacting with Computers*, 28(1). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/iwc/iwu027>.
- van Deursen, A.J.A.M. and Helsper, E.J. (2015) 'The Third-Level Digital Divide: Who Benefits Most from Being Online?', in, pp. 29–52. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/s2050-206020150000010002>.
- Van Deursen, A.J.A.M. and Helsper, E.J. (2018) 'Collateral benefits of Internet use: Explaining the diverse outcomes of engaging with the Internet', *New Media and Society*, 20(7). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444817715282>.
- van Deursen, A.J.A.M. and Mossberger, K. (2018) 'Any Thing for Anyone? A New Digital Divide in Internet-of-Things Skills', *Policy and Internet*, 10(2), pp. 122–140. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/POI3.171>.

- Van Dijk, J.A.G.M. (2017a) 'Digital Divide: Impact of Access'. Available at:
<https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118783764.wbieme0043>.
- Van Dijk, J.A.G.M. (2017b) 'Digital Divide: Impact of Access'. Available at:
<https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118783764.wbieme0043>.
- Dodel, M. and Mesch, G. (2018) 'Inequality in digital skills and the adoption of online safety behaviors', *Information, Communication & Society*, 21(5), pp. 712–728. Available at:
<https://doi.org/10.1080/1369118X.2018.1428652>.
- Fals-Borda, O. (1995) *Research for Social Justice, North-South Convergences Plenary*. Available at: <http://comm-org.wisc.edu/si/falsborda.htm> (Accessed: 22 May 2022).
- Farag, A., Greeley, L. and Swindell, A. (2021) 'Freire 2.0: Pedagogy of the digitally oppressed', *https://doi.org/10.1080/00131857.2021.2010541*, 54(13), pp. 2214–2227. Available at:
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00131857.2021.2010541>.
- Ferguson, Z. and Carnegie United Kingdom Trust. (no date) 'Kinder communities : the power of everyday relationships', p. 37. Available at: <https://www.carnegieuktrust.org.uk/publications/kinder-communities-power-everyday-relationships/> (Accessed: 30 April 2023).
- Ferrara, E., Cresci, S. and Luceri, L. (2020) 'Misinformation, manipulation, and abuse on social media in the era of COVID-19', *Journal of Computational Social Science*, 3(2), pp. 271–277. Available at:
<https://doi.org/10.1007/S42001-020-00094-5/FIGURES/1>.
- Freire, P. (1972) *Pedagogy of the oppressed.*, Penguin.
- Freire, P. and Ramos, M.B. (2017) 'Pedagogy of the oppressed', p. 156.
- French, T., Quinn, L. and Yates, S. (2018) *Digital Motivation: Exploring the reasons people are offline*. Available at:
https://www.goodthingsfoundation.org/sites/default/files/research-publications/understanding_motivations_of_non-users_of_the_internet_report_v2.pdf (Accessed: 16 May 2019).
- Frideres, James. (1992) *A world of communities : participatory research perspectives*. North York Ont.: Captus Univ. Publ.

- Friedline, T. and Chen, Z. (2021) 'Digital redlining and the fintech marketplace: Evidence from US zip codes', *Journal of Consumer Affairs*, 55(2), pp. 366–388. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/JOCA.12297>.
- Gibson, L., Sloan, D. and Moncur, W. (2013) 'E-health and digital inclusion', *User-Driven Healthcare: Concepts, Methodologies, Tools, and Applications*, 1, pp. 197–210. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-4666-2770-3.CH011>.
- Goggin, G. (2017) 'Disability and digital inequalities: Rethinking digital divides with disability theory', in *Theorizing Digital Divides*. Taylor and Francis, pp. 63–74. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315455334>.
- Goggin, G., Ellis, K. and Hawkins, W. (2019) 'Disability at the centre of digital inclusion: assessing a new moment in technology and rights', *Communication Research and Practice*, 5(3), pp. 290–303. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/22041451.2019.1641061>.
- Golembiewski, E. *et al.* (2017) 'Social Network Decay as Potential Recovery from Homelessness: A Mixed Methods Study in Housing First Programming', *Social sciences (Basel, Switzerland)*, 6(3). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/SOCSCI6030096>.
- Gonzalez, R., Fuentes, A. and Muñoz, E. (2020) 'On Social Capital and Health: The Moderating Role of Income Inequality in Comparative Perspective', *International Journal of Sociology*, 50(1), pp. 68–85. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207659.2019.1709138>.
- Goss, E.P. and Phillips, J.M. (2002) 'How information technology affects wages: Evidence using Internet usage as a proxy for IT skills', *Journal of Labor Research*, 23(3), pp. 463–474. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/S12122-002-1047-X>.
- Government, T.S. (2014) *Digital Participation: A National Framework for Local Action - gov.scot*. Available at: <https://www.gov.scot/publications/digital-participation-national-framework-local-action/pages/7/> (Accessed: 11 May 2021).
- Haight, M., Quan-Haase, A. and Corbett, B.A. (2014) 'Revisiting the digital divide in Canada: the impact of demographic factors on access to the internet, level of online activity, and social networking site usage', *Information, Communication & Society*, 17(4), pp. 503–519. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369118X.2014.891633>.

- Harris, C., Straker, L. and Pollock, C. (2017) 'A socioeconomic related "digital divide" exists in how, not if, young people use computers', *PLoS ONE*, 12(3). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0175011>.
- Helsper, E. (2021) 'The Digital Disconnect: The Social Causes and Consequences of Digital Inequalities Digital World: From Divides to Socio-Digital Inequalities'. Available at: <https://dx.doi.org/10.4135/9781526492982.n3> (Accessed: 25 February 2023).
- Helsper, E.J. (2017) 'The Social Relativity of Digital Exclusion: Applying Relative Deprivation Theory to Digital Inequalities', *Communication Theory*, 27(3), pp. 223–242. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/comt.12110>.
- Herr, K. and Anderson, G. (2012) 'The Action Research Dissertation: A Guide for Students and Faculty', *The Action Research Dissertation: A Guide for Students and Faculty* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781452226644>.
- Hibbard, J. and Gilbert, H. (2014) 'Supporting people to manage their health: An introduction to patient activation'.
- Holmes, H. and Burgess, G. (2022) 'Digital exclusion and poverty in the UK: How structural inequality shapes experiences of getting online', *Digital Geography and Society*, 3, p. 100041. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.DIGGEO.2022.100041>.
- Humphry, J. (2019) 'Looking for Wi-Fi: youth homelessness and mobile connectivity in the city', *Information, Communication & Society*, pp. 1–15. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369118x.2019.1670227>.
- Itu (2019) *The State of Broadband 2019 Broadband as a Foundation for Sustainable Development*.
- Jaeger, P.T. et al. (2012) 'The Intersection of Public Policy and Public Access: Digital Divides, Digital Literacy, Digital Inclusion, and Public Libraries', *Public Library Quarterly*, 31(1), pp. 1–20. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/01616846.2012.654728>.
- JAM Van Deursen, A. et al. (2017) 'The compoundness and sequentiality of digital inequality', *International Journal of Communication* [Preprint].

James, E., Milenkiewicz, M. and Bucknam, A. (2014) 'Cycles of PAR: The Power of the Iterative Process', *Participatory Action Research for Educational Leadership: Using Data-Driven Decision Making to Improve Schools*, pp. 145–158. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781483329369.N9>.

Jarvis, P. (1999) 'The Practitioner-Researcher. Developing Theory from Practice. Jossey-Bass Higher and Adult Education Series.', *The Practitioner-Researcher. Developing Theory from Practice*, pp. 131–137.

Kindon, S.Louise., Pain, Rachel. and Kesby, M. (2007) 'Participatory action research approaches and methods : connecting people, participation and place', p. 260.

van Laar, E. *et al.* (2017) 'The relation between 21st-century skills and digital skills: A systematic literature review', *Computers in Human Behavior*, 72. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2017.03.010>.

LATAPI, P. (1988) 'Participatory Research : A New Research Paradigm ? in Adult Education in International Perspective', *Alberta journal of educational research*, 34(3).

Lemieux-Cumberlege, A. and Taylor, E.P. (2019) 'An exploratory study on the factors affecting the mental health and well-being of frontline workers in homeless services', *Health & Social Care in the Community*, 27(4), pp. e367–e378. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/HSC.12738>.

Lindell, J. (2020) 'Digital Capital: A Bourdieusian Perspective on the Digital Divide', <https://doi.org/10.1177/0267323120935320>, 35(4), pp. 423–425. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0267323120935320>.

Lissitsa, S., Chachashvili-Bolotin, S. and Bokek-Cohen, Y. (2017) 'Digital skills and extrinsic rewards in late career', *Technology in Society*, 51, pp. 46–55. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.TECHSOC.2017.07.006>.

Livingstone, S. (2014) 'Children's digital rights: a priority Article (Published version) (Refereed)'.

Lloyds Bank Consumer Digital Index 2019 (2019). Available at:

https://www.lloydsbank.com/assets/media/pdfs/banking_with_us/whats-happening/LB-Consumer-Digital-Index-2019-Report.pdf (Accessed: 2 September 2019).

Malcom-Piqueux, L.E. (2015) *Participatory action research, Research in the College Context: Approaches and Methods*. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315740447-12>.

- Marlatt, A.G., Larimer, M.E. and Witkiewitz, K. (2011) *Harm Reduction, Second Edition: Pragmatic Strategies for Managing High-Risk ...* - Google Books, Guilford Press, London. Available at: https://books.google.co.uk/books?hl=en&lr=&id=9UeIN01-fgwC&oi=fnd&pg=PP2&ots=3gl21AKdLz&sig=NUn2K9v9Srx2pPoFcnL38ZRAMw&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q&f=false (Accessed: 29 April 2023).
- Mathiesen, K. (2014) 'Human Rights for the Digital Age', <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/08900523.2014.863124>, 29(1), pp. 2–18. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/08900523.2014.863124>.
- McIntyre, A. (2008) 'Participatory Action Research'. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781483385679>.
- McTaggart, R., Nixon, R. and Kemmis, S. (2017) 'Critical Participatory Action Research', *The Palgrave International Handbook of Action Research*, pp. 21–35. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1057/978-1-137-40523-4_2.
- Mihelj, S., Leguina, A. and Downey, J. (2019) 'Culture is digital: Cultural participation, diversity and the digital divide', *New Media & Society*, p. 146144481882281. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444818822816>.
- Millar, J. and Bennett, F. (2017) 'Universal Credit: Assumptions, Contradictions and Virtual Reality', *Social Policy and Society*, 16(2). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1017/s1474746416000154>.
- Min, S.J. (2010) 'From the digital divide to the democratic divide: Internet skills, political interest, and the second-level digital divide in political internet use', *Journal of Information Technology and Politics* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/19331680903109402>.
- National Performance Framework | National Performance Framework* (no date). Available at: <https://nationalperformance.gov.scot/> (Accessed: 28 May 2023).
- Nyemba, F. and Mayer, M. (2017) 'Exploring the roots of participatory action research: An interview with Dr Marja-Liisa Swantz', <https://doi.org/10.1177/1476750316684003>, 16(3), pp. 319–338. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1476750316684003>.
- P., R. *et al.* (2013) 'Enhancing social participation in young people with disabilities: Evidence based strategies for supporting access to online social networking', *Developmental Medicine and Child Neurology* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/dmcn.12259>.

- Pain, R., Whitman, G. and Milledge, D. (2017) *Participatory Action Research Toolkit: An introduction to Learning, Research and Action using PAR as an approach*.
- Park, S. (2017a) *Digital capital, Digital Capital*. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1057/978-1-137-59332-0>.
- Park, S. (2017b) *Digital capital, Digital Capital*. Palgrave Macmillan. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1057/978-1-137-59332-0>.
- Park, S. and Park, S. (2017) 'The Varied Spectrum of Digital Engagement', in *Digital Capital*. Palgrave Macmillan UK, pp. 13–34. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1057/978-1-137-59332-0_2.
- Philip, L.J., Cottrill, C. and Farrington, J. (2015) "'Two-speed' Scotland: Patterns and Implications of the Digital Divide in Contemporary Scotland', *Scottish Geographical Journal*, 131(3–4). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14702541.2015.1067327>.
- Phillips, L. (2015) 'Homelessness: Perception of Causes and Solutions', <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/10875549.2014.951981>, 19(1), pp. 1–19. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/10875549.2014.951981>.
- Pinxten, W. and Lievens, J. (2014) 'The importance of economic, social and cultural capital in understanding health inequalities: using a Bourdieu-based approach in research on physical and mental health perceptions', *Sociology of Health & Illness*, 36(7), pp. 1095–1110. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9566.12154>.
- Pirisi, A. (2000) 'Low health literacy prevents equal access to care.', *Lancet*, 356(9244), p. 1828. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(05\)73297-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(05)73297-9).
- Polizzi, G. (2020) 'Digital literacy and the national curriculum for England: Learning from how the experts engage with and evaluate online content', *Computers & Education*, 152, p. 103859. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.COMPEDU.2020.103859>.
- Radovanović, D., Hogan, B. and Lalić, D. (2015) 'Overcoming digital divides in higher education: Digital literacy beyond Facebook', *New Media and Society*, 17(10). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444815588323>.
- Ragnedda, M. (2018) 'Conceptualizing Digital Capital', *Telematics and Informatics*, (8), p. 35. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tele.2018.10.006>.

- Ragnedda, M. and Laura Ruiu, and M. (2017) 'Social capital and the three levels of digital divide', in *Theorizing Digital Divides*. Routledge, pp. 21–34. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315455334-3>.
- Ragnedda, M. and Ruiu, M.L. (2020) 'DIGITAL CAPITAL: A Bourdieusian Perspective on the Digital Divide', *Digital Capital: A Bourdieusian Perspective on the Digital Divide*, pp. 1–122. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/9781839095504/URN:EMERALDGROUP.COM:ASSET:ID:BINARY:9781839095504.LARGE:OVER.GIF>.
- Ragnedda, M., Ruiu, M.L. and Addeo, F. (2019) 'Measuring Digital Capital: An empirical investigation', *New Media and Society* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444819869604>.
- Rains, S.A. and Tsetsi, E. (2017) 'Social support and digital inequality: Does Internet use magnify or mitigate traditional inequities in support availability?', *Communication Monographs*, 84(1). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/03637751.2016.1228252>.
- Ramsetty, A. and Adams, C. (2020) 'Impact of the digital divide in the age of COVID-19', *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association : JAMIA*, 27(7), pp. 1147–1148. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/jamia/ocaa078>.
- Ramsetty, A. and Adams, C. (no date) 'Impact of the digital divide in the age of COVID-19'. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/jamia/ocaa078>.
- Ramsten, C. *et al.* (2018) 'Information and communication technology use in daily life among young adults with mild-to-moderate intellectual disability', *Journal of Intellectual Disabilities*, p. 174462951878435. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1744629518784351>.
- Rea, J. (2023) 'Social relationships, stigma, and wellbeing through experiences of homelessness in the United Kingdom', *Journal of Social Issues*, 79(1), pp. 465–493. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/JOSI.12572>.
- Real, B. *et al.* (2015) 'Digital Inclusion and the Affordable Care Act: Public Libraries, Politics, Policy, and Enrollment in "Obamacare"', *Public Library Quarterly*, 34(1). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/01616846.2015.1000770>.
- Roberson, J. and Nardi, B. (2010) *Survival Needs and Social Inclusion: Technology Use Among the Homeless*.

- Robinson, L. *et al.* (2020) 'Digital inequalities 2.0: Legacy inequalities in the information age', *First Monday* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5210/FM.V25I7.10842>.
- Roozenbeek, J. *et al.* (2020) 'Susceptibility to misinformation about COVID-19 around the world', *Royal Society Open Science*, 7(10). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1098/RSOS.201199>.
- Scholz, F., Yalcin, B. and Priestley, M. (2017) 'Internet access for disabled people: Understanding socio-relational factors in Europe', *Cyberpsychology: Journal of Psychosocial Research on Cyberspace*, 11(1), p. 4. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5817/CP2017-1-4>.
- Scottish Government (2021a) *A changing nation: how Scotland will thrive in a digital world* - gov.scot. Available at: <https://www.gov.scot/publications/a-changing-nation-how-scotland-will-thrive-in-a-digital-world/> (Accessed: 29 May 2022).
- Scottish Government (2021b) 'Reset and Rebuild: A Recovery Plan for Sexual Health and Blood Borne Virus Services'.
- Scottish Government, T. (no date) *REALISING SCOTLAND'S FULL POTENTIAL IN A DIGITAL WORLD: A DIGITAL STRATEGY FOR SCOTLAND*.
- Seifert, A. (2020a) 'The Digital Exclusion of Older Adults during the COVID-19 Pandemic', *Journal of Gerontological Social Work* [Preprint]. Routledge. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/01634372.2020.1764687>.
- Seifert, A. (2020b) 'The Digital Exclusion of Older Adults during the COVID-19 Pandemic', *Journal of Gerontological Social Work* [Preprint]. Routledge. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/01634372.2020.1764687>.
- Selwyn, N. (2004) 'Reconsidering Political and Popular Understandings of the Digital Divide', *New Media & Society*, 6(3), pp. 341–362. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444804042519>.
- Shimei, N. and Lavie-Ajayi, M. (2021) 'Four practices for conducting feminist participatory action research with young women', <https://doi.org/10.1177/14767503211036489>, 20(3), pp. 261–277. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/14767503211036489>.
- Skog, D.A., Wimelius, H. and Sandberg, J. (2018) 'Digital Disruption', *Business and Information Systems Engineering*, 60(5), pp. 431–437. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/S12599-018-0550-4/FIGURES/1>.

- Somerville, P. (2013) 'Understanding Homelessness', <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/14036096.2012.756096>, 30(4), pp. 384–415. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14036096.2012.756096>.
- Song, L. (2013) 'Social capital and health', in *Medical Sociology on the Move: New Directions in Theory*. Springer Netherlands, pp. 233–257. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-6193-3_12.
- Stevenson, S. (2009) 'Digital divide: A discursive move away from the real inequities', *Information Society*, 25(1), pp. 1–22. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/01972240802587539>.
- Stevenson, S.A. and Domsy, C. (2016) 'Redeploying public librarians to the front-lines: prioritizing digital inclusion', *Library Review*. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/LR-02-2016-0015>.
- Sudore, R.L. *et al.* (2006) 'Use of a Modified Informed Consent Process among Vulnerable Patients: A Descriptive Study', *Journal of General Internal Medicine*, 21(8), pp. 867–873. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/J.1525-1497.2006.00535.X>.
- Tait, A.R. *et al.* (2005) 'Improving the readability and processability of a pediatric informed consent document: effects on parents' understanding', *Archives of pediatrics & adolescent medicine*, 159(4), pp. 347–352. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1001/ARCHPEDI.159.4.347>.
- Taylor, L. (2017) 'What is data justice? The case for connecting digital rights and freedoms globally', *Big Data and Society*, 4(2). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/2053951717736335>.
- The Scottish Government (2012) 'Scotland's Digital Future: infrastructure action plan'. Available at: <http://www.gov.scot/publications/scotlands-digital-future-infrastructure-action-plan/> (Accessed: 27 May 2023).
- Thomson, P. and Gunterb, H. (2011) 'Inside, outside, upside down: the fluidity of academic researcher "identity" in working with/in school', <https://doi.org/10.1080/1743727X.2011.552309>, 34(1), pp. 17–30. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/1743727X.2011.552309>.
- Tsai, H. yi S. *et al.* (2015) 'Getting Grandma Online: Are Tablets the Answer for Increasing Digital Inclusion for Older Adults in the U.S.?', *Educational Gerontology*, 41(10). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/03601277.2015.1048165>.

- UK Consumer Digital Index 2021 | Lloyds Bank (no date). Available at: <https://www.lloydsbank.com/banking-with-us/whats-happening/consumer-digital-index.html> (Accessed: 13 December 2021).
- Vial, G. (2019) 'Understanding digital transformation: A review and a research agenda', *The Journal of Strategic Information Systems*, 28(2), pp. 118–144. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JSIS.2019.01.003>.
- Vida Estacio, E., Whittle, R. and Protheroe, J. (no date) *The digital divide: Examining socio-demographic factors associated with health literacy, access and use of internet to seek health information*.
- Wagg, S. and Simeonova, B. (2021) 'A policy-level perspective to tackle rural digital inclusion', *Information Technology and People* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/ITP-01-2020-0047/FULL/XML>.
- Weritz, P. (2022) 'Hey Leaders, It's Time to Train the Workforce: Critical Skills in the Digital Workplace', *Administrative Sciences*, 12(3). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/ADMSCI12030094>.
- White, D. and Carnegie United Kingdom Trust (no date) *Digitally savvy citizens*.
- Williams, F. *et al.* (2016) "'Digital by Default" and the "hard to reach": Exploring solutions to digital exclusion in remote rural areas', *Local Economy*, 31(7). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0269094216670938>.
- Wilson, G. (Author of A. digital world for all?), Grant, A. (Senior policy and development officer) and Carnegie United Kingdom Trust. (2017) 'A digital world for all? : findings from a programme of digital inclusion for vulnerable young people across the UK', p. 68. Available at: https://d1ssu070pg2v9i.cloudfront.net/pex/carnegie_uk_trust/2017/10/NotWithoutMe-2.pdf (Accessed: 27 March 2019).
- Yates, S., Kirby, J. and Lockley, E. (2015) 'Digital media use: Differences and inequalities in relation to class and age', *Sociological Research Online*, 20(4). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5153/sro.3751>.
- Yu, R.P. *et al.* (2016) 'Mapping the two levels of digital divide: Internet access and social network site adoption among older adults in the USA', *Information Communication and Society*, 19(10). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369118X.2015.1109695>.

Appendices

Appendix A: Essential Digital Skills Toolkit (SCVO): tested during the first research cycle

This is an interactive document and can be found [here](#).

Appendix B: Co-designed Get Digital Assessment Tool used during first research cycle

Instructions: There are 20 Digital Skills in this assessment tool. Please answer Question 1 for each skill. If your answer is 'Yes', please skip Question 2 for that skill and go onto the next skill. If your answer to 'Question 1' is no, please answer Question 2 before moving onto the next skill.

Get Digital Skills Assessment

Foundation Skills	Q.1: Can you do this?	Q.2: Do you want to learn this?
1. Turn on a device I can turn on a device	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
2. Use controls on the device I can use the controls (mouse, keyboard, touch screen) to interact with the home screen & locate/open apps & programs.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
3. Accessibility tools I can use the required accessibility tools (e.g. text to speech)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
4. Connect to WiFi I can connect to a safe and secure WiFi network.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
5. Use passwords	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No

I can update my password when prompted and understand they should be kept safe and secure		
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Communicating	Q.1: Can you do this?	Q.2: Do you want to learn this?
6. Messaging Tools: I can communicate with emails and messaging tools (e.g. Gmail, WhatsApp, Messenger)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
7. Social Media: I can post on social media platforms (e.g. Facebook, Twitter)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
8. Video Calls: I can make video or audio calls (Facebook, Face Time, Skype)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No

Handling Information & Content	Q.1: Can you do this?	Q.2: Do you want to learn this?
9. Information in the Cloud: I can save information in the cloud and access it again from a different device (e.g. Google Drive, DropBox)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
10. Online entertainment: I can access online entertainment legally (e.g. Youtube, Spotify, Online Gaming)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
11. Checking online information	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No

I can check if online information is true or false (URL in Browser, Reviews, Trust Pilot)		
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Transacting	Q.1: Can you do this?	Q.2: Do you want to learn this?
12. Online Purchasing I can buy things online and know how to check if a website is safe (e.g. eBay, Amazon, Google Shopping, Tesco)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
13. Online Services I can use online services (e.g Universal Credit, JobCentre Plus or e-Citizenship)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
14. Online Banking I can use online banking websites and apps (e.g. Barclays, Bank of Scotland)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No

Problem Solving	Q.1: Can you do this?	Q.2: Do you want to learn this?
15. Online Chat I can use online chat to ask for help (Online Chat)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
16. Searching for Solutions Online I can find out how to do something online (e.g. Youtube, Google)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No

17. Online Navigation I can use online maps to help me find my way to places (Google Maps, Street View)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
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Being Safe & Legal Online	Q.1: Can you do this?	Q.2: Do you want to learn this?
18. Passwords I can create strong and secure passwords. (Account Settings/Information)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
19. Recognising suspicious weblinks I can recognise suspicious weblinks. (Browser URL)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
20. Privacy Settings I can use privacy settings to control what people see. (Account Settings)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No

How many of the above skills can you do?

Get Digital Skills	Total:	___ / 20
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How confident do you feel about engaging with the digital world?

Please rate from 1 to 5

(1 = not confident, 5 = very confident)

Confidence	Total:	___ / 5
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Appendix C : Digital Zone Fair Use Policy

By using our computer equipment, you agree that you will respect our Digital Zone rules:

X DO NOT access or share **pornographic** content

X DO NOT access any **gambling** websites, or use our computer equipment for gambling activities

X DO NOT misuse our computer equipment for any **illegal activity**, including:

X Attempting to access another person's files or accounts (i.e. **hacking**)

X Violating copyright laws and software licensing agreements (i.e. **online piracy**)

X Buying or selling **illegal products/substances** online

X **Viewing illegal material** that is against the law, including obscenity or child pornography

X DO NOT access or share any inappropriate content or information that can **cause offence** or **intimidate** others online or offline

X DO NOT **tamper with or damage** our computer equipment in any way

X DO NOT **save any personal files** onto our computer - these will be removed by staff

✓ DO give **priority** to others who have more important or immediate needs for the computer

✓ DO **respect** all Streetwork staff and other Hub users

✓ DO **respect** the computer equipment and keep the Digital Zone clean

✓ DO save your personal files onto your **personal cloud storage account**, such as Google Drive, OneDrive, Dropbox, iCloud, etc.

✓ DO **sign out** of all accounts when you finish with the computer, and **clear your browser history** in your browser settings

✓ DO **ask Streetwork staff** for help with printing, or other support

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Appendix D : Quick Wins Framework

Digital Participation

Digital participation has become an essential part of our everyday lives and is often embedded into our daily activities: socialising with friends, managing our finances, staying up to date with the latest news and watching movies.

Digital Inequality

Despite the advantages of being digitally included, not everyone has the access, skills, or confidence to get online. People experiencing homelessness are among the most digitally excluded groups in society. This is a severe disadvantage in life.

Get Everyone Connected

We want everyone to have the opportunity to get online. Our Get Connected projects aim to enable people experiencing homelessness to be included in the digital landscape and to enjoy all of the benefits that come with it.

The Get Connected Model

We provide the people we support with a digital device, unlimited connectivity and digital champion support based around the Quick Wins Framework.

Digital Champion Approach

Digital Champions play a key role in helping people to get online and enjoy the many benefits of digital inclusion. By supporting people to access the digital tools in this document, you can make a huge, positive difference in their lives.

Person Centred Support

Find out what the person would like to do in each of the key areas in this document and find a digital solution that works for them. If the person wants to connect with a family member via a messaging app – find out what platform the person’s family member uses as a messaging tool. If they use WhatsApp, it makes sense to use that platform.

Focus on 5 Key Areas

We have consulted with people who have lived experience of homelessness and frontline workers and have identified **5 Key Areas** that can deliver positive change for the people we support.

1. Communicating
2. Finding Information
3. Money Matters
4. Entertainment and Learning
5. Harm Reduction (if applicable)

Find Quick Wins

Be sure to listen to the needs of the person and find 'quick wins' in this document to help them get set up with life changing digital tools!

Staying Safe Online

Staying safe online is essential at all times and underpins all aspects of digital participation. Digital is awesome and opens up incredible opportunities for people, but we must also be aware of some of the dangers online. Please ensure you help the people you support to be safe and legal online. We have highlighted some of the key themes, and you should discuss these with participants as you work through the document with them.

Reliable and Mis-Information

Mis-Information is on the increase, this can come in the form of fraudulent or unsolicited messages, texts and emails, phishing, scams, fake news articles and/or websites. As digital champions, we need to ensure people are accessing information from reliable sources.

Example of reliable sources

- Health: NHS
- Legal Issues: Police Scotland
- Government Updates: UK and Scottish Governments
- News: BBC

Here is some great advice from Police Scotland:

Stay safe and don't:

- Reply to suspicious messages or calls
- Open links and attachments in unsolicited emails and text messages
- Share your bank card details or personal financial information

- Share news that doesn't come from official sources
- Make donations to charities with checking their authenticity
- Buy things online that seem to be sold out everywhere
- Send money up front to someone you don't know

Other Safeguarding Considerations:

Please ensure the people you support are aware of the following issues:

Data and Security

- Passwords - how to set strong passwords to secure their accounts.
- GDPR - explain very clearly what happens with personal data when using tools.
- Digital footprint : awareness of online presence and the permanence of this
- Apps - geolocation etc - how to manage this setting / turn it off.
- Cookies - understanding what cookies do and how they may use your data.

Personal Vulnerability

- Bullying - awareness that bullying and harassment can occur online (social media)
- Enabling destructive, high risk behaviour - (such as Gambling)
- Exploitation - chat rooms, catfishing, sexual exploitation (people aren't always as they seem)
- Recruitment / targeting for extremist groups etc - PREVENT strategy

Let's Get Started...

Device Controls and Features

Before we get into the Quick Wins Framework, it's really important to check that the participant can use the device controls and features listed in the table below.

Please work with the participant to ensure they can use the device:

	Device Controls and Features	Description
1.	Turn device on and off	Locate the power button
2.	Use volume controls	Locate the volume up and down buttons
3.	Connectivity	Connect to a WiFi or mobile network
4.	Securing the device	Use the lock feature and password / pin to secure the device
5.	Make and receive calls	Use keypad to call numbers and access voicemail
6.	Send and receive texts	Use text messaging app to send and receive messages
7.	Manage contacts	Add, edit and delete your contacts
8.	Take photos	Use your camera to take photos
9.	Use the Play Store	Download other apps from the play store

10.	Accessories	Highlight the range of accessories that maybe useful, (torch, calculator, voice memo, clock)
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Accessibility

Show the person the accessibility settings on the device - it can make a huge difference. Do they need a larger font? Would a coloured background make it easier to see? Try built in speech tools. Play around with the device and see what works.

Take me to the next level...

Work with the participant to select things that interest them most. Ideally pick one or two items from each Key Area to work on initially (you can add more later if required).

What would you like to do with your new device?

	I would like to....	Yes / No	Go To...
1.	Sign up for an email address		Key Area 1: Communicating (Page 5)
2.	Speak online with friends, family		Key Area 1: Communicating (Page 5)
3.	Use online to engage with other key people in my life		Key Area 1: Communicating (Page 7)
4.	Use the internet to search for things that interest me		Key Area 2: Finding information (Page 7)
5.	Be able to search for important information from reliable sources		Key Area 2: Finding information (Page 7)
6.	Manage my money online		Key area 3: Money matters (Page 9)
7.	Making my money go further		Key area 3: Money matters (Page 9)
8.	Shopping online		Key area 3: Money matters (Page 9)

9.	Keep myself entertained accessing Music		Key area 4: Entertainment and Learning (Page 12)
10.	Keep myself entertained accessing Video		Key area 4: Entertainment and Learning (Page 12)
11.	Keep myself entertained accessing Games		Key area 4: Entertainment and Learning (Page 12)
12.	Keep myself entertained accessing Reading materiel		Key area 4: Entertainment and Learning (Page 12)
13.	Learn new things		Key area 4: Entertainment and Learning (Page 12)
14.	Use online tools to stay safe and well		Key Area 5: Harm reduction (Page 15)
15.	Stay safe and legal in the digital world		Digital safeguarding (Page 2)

Key Area 1: Communicating

“Communication leads to community”

Help people to connect with the people and organisations in their life using these digital communication tools. There are many ready made digital communication tools to help us stay in touch such as email, messaging and video calls. They help to reduce social isolation and help people to access support.

Use a person centred approach to find out if any of the tools below would be useful. Do they have easy access to this kind of tool? Would it be helpful to speak with friends and family?? Do they know how to use it?

Think about using a messaging method that you both like to use to connect with each other, you can then continue to meet digitally using the preferred method going forward

Quick Wins

Quick Win	Tools	Notes and Ideas	How can it help?
Email	Gmail https://support.google.com/mail/answer/56256?hl=en-GB	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gmail is recommended. Google accounts include access to other digital tools: G Drive, Docs, Sheets, Slides, Contacts, Hangouts • An email is required for most online accounts. 	<p>Reduce social isolation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Connecting with family & friends • Making new online friends <p>Contact Homelessness Provider:</p>
Text and voice Messaging	WhatsApp https://www.whatsapp.com/ (App)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Messaging apps are great for staying in touch with people (such as friends, family, support workers etc (Highly recommended quick win) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital Champions • Support workers <p>Access services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social services • Medical Professionals • Schools (if children present) <p>Enable financial support</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Banks • Universal credit • CAB
	Messenger https://en-gb.facebook.com/reg/ (App)		
	Phone Text Messaging		
Video Calls	Teams https://www.microsoft.com/en-gb/microsoft-teams/group-chat-software Messenger https://en-gb.facebook.com/reg/ (App) WhatsApp https://www.whatsapp.com/ (App)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Video calls really help to reduce social isolation as this maintains face to face contact 	<p>Contact Accommodation Admin:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Landlord • Housing association <p>Access Emergency support:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Women's Aid • Samaritans • AA • CAMHS • SAMH

	<p>Zoom https://zoom.us/signin</p> <p>Google Hangouts / Meet google.com/hangouts</p>		
<p>Social Media</p>	<p>Facebook facebook.com</p> <p>Twitter twitter.com/home</p> <p>Instagram instagram.com</p> <p>Tik-Tok tiktok.com</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social media can be a great communication tool, each platform has a variety of tools aimed at helping people connect. 	

Key Area 2: Finding Information

“Knowledge is power”

Finding out information in an instant is an incredibly powerful tool. Help the people you support to learn how to find out information from reliable sources when they need it.

Can people search for information on Google? Do they know how to find out the latest news? Show people how they can check things out and get information from reliable sources.

Quick Wins			
Quick Win	Tools	Notes and Ideas	How can it help?
General Information	Google https://www.google.co.uk/?safe=active&su=on	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Add the Google Search App to the home screen for quick access	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• You can ask google ANYTHING: who is Scotland’s highest goalscorer? Who wrote War and Peace?

	<p>Duck Duck Go</p> <p>duckduckgo.com/</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> An alternative search engine for people who would rather not use Google (this will need to be installed on their device if they want to use this) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Remember - not everything you read online is true!
<p>Misinformation: Ensure the people you support are aware of 'misinformation'. There are many fake news sites and scams circulating online. Always access information from a reliable source.</p> <p>See about this in the 'Digital Safeguarding' section on page 2. You may wish to demonstrate unreliable websites and examples of misinformation.</p>			
Health Information	<p>NHS Scotland</p> <p>nhsinform.scot/</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Add important websites to favourites / bookmarks so it's easy to revisit. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Received up to date, accurate and reliable health information.
	<p>NHS Near Me</p> <p>nearme.scot</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> You need an appointment to use this service. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A video consultation service allowing people to speak with health professionals. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Connect with health professionals in your own time and space.
Simon Community Scotland Websites	<p>Simon Community</p> <p>simonscotland.org/g-et-support/</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Add this as a bookmark to access the information you need quickly and easily. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Find out all of the latest news, and information about the services we offer.
Support Services Information	<p>Street Support</p> <p>streetsupport.net/</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Access local advice and support services for people experiencing homelessness in Edinburgh and Glasgow. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A one stop shop to find support services that can help you in your local area at a time that works for you.
Government Updates	<p>Scottish Government</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Find up to date information on Government laws, guidelines, safety protocols, updates, and

	<p>https://www.gov.scot/</p> <p>Local Authority</p> <p>Find your local authority website online.</p>		<p>entitlements.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Find out when your bins are collected and many other services from your local authority
<p>BBC Media</p>	<p>BBC Website</p> <p>bbc.co.uk</p> <p>(TV Licence Required)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Wellbeing Advice: Avoid tracking the news 24/7. Try checking the latest news at specific times in a day - it can increase mental health & wellbeing. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Stay up to date with what's going on around the world: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ News ○ Sport ○ Culture ○ Weather ○ Entertainment and Learning (see Key Area 4)

Key Area 3: Money Matters

“Budgeting makes the things that excite you possible”

Accessing digital tools that give people instant and accurate visibility of their financial situation helps people to be more in control of their lives and take positive steps. This includes being able to easily manage bank accounts, access benefits, budget, manage debt, find the best prices and shop online.

Do people have a bank account? Can they access it through a banking app? Can they claim and manage their benefits online? Can they compare prices and shop online?

Quick Wins			
Quick Win	Tools	Notes and Ideas	How can it help?
Online Banking	Existing user of banking services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Help someone find and download their bank's App to their phone / laptop or access online. Discuss security issues. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Autonomy and control Access to finances Ability to pay for goods and services online Budgeting from within the app
	Accessing banking services for the first time	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> If someone does not have a bank account and would like to open one - follow this process: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> xxx 	Opening a bank account helps
	PayPal paypal.com	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> When someone has a bank account they can then register with Paypal, and can then click the 'paypal' button when making purchases. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Alternative way to store money online and pay for things. Easy, secure checkout experience when purchasing online
Managing	Universal Credit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Supporting people to 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Being aware of what financial support

Benefit Claims	gov.uk/apply-universal-credit	manage their own benefits online through the government portal.	<p>is available, the universal credit helper tool is a simple step by step guide to applying for universal credit.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Once set up with an online universal credit account then managing claims becomes far easier Other benefits can be accessed through the Government benefits portal, This contains a full list of benefits that might be available to someone together with links to calculators to work out what a person's entitlement could be.
	Universal credit helper tool https://uc-helper.co.uk/scvo/home		
	Benefits www.gov.uk/browse/benefits		
Budgeting	Money Helper https://www.moneyhelper.org.uk/en/everyday-money/budgeting?source=mas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> For people who would like to have more control over their money then there are useful budgeting tools online, working through a budget planner with someone helps them understand their financial position. 	
Debt management	Money advice service https://www.moneyadviceservice.org.uk/	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The money advice service offers money advice 24 hours a day online and it also can be accessed by using a freephone number on 0800 138 7777 (open weekdays) 	
Online Purchasing	Tesco www.tesco.com Asda asda.com Sainsbury's	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> For some people home food delivery can be a lifeline, it enables food to be delivered to a person's door without the need to go to the supermarket. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Convenient - no need to leave the house to get supplies in the case of deliveroo, Uber eats and Just eat supplies can be delivered in under an hour (in larger cities) Requires a bank account to access.

	sainsburys.co.uk		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can be more expensive than shopping yourself due to delivery charges. • The range of products available are infinite • Hot food can be delivered to your door very quickly
	Amazon amazon.co.uk	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Purchase almost anything and have it delivered to your door! 	
	Takeaway food just-eat.co.uk deliveroo.co.uk ubereats.com	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Get take away food and essential groceries delivered to your house. (not available in all locations) 	
Saving money online	Money Saving expert https://www.moneysavingexpert.com/	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A great website that covers loads of topics, all based around saving money from shopping deals to reducing household bills. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • People in general do not like to shop around, they tend to stick with the same provider. Unfortunately doing this leads to people missing out on the best deals. We should always encourage people to shop around when making purchases and these websites are designed to help with this
Energy and Internet	USwitch https://www.uswitch.com/	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A website that compares prices across a variety of providers with the aim of reducing household energy, broadband and mobile deals. 	

Key Area 4: Entertainment and Learning

“I’m still learning” - Michelangelo (aged 87)

Digital can offer many different forms of entertainment for fun, learning and to stay well. Support people to access online entertainment that interests them!

How is the person currently keeping themselves entertained, active and learning?

Do they like reading? Exercising? Arts and crafts? Playing games? Watching movies?

Look for some sites, tools and apps that could help!

Quick Wins: Entertainment and Learning			
Quick Win	Tool	Notes and Ideas	How can it help?
Watching	Youtube Youtube.com	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Search for something you’re interested in and see what comes up: music, comedy, or sporting moments. • Keeping well: Search for health and wellbeing, yoga, meditation, healthy eating recipes and instructional videos, workouts. • Online Classes - learn a new skill: yoga, cooking, guitar, knitting, DIY 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Find something to laugh about. • Be in a good frame of mind, be fit and healthy and eat well. • Reduce boredom / pass time when you maybe feeling a bit lonely or isolated • Most content is on demand, so can be, watched when you like (On demand includes TV programmes, box sets, movies, documentaries, music videos etc.)
	Vimeo* vimeo.com	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A video resource to share and watch video content. 	
	BBC iPlayer bbc.co.uk/iplayer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Content on demand: gives access to TV programmes, box sets, movies, documentaries, music videos etc from the BBC and ITV 	
	STV Player		

Listening	Netflix* netflix.com	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Offers a wide range of entertainment including original content 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Beware that many streaming services are offered on a subscription basis so to watch them you would need to pay a monthly fee, this typically can cost between £10 and £12 a months, some services offer introductory offers so look out for these. Listening to podcasts and audiobooks is a great way to pass time and be entertained. You can do this while doing other things too like working out, going for a walk or housework. You can stop listening at anytime, and easily return to where you left off when you are ready to continue.
	Amazon* https://www.amazon.co.uk/amazonprime	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Amazon Prime streaming is included in the Amazon subscription which includes free parcel delivery. 	
	Disney Plus* disneyplus.com	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Offers a wide range of entertainment including original content 	
	Britbox* https://watch.britbox.co.uk/	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Includes lots of old BBC, ITV, and Channel 4 content. 	
	BBC Sounds bbc.co.uk/sounds	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> BBC Sounds gives free access to all BBC radio shows and podcasts. 	
	Google Podcasts Podcasts.google.com	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Another resource offering access to loads of Podcast content much of it free. 	
	Spotify https://accounts.spotify.com/en/login	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A music streaming service, the free version contains lots of content. There is a subscription to access the full content 	
	Audible* audible.co.uk	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Carry thousands of books on one device!, some free content and good introductory offers. 	
	Kindle* amazon.co.uk	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Works in a similar way to Audible, some free content. 	
	Websites	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Search google for free online games 	

Play	SmartPhone Apps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Google Play Games, many of them are free. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Online gaming can be a way to connect with others with similar interests Some games are designed to keep the brain active and these can be good for mental health Whilst many games are free to play, users should be aware of in-game purchases, accessing these could unknowingly charge a registered bank card. Education: such as learning a language, brushing up on English and Maths, exploring a hobby for example can be great ways of using the power of digital, there are many resources available to suit every interest and learning style.
	Video Games*	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> For more serious gaming, games consoles are the device of choice, these can be expensive. 	
Learn	TedTalks ted.com/talks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ted talks cover a large variety of subjects and are informative and free to listen to. 	
	Blogs, articles, website	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Blog: 10 websites where you can read books online for free: https://ebookfriendly.com/sites-where-you-can-read-books-online/ Blog: Top 10 Podcasts of All Time https://screenrant.com/best-top-podcasts-all-time/ 	
	Open University https://www.open.edu/openlearn/	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A resource full of free courses catering for a range of abilities 	

	BBC ESOL https://www.bbc.co.uk/learningenglish/	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A BBC resource to support people learning English. 	
	Duolingo www.duolingo.com/courses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is there a language you've always wanted to learn? Or one you'd like to brush up on? 	

*Paid content

Key Area 5: Harm Reduction

“The opposite of addiction is not sobriety, it’s connection”

Harm reduction is an approach which aims to reduce the harm associated with people’s substance use, or any behaviours that may cause harm to a person, without expecting a person to stop that behaviour in order to access support. Harm Reduction is grounded in human rights and social justice and focuses on ensuring people have access to the information, advice, and support so they can make informed decisions about their health and their lives.

The By My Side app provides people with access to evidenced based harm reduction resources and services - supporting people to stay well and make informed choices around their health and wellbeing.

Do people have access to information they need to keep themselves safe and well?

Use a person centred approach to empower the person using the app to access resources and services that are relevant to them on their support journey.

Quick Wins			
Quick Win	Tools	Notes and Ideas	How can it help?
	Local Services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The By My Side app features a range of local services within Glasgow. 	Access the services you need including directions and contact details. Watch a ‘Virtual Hello’ from a service provider to learn about what their support looks like and what they can offer.
	Check On Me	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This is a safety feature to enable a text message to be sent to a chosen person asking them to do a safety check 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Send a text to a person of your choice so they can check on you - we want you to be safe.
	How am I Feeling?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This is an interactive feature designed for daily use allowing each person to ‘check in’ and track their mood. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Track your wellbeing through a 7 day log. A tool you can use in keywork sessions and reviews with your Support Worker.

Note: See the ‘Digital Safeguarding’ section on page 8.

Additional Resources

Here is a list of resources that may be useful during the coronavirus pandemic:

Scam Share

Trading Standards Scotland - Learn about the most recent scams related to Coronavirus:

<https://mailchi.mp/c393189962ca/scam-share-latest-covid-19-scams?e=600ac59ddf>

Police Scotland

Shut Out Scammers

<https://www.scotland.police.uk/keep-safe/personal-safety/shut-out-scammers>

Learn My Way guides

Very clear, use plain English and would be usable in this context (when adapted etc) but subject to intellectual property agreements, as would similar resources from Digital Unite.

<https://www.learnmyway.com/subjects>

Tips for Digital Champions:

Three top tips for digital champions supporting people during the coronavirus pandemic.

<https://www.digitalunite.com/news-reviews/three-top-tips-virtual-digital-champions>

Free Food List:

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1tdB8vrJI7kavZqlppCoaLQM0mLWsK4Qx82s5Yg5J1w4/edit#gid=0>

Services Directory (Glasgow Only):

<https://www.glasgowhelps.org/Corona Checks>

Contact Us

Please get in touch if you would like to:

- Discuss something about Get Digital Scotland
- Get some advice on best practice
- Share an idea about digital inclusion
- Share some useful resources

We would love to hear from you!